

THE OSTEOLOGY AND PHYLOGENY OF THE
CHAETODONTIDAE (TELEOSTEI:
PERCIFORMES)

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by

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Preface to the Electronic Version

The two printed copies of this dissertation were submitted to the University of Hawaii Graduate Division in October of 1988. Since then this work has been available only by visiting the UH Library at Manoa, or later through the University of Michigan Dissertation Archive. The Archive, however, provides only a smaller format in which illustrations and half-tone figures are not well reproduced. Because of its limited availability and poor reproduction, this work has been ignored for most part, but more recently it was somewhat misunderstood. To remedy this situation, the dissertation is reproduced here in electronic form.

The text in this electronic version was produced from the near-original Word Perfect 4.2 files, which were then converted to Word 2000. Because several of my source files had file dates later than October, 1988, indicating the contents might have been modified, the text reproduced here was compared, page by page, to the paper original. My goal in most sections was to keep the text exactly as it was in the original; only typographical errors and formatting errors were corrected. The one deviation from the original I have admitted by intention is the addition of permanent catalog numbers for the material examined. My personal collection (SDB) was deposited and cataloged at AMNH after I submitted the dissertation. The AMNH numbers have been added to the figure captions and the Material Examined (Appendix A) because I believe these references to voucher material are more important than fidelity to the original. Adding the catalog numbers caused the text to be longer than in the original, so I reduced the spacing between lines to keep the total number of pages in Appendix A consistent with the original. Still, the exact pagination departs from the original. Again, minor formatting inconsistencies were corrected in Appendix A.

Illustrations (line art) and black and white photographs were digitized with different protocols. Illustrations were scanned as binary images (single bit color depth) at 1200 dpi. The resulting TIFF images were then placed in Word documents and converted to PDF. Conversion to PDF then reduced binary images to 300 dpi. Black and white photographs (scanning electron micrographs) were scanned at 600 dpi. A small amount of touch up work was done to remove scratches and dust. Conversion to PDF then reduced their resolution to 150 dpi.

– *S.D. Blum*, August 22, 2003

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ABSTRACT

The phylogenetic position of the Chaetodontidae among percoid fishes, and the relationships among chaetodontid genera and subgenera are inferred from cladistic analyses of anatomy. The Pomacanthidae and Chaetodontidae are shown to be sister-taxa by four characters that are either unique or rare among deep-bodied percoids (most notably the organization of jaw tooth replacement). The second outgroup of the Chaetodontidae contains the Ehippididae (including Drepane), Scatophagidae, Siganidae, Luvarus, Zanclus, and the Acanthuridae (modified after Tyler et al., MS). These taxa and other deep-bodied percoids were examined in order to polarize characters that vary among chaetodontids.

Twenty-two osteologically distinct genera and subgenera are recognized among the Chaetodontidae: Amphichaetodon, Chelmonops, Chelmon, Coradion, Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, Hemitaurichthys, Prognathodes, Roa, Chaetodon, Rabdophorus, Roaops, Exornator, Lepidochaetodon, Parachaetodon, Megaprotodon, Gonochaetodon, Tetrachaetodon, Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus. Certain species of Chaetodon are realigned among subgenera in order to keep these taxa from being polyphyletic.

Fourteen inter-nested monophyletic groups are identified by shared derived characters. Amphichaetodon is shown to be the most primitive chaetodontid taxon. Chelmonops, Chelmon, Coradion, form a monophyletic group, as

do Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys. These groups are shown to be sister taxa. Chaetodon sensu Burgess is shown to be paraphyletic unless Parachaetodon is included as a subgenus. A new "otophysic" connection (between the swimbladder and lateral line at the supracleithrum) is described, and found in Parachaetodon and all subgenera of Chaetodon sensu Burgess except the more primitive Prognathodes and Roa. It is recommended that the latter two taxa be recognized as genera, and that Megaprotodon and Gonochaetodon continue to be recognized as subgenera of Chaetodon.

A morphometric analysis of body shape among 18 species (comprising five closely related subgenera of Chaetodon) was performed in an attempt to further resolve their interrelationships. Four size-free shape variables were derived using sheared principal components analysis. Continuous shape variables were converted into discrete characters (for phylogenetic analysis) by generalized gap coding. Consistency among the discrete shape characters was low, and the resultant cladograms were not robust to the choice of gap size. No further cladistic resolution was achieved with the morphometric methods.

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CHAPTER I
INTRODUCTION

The Chaetodontidae are a diverse family of circumglobally distributed marine percoid fishes with representatives on virtually every coral reef system in the world. Their conspicuous and species-specific color patterns have attracted the attention of marine biologists throughout history. Their diurnal habits, and epi-benthic, shallow-water distributions make them tractable subjects for testing broadly applicable models in biology. Since the comprehensive literature review by Burgess (1978), and supplementary bibliography in Allen (1980), workers have continued to address diverse aspects of chaetodontid biology, including: ecological distributions and feeding behaviors (Anderson et al., 1981; Birkland and Neudecker, 1981; Bouchon-Navaro, 1979, 1986; Findley and Findley, 1985; Harmelin-Vivien and Bouchon-Navaro, 1981, 1983; Lasker, 1985; Ralston, 1981; Reese, 1981; and Tricas, 1985), functional morphology (Motta, 1982, 1985, 1987), mating systems (Lobel and Neudecker, 1982), color patterns (Erlich et al., 1977; Kelley and Hourigan, 1983), visual biology (Snow and Rylander, 1981), and interspecific hybridization

(Randall et al., 1977; Randall and Fridman, 1981; and Sano et al., 1984). In many of these studies, hypotheses of adaptation (i.e. specialization, optimization, etc.) were tested using the comparative method.

In a concise, statistically-framed exposition, Felsenstein (1983) demonstrated that the inferential power of comparative studies can be severely diminished by a lack of independence among observations (i.e. species). The distributions of attributes among species may be correlated for historical reasons (common descent) as well as adaptive ones. The only way to distinguish between historical and adaptive causes is to compare species whose attributes have arisen independently. A corroborated phylogenetic hypothesis must be used to design such comparisons. However, a comprehensive phylogenetic hypothesis of the Chaetodontidae does not exist. All previous classifications of the family were derived using classical (inexplicit) or phenetic methods.

The most widely accepted classification of the Chaetodontidae is that of Burgess (1978), who recognized 114 valid species among 10 genera. He placed most of these species (90) among 13 subgenera within the genus Chaetodon Linnaeus 1758. In addition to establishing the validity of chaetodontid species known at that time, Burgess altered chaetodontid nomenclature by relegating three commonly recognized genera, Prognathodes Gill 1862, Megaprotodon

Guichenot 1848, and Gonochaetodon Bleeker 1876, to subgeneric status within the large genus Chaetodon.

From the time Burgess completed his revision (nearly ten years before its publication) to the present, five new species have been described, Chaetodon (Prognathodes) guezei Maugé and Bauchot 1976, Chaetodon (Roa) flavocoronatus Meyers 1980, Chaetodon (Prognathodes) obliquus Lubbock and Edwards 1980, Chaetodon (Roa) guyotensis Yamamoto and Tameka (in Okamura et al.) 1982, and Chelmonops curiosus Kuitert 1986 (subgeneric placements according to the authors). Additionally, Allen and Kuitert (1978) elevated Heniochus diphreutes Jordan 1903 from synonymy with H. acuminatus Linnaeus 1758, and Klausewitz and Fricke (1985) the specific distinctions among Chaetodon (Roa) modestus Schlegel 1842, C. excelsa (Jordan) 1921, and C. jayakari Norman 1839. Although these authors followed Burgess in their classifications of new species, the consensus among systematists concerning chaetodontid taxonomy has been declining.

Three reviews of the family have appeared since Burgess completed his revision. Nalbant (1973) was unaware of Burgess's dissertation, but nevertheless created an alignment of species that deviated only moderately from Burgess's, without describing any new supraspecific taxa. Allen (1980) followed Burgess (1978) in most regards explicitly for the sake of stability, but placed Chaetodon

(Roa) excelsa (Jordan) 1922 and C. (R.) jayakari Norman 1939 into synonymy with C. (R.) modestus Schlegel 1842, and moved C. reticulatus Cuvier 1831 from the subgenus Citharoedus Kaup 1860 to the subgenus Chaetodontops Bleeker 1876 without comment.

Maugé and Bauchot (1984), on the other hand, used the data reported by Burgess (1978) and a variety of phenetic clustering techniques to produce a classification that differed markedly from all preceding ones. They described four new genera, six new subgenera, and drastically realigned species within existing higher taxa. Realignments often involved the placement of sibling species in different genera and subgenera (e.g. Rabdophorus fasciatus [Forsskal] 1775 - Chaetodontops lunula [Lacepede] 1803, and Heterochaetodon [Heterochaetodon] assarius [Waite] 1905 - H. [Burgessius] miliaris [Quoy and Gaimard] 1824), and the grouping of species that are outwardly very dissimilar (e.g. Megaprotodon trifascialis [Quoy and Gaimard] 1825, M. blackburni [Desjardins] 1836, and M. plebeius [Cuvier] 1831). Maugé and Bauchot (1984) intended to create an objective, and therefore, stable taxonomy, but their results were so bizarre that confusion will be the more likely result.

Subsequent authors have not accepted the taxonomy of Maugé and Bauchot (1984), but neither have the universally accepted that of Burgess (1978). Nalbant commented (1984,

p. 239) that "Chaetodon (sensu Burgess, 1978) represents a rather composite genus which includes too many evolutive trends and is not a natural unity". Nalbant (1986) has since advocated the recognition of Prognathodes, Roa Jordan 1923, and Roaops Maugé and Bauchot 1984, as genera. As noted by Reese (1981) others continue to use Megaprotodon Guichenot 1848 and Gonochaetodon Bleeker 1876 as generic names. None of the various positions on chaetodontid classification have been argued from a well supported hypothesis of their phylogeny.

The central objective of this study was to produce a phylogenetic hypothesis of the Chaetodontidae that can stabilize their nomenclature, and guide comparative investigation of their biology. Osteological differences among species groups provided most of the evidence for relationships, and the methods of analysis or interpretation were cladistic (sensu Hennig, 1966; as extended and discussed by numerous authors, including Farris et al., 1970; Farris, 1970, 1982, 1983; Patterson, 1983; and Maddison et al., 1984).

The fundamental tenet of cladistics is that common ancestry can only be inferred from derived character states.

Two methods of distinguishing primitive and derived character states have been promoted vigorously in the literature, the ontogenetic method (e.g. Nelson, 1978, 1985; Patterson, 1983) and outgroup comparison (e.g. Watrous and

Wheeler, 1981; Farris, 1982; and Maddison et al., 1984). Of these, the latter is more widely used because it is often difficult to obtain adequate ontogenetic series for most taxa and characters. Moreover, de Queiroz (1985) has argued that ontogenetic transformations should be used as character, and not as the method for polarizing character states seen in adults. In the analyses presented here, characters were polarized exclusively by outgroup comparison.

Maddison et al., (1984, p. 91, fig. 10A) have shown that if two or more of the ingroup character states also occur among the outgroups, and the relationships among the outgroup taxa are unresolved, the primitive ingroup character state cannot be determined by parsimony. They have also shown that if the relationships among the outgroups are known, polarization may be possible, even in the face of such outgroup variability. Outgroup comparison is thus most effective when outgroup relationships are as broad and resolved as possible. The central analysis of relationships within the Chaetodontidae is preceded by a phylogenetic analysis of chaetodontid outgroups, i.e. percoid families that have traditionally been regarded as their closest relatives.

The osteological survey of the Chaetodontidae shows that qualitative skeletal evolution has not kept pace with speciation; many species have skeletons that are virtually

identical. Consequently, osteology does not provide the data necessary to estimate relationships within groups of closely related species. However, all valid species exhibit a unique combination of color pattern, meristics (scale, fin-ray, and fin-spine counts), and body shape. Resources were not available to study all features in all species, but variation in body shape was analyzed in a group of 18 closely related species.

In contrast to the qualitative osteological (discrete) data sets that were used in the outgroup and main ingroup analyses, the morphometric data set contains more than 70 metric (continuous) variables. Two intermediate analyses were required to make the raw morphometric amenable to cladistic analysis. Redundancy among the continuous variables, and covariation due to growth were "removed" by sheared principal components analysis (Humphries et al., 1981). The resultant continuous variables, which describe size-free shape differences within and among species, were translated into discrete characters by the generalized gap coding method of Archie (1985). The discrete characters were then submitted to a standard cladistic analysis, comparable to those used in the osteological analyses.

The species in the morphometric analysis belong to six subgenera that form a monophyletic group within Chaetodon. Species within subgenera are osteologically identical, but subgenera within the larger group are distinct. The

osteological data thus provide a basal sequence of relationships among the species groups, and a standard of reference for evaluating the results of the morphometric data and methods.

CHAPTER II

OUTGROUP RELATIONSHIPS OF THE CHAETODONTIDAE

Introduction

Candidates for outgroup taxa were selected from published systematic works. Characters used by previous authors to support relationships of the Chaetodontidae to other families were reviewed in a cladistic context. The interpretations of morphology made by these authors were reconciled against my own examination of material, and new characters were discovered in the osteological survey of deep-bodied percoids. Characters were polarized by comparison to a general outgroup, the suborder Percoidei (sensu Johnson, 1984). The cladistic analysis of characters was numerical, and a branch and bound algorithm (Hendy and Penny, 1982; implementation by D.L. Swofford, 1985) was used to reveal all maximally parsimonious trees.

Previous Works: Candidates for Outgroup Taxa and Characters

Highly compressed, deep-bodied, marine percoids were first united into a single taxon, the Squamipennes, by Cuvier (1827, p. 171). The original Squamipennes contained

13 genera that are now placed among the families Chaetodontidae, Pomacanthidae, Ehippididae, Monodactylidae, Sparidae, Coracinidae, Bramidae, Pempheridae, and Toxotidae.

A suprafamilial taxon more or less equivalent to Cuvier's Squamipennes has appeared irregularly in subsequent comprehensive systematic works. (If the Squamipennes was omitted, its members were simply included as members of the Percoidei.) An excellent review of the literature concerning squamipennian fishes is contained in Burgess (1978). Burgess also noted that some authors had suggested relationships between the Chaetodontidae and non-squamipennian fishes, such as the Antigoniidae (Jordan, 1924; Boulenger, 1904), and Acanthuridae (e.g. Gregory, 1933). Since Burgess's review, four studies have more or less specifically addressed relationships among these families (Mok and Shen, 1983; Rosen, 1984; Gosline, 1985; and Tyler et al., MS).

Mok and Shen (1983) made an osteological survey of the Squamipennes and presented a cladistic hypothesis of their relationships (Fig. 1). While their study encompassed a wide range of osteological systems, their conclusions were compromised by several problems. Nodes on their cladogram were supported by at most three characters, and many concerned minute structural details. The phylogenetic significance of these potentially trivial characters was not supported by a thorough analysis of within-group variation.

Fig. 1. Relationships among the Squamipennes Proposed by Mok and Shen (1983).

Several of the more substantial characters were diagnosed incorrectly, and still others were polarized incorrectly. These errors are discussed by Tyler et al. (MS), and in the character descriptions below. Mok and Shen claimed that their phylogenetic hypothesis is most parsimonious, but they did not make explicit interpretations of conflicting characters. Therefore, the assertion that their cladogram is most parsimonious cannot be evaluated.

Rosen (1984) examined the relationships among the Zeiformes, Plectognathi (Tetraodontiformes plus Triacanthoidei), and a variety of deep-bodied percoids. His conclusions are relevant to chaetodontid relationships because plectognaths were previously viewed as acanthurid derivatives, and acanthurids were viewed as "chaetodontoid" derivatives (eg. Gregory, 1933). Rosen proposed that the traditional Zeiformes is paraphyletic without the Plectognathi. Having concluded that the Acanthuridae are not related to the Plectognathi, Rosen briefly addressed the question of acanthurid relationships. He interpreted Tyler's (1970) remarks to mean that the Siganidae have no special relationship to the Acanthuridae, and searched for a more likely sister group of to the Acanthuridae among other squamipennians. He examined several characters (sequentially, not simultaneously) and eliminated from further consideration those taxa that have more primitive character states than acanthurids. He tentatively proposed a chaetodontid-acanthurid sister group relationship, and

supported it with their common possession of: 1) fewer than three predorsal bones, 2) small pharyngobranchials with filiform teeth, 3) a closed beryciform foramen on the anterior ceratohyal (but see Fig. 20), and 4) a peculiar ceratohyal-hypohyal articulation (incorrectly described). As will be shown below, the correctly diagnosed characters do not support a sister group relationship between the Acanthuridae and Chaetodontidae.

Gosline (1985) reviewed the osteology of "deep-bodied percoids". His study group differed from Mok and Shen's by the inclusion of the Oplegnathidae, Labracoglossidae, and by the exclusion of the Enoplosidae, Toxotidae, and the Acanthuroidei. Gosline's rejection of cladistic methodology was evident in his conclusions. He stated that deep-bodied percoids probably do not form a natural group because he found no evidence that they do. In order to support this conclusion cladistically, he would have had to show that some members of his "deep-bodied percoids" are more closely related to other percoids that are not deep-bodied. A more appropriate conclusion to draw from no evidence would have been no conclusion.

Despite the potential lack of monophyly, Gosline concluded that there are three smaller "natural" groups within the assemblage. He defined one group (his 1a: Kyphosidae, Scorpididae, Labracoglossidae, Girellidae,

Oplegnathidae, Scatophagidae, Pomacanthidae, Chaetodontidae, and Monodactylidae) as deep-bodied percoids with large epiotic apophyses, and coracoids with anterior extensions that meet the tips of the cleithra mid-ventrally. He then defined the coordinate group (1b: Ehippididae and Drepanidae) by the absence of these features. Thus, he used both the primitive and derived states of the same character to diagnose coordinate groups. Within the context of his study, at most only half of this information can be used to infer relationships because the other half necessarily represents symplesiomorphy.

Gosline recognized a third natural group as a subdivision of group 1a. He separated the Monodactylidae from the remainder of that group on the basis of three peculiar features: rudimentary pelvic fins, the supraoccipital crest extending on to preorbital area, and a swim bladder with large posterior extensions on either side of the hemal spines. Again, his observations have little relevance to the interrelationships among these fishes because the derived conditions are autapomorphic.

Tyler et al. (MS) presented a hypothesis of relationships among what they termed the higher Squamipennes (the Pomacanthidae, Chaetodontidae, Drepanidae, Ehippididae, Scatophagidae, Siganidae, Luvaridae, Zanclidae, and Acanthuridae; Fig. 2). Tyler et al. supported the monophyly of this group with seven

synapomorphies: 1) the presence of a foramen in the pelvic bone between the articulating processes of the pelvic spine, 2) pharyngobranchials with comma-shaped tooth plates bearing filiform teeth (except scatophagids, which possess large tooth plates), 3) six or fewer branchiostegal rays, 4) a variously developed bony or cartilaginous parashpenoidal apophysis, 5) a vacant interneural space among the precaudal vertebrae (two neural spines without an intervening pterygiophore), 6) the absence of a tooth plate on the second epibranchial, and 7) the absence of dorsal and anal fin stays (osseous or cartilaginous elements just posterior to the last pterygiophores).

Mok and Shen (1983) proposed a similar higher squamipennian clade, but also included the Pentacerotidae within it. Mok and Shen supported their clade with only one feature, the structure of the pelvic spine articulation, which they divided into a three-state transformation series: pelvic foramen absent (most primitive), foramen present, and pelvic spine interlocked through the foramen. They included the Pentacerotidae in this clade because pentacerotids have the most derived state, an interlocked pelvic spine. Tyler et al. regarded the pentacerotid condition as convergent because pentacerotids lack all of the other higher squamipennian characters listed above.

Tyler et al. accepted the hypothesis of Starks (1926) that the Chaetodontidae, Pomacanthidae, and Drepane form a

Fig. 2. Relationships among the Higher Squamipennes
Proposed by Tyler et al. (MS).

monophyletic group because these taxa share a unique ethmoid structure. They hypothesized that the sister group of the chaetodontid-pomacanthid-Drepane group is a clade containing, in ascending sequence, the Ephippididae, Scatophagidae, Siganidae, Luvarus, Zanclus, and Acanthuridae. This second clade is united by seven synapomorphies, of which, five are unreversed non-reductive specializations, one is reversed within the group, and one is a reduction (loss). These characters are discussed below in the character analysis.

Tyler et al. hypothesized that the scatophagids are the sister-group to the Acanthuroidei (Siganidae, Luvarus, Zanclus, and Acanthuridae) on the basis of two reductions, which are also discussed below. They stated that it is possible to interpret two additional reductive features as synapomorphies at this level, but because homoplasy has occurred higher in the group, character reconstructions that place the transformations at different nodes are equally parsimonious. These features are loss of the parietals (absent in scatophagids and siganids, but present in Luvarus (larvae only), Zanclus, acanthurids, and most other teleosts), and loss of a principal caudal fin ray (16 in scatophagids, Luvarus, Zanclus, and acanthurids, but 17 in other percoids and siganids). In their scheme, only the reconstructions of these characters can vary, not the cladistic positions of the Scatophagidae and Siganidae. This is because the family Siganidae is shown to be the

sister-group of all other acanthuroids by 11 synapomorphies.

The relationships proposed by Tyler et al. within the Acanthuroidei are not discussed here because they are well supported and do not significantly affect the outgroup relationships of the Chaetodontidae.

There are, however, several character conflicts that argue against the relationships near the base of the cladogram proposed by Tyler et al. Most of these conflicts are created by the peculiar combination of derived character states that occur in Drepane. Tyler et al. did not discuss the characters that conflict with their placement of Drepane. As will be shown below, these conflicting characters are numerous enough to alter the position of Drepane, and thereby, the outgroup relationships of the Chaetodontidae.

Taxa Included in the Analysis of Outgroup Relationships

I have followed Tyler et al. by assuming that their higher Squamipennes is a monophyletic group, and that this group contains the Chaetodontidae and their closest relatives: the Pomacanthidae, Drepane, Ehippididae, Scatophagidae, and Acanthuroidei. I have excluded from this analysis several of the families that were included by Mok and Shen (1983) and Gosline (1985): the Toxotidae,

Enoplosidae, Girellidae, Labracoglossidae, Monodactylidae, Oplegnathidae, and Pentacerotidae. These taxa were excluded because they lack the synapomorphies that Tyler et al. used to diagnose the higher Squamipennes. Microcanthus (Scorpididae) was included only to illustrate the closest possible comparison between a lower squamipennian and the Chaetodontidae (Microcanthus was placed in the Chaetodontidae as recently as Ahl, 1923). Kyphosus (Kyphosidae) was included in order to show that Microcanthus and other scorpidids probably have closer affinities to percoids that are not members of the higher Squamipennes.

Rosen's (1984) description of zeiform morphology and his hypothesis of zeiform-tetraodontiform relationship imply that the Zeiformes and Tetraodontiformes might be derived from within the higher Squamipennes. Moreover, even if Rosen's zeiform-tetraodontiform hypothesis were rejected, tetraodontiforms have traditionally been allied with the higher Squamipennes (i.e. the acanthurids). The exclusion of the Zeiformes and Tetraodontiformes from the higher Squamipennes potentially makes the latter paraphyletic. Nevertheless, I have excluded these orders from the analysis of outgroup relationships for practical reasons, as did Tyler et al. (the Zeiformes and Tetraodontiformes are both large and diverse groups). Moreover, I argue that even if this exclusion is incorrect, it should not seriously affect polarity decisions within the Chaetodontidae.

Zeiforms and tetraodontiforms are highly derived fishes. The most chaetodontid-like genus in either of the two orders, Antigonia, has no synapomorphies that link it to the Chaetodontidae exclusive of all other higher squamipennians (sensu Tyler et al.). It is therefore unlikely that either the Zeiformes or Tetraodontiformes is the first or second outgroup of the Chaetodontidae. (These are the outgroups that strongly affect polarity decisions within the ingroup.) At its greatest, the influence of these taxa on outgroup comparison would be limited to the case in which one (or both) of these taxa is a derived member of a group that is otherwise much more primitive (e.g. as would be the case if tetraodontiforms were acanthuroid derivatives). Therefore, it is unlikely that the exclusion of these taxa from the outgroup analysis will lead to erroneous polarity decisions within the Chaetodontidae.

Character Descriptions

The following characters were compiled from the literature discussed above, and from my own examination of specimens. Derived states were determined by comparison to a general outgroup, the Percoidei. All character state transformations are represented as binary characters. The presentation of characters below and in the data matrix is

organized according to the groups they diagnose, and not by anatomical systems. This organization was chosen to facilitate the perception of hierarchy and conflict within the data, particularly when the data are viewed as a matrix.

Each character description contains a short description of the derived state, a contrast of the primitive and derived states, and any discussion of the pertinent literature. The distribution of the primitive and derived character states is given in the data matrix (Table 1).

1) Tooth plate on second epibranchial absent. In unspecialized percoids and many non-percomorph teleosts, a small, ventral, tooth plate is present on the medial end of the second epibranchial, just lateral to the pharyngobranchial tooth plate. The absence of this tooth plate is a derived feature among percoids (Tyler et al., MS). However, the loss of this tooth plate is not unique among percoids or percoid derivatives.

Mok and Shen (1983) misinterpreted the presence of the second epibranchial tooth plate as the derived condition (discussed by Tyler et al.). Further, Mok and Shen's placement of this transformation on their cladogram erroneously indicates that the tooth-plate is present in Kyphosus and Microcanthus. This tooth plate is absent in these taxa.

2) First epipleural rib broad. In all percoids examined, the first epipleural rib is not differentiated

from those that follow. In many, but not all, fishes that have been considered members of the Kyphosidae and Scorpionidae (Kyphosus and Microcanthus in this analysis), the first epipleural rib is broadly flattened and significantly more robust than succeeding ribs (Mok and Shen, 1985).

Mok and Shen also characterized toxotids as having several expanded anterior epipleural ribs. However, the condition that occurs in toxotids is more accurately described as progressive reduction of the more posterior ribs rather than hypertrophication of the anterior ones.

3) Comma-shaped tooth patches on pharyngobranchials. Rosen (1984) diagnosed the pharyngobranchials of higher squamipennes as being very reduced, and bearing "comma-shaped" tooth patches of filiform teeth. The pharyngobranchials of almost all higher squamipennians are significantly reduced (Fig. 3), but they are not necessarily comma-shaped. In several groups, the tooth patches, or plates, are actually more elliptical in shape. Reduced pharyngobranchials and elliptical tooth patches also occur in Microcanthus strigatus. Among the higher Squamipennes, only scatophagids have large pharyngobranchial tooth plates, but their pharyngobranchial teeth are nevertheless filiform.

4) Branchiostegal rays six or fewer. Tyler et al. reported that all higher squamipennians have six or fewer branchiostegal rays, while most percoids have seven. Mok

Fig. 3. Relative Sizes of Pharyngobranchial Tooth Plates. Silhouettes of the left pharyngobranchial tooth plates are shown in ventral view. The maximum size difference among these specimens is about ten percent, as indicated by their standard lengths. A, Kyphosus sectatrix, AMNH 20855, 63 mm; B, Platax pinnatus, AMNH 88344, 57 mm; C, Chaetodon baronessa, USNM 266891, 56 mm.

Abbreviations:

PB II-V pharyngobranchials II-IV

A

B

C

and Shen (1983, fig. 12D) illustrated Microcanthus as having six. The basihyal in their illustration is dislocated from its natural position, and their specimen may have been damaged. Specimens of Microcanthus examined here have seven branchiostegals. Thus, either Microcanthus is polymorphic, or Mok and Shen's illustration is incorrect.

5) Opercular membranes attached to the isthmus. In most percoids and all lower squamipennians examined, the opercular membranes are attached to each other mid-ventrally across the isthmus below the posterior end of the lower jaw (angular). In all higher squamipennians, the opercular membranes are not attached to each other, but rather to the isthmus. In pomacanthids, the point of attachment is anterior, just behind the anterior end of the interopercle.

In all other higher squamipennians, the point of attachment is even more posterior (see character 8).

6) Parashpenoidal apophysis present. Tyler et al. characterized higher squamipennes as having a "variously developed parasphenoidal apophysis". In many percoids, the parasphenoid produces a median ventrally-directed blade along its length beneath the orbits. The parasphenoidal apophysis protrudes postero-ventrally either at the posterior end of this blade, or just behind it. The apophysis suspends the third pharyngobranchials. Where it is well developed it also appears to serve as a bracing fulcrum, facilitating manipulation of the pharyngobranchials. Where it is less developed, it marks

the origin of the obliquus dorsalis muscles, which then insert on the third pharyngobranchials. Further comments on this structure are made by Rosen (1984), and Tyler et al. (MS). It is not unique to higher squamipennians, as it occurs in the "pharyngognaths" (e.g. cichlids, pomacentrids, embiotocids, and labroids) and in gerriids. The development of this structure seems to be positively correlated with size in some of the higher squamipennians. It is weakly developed in most adult chaetodontids, and virtually absent in small ones. It is also absent in a specimen of Rhinoprenes (a very apomorphic ehippidid) that is larger than other ehippidids that have one (Rhinoprenes was therefore coded as lacking the apophysis).

7) Vacant interneural space present. In most percoids examined, the proximal end of at least one dorsal pterygiophore interdigitates between successive neural spines. In the higher Squamipennes, there is typically one interneural space that lacks an interdigitating pterygiophore. This gap may be as far forward as between neural spines five and six, or as far posterior as between spines eight and nine. While the presence of a vacant interneural space is rare among percoids, it is not uniformly present among higher squamipennians, being present in Chaetodipterus, Drepane, chaetodontids, scatophagids and

acanthuroids, but consistently absent in pomacanthids, Platax and Rhinoprenes.

8) Opercular membranes attached to the isthmus posteriorly and ventro-laterally, resulting in a restricted opercular aperture. In most percoids, the opercular membranes are joined to each other across the isthmus anteriorly. In chaetodontids, ehippidids, scatophagids, and acanthuroids, the opercular membranes are attached to the isthmus posteriorly and somewhat laterally, just under the anterior end of the subopercle (Tyler et al., MS).

9) Tooth replacement occurs in waves. Pomacanthids and chaetodontids share a unique pattern of tooth loss and replacement. Within a tooth row, replacement teeth are added postero-laterally, and older teeth are lost antero-medially. The organization of tooth replacement produces sequences of contiguous teeth within rows that are interrupted by gaps (Fig. 4). Addition and loss of teeth causes each row of teeth (usually 5-8) to travel postero-laterally over time, even though individual teeth do not move. The gaps among contiguous teeth are offset medially in more lingual rows, and the positions of gaps create a banding pattern among tooth rows. This pattern of tooth replacement is unique among percoids as far as known, and is described more fully in Appendix B.

10) Pterosphenooids touch medially and form the dorsal margin of the optic foramen. In primitive teleosts, the

Fig. 4. Tooth Arrangements in Ehippidids and Pomacanthids. All scanning electron micrographs (Figs. 4, 25, 26, 27, and 28) are of left premaxillae, unless specified as a left dentary. Views are generally from the anterior such that the arrangement of alveoli can be seen. If the scale bar is oriented in a normal reading position, dorsal will be up and medial to the right, unless specified otherwise. A, Chaetodipterus faber, AMNH 88441, 197 mm, premaxilla, slightly dorsal view, emerging replacement teeth are randomly distributed; B, Pomacanthus paru, AMNH 88443, 160 mm, premaxilla, view nearly parallel to alveolar axes, showing alternating arrangement of tooth pedestals (alveoli) and gaps where replacement teeth form; C, Chaetodontoplus sp., AMNH 88354, 87 mm; D, as in C, except premaxilla is inverted and dorso-labial laminar bone surrounding alveolar region has been removed to expose a perpendicular view of tooth pedestals.

optic foramen is bordered by the basisphenoid ventrally, the pterosphenoids laterally, and the orbitosphenoid dorsally. In percoids, the lack of an orbitosphenoid leaves the optic foramen open dorsally, and the medial margins of the pterosphenoids remain widely separated. In pomacanthids and chaetodontids, the optic foramen is closed by dorso-medial expansions of the pterosphenoids (Fig. 5). As in other squamipennians, the ventro-medial margins of the frontals remain widely separated, leaving a large opening in the antero-ventral wall of the brain case. In all other percoids in which the pterosphenoids touch medially (e.g. Gerres), the frontals are not separated ventro medially, and thus the juxtaposition of the pterosphenoids is not a result of their own increased width, but rather the increased medial extent of the frontals. Because the anterior neurocranium in Gerres has a radically different architecture, its pterosphenoid morphology was not interpreted as homologous with that in pomacanthids and chaetodontids.

11) Pharyngobranchials reduced to very narrow, laterally aligned rows of very fine teeth. Extreme reduction of the pharyngobranchials occurs in pomacanthids and chaetodontids (Fig. 3). In these fishes, pharyngobranchials two through four are perpendicular to the body axis, and the teeth are extremely fine.

Fig. 5. Antero-ventral View of the Neurocranium in a Chaetodontid, Chelmonops truncatus. In pomacanthids and chaetodontids, the pterosphenoids make contact medially and reform the optic foramen. (Portion of parasphenoid under the orbit removed.)

Abbreviations:

ASP	autosphenotic
BOC	basioccipital
EXO	exoccipital
FR	frontal
LE	lateral ethmoid
OF	optic foramen
PAR	parasphenoid
PRO	prootic
PTO	pterotic
PTS	pterosphenoid
VOM	vomer

12) Mesethmoid inverted, between or posterior to the lateral ethmoids. Starks (1926) made the most comprehensive survey of ethmoid structure in teleosts. He began his entry under Drepane punctata (p. 272): "The condition of the mesethmoid is unique, as far as known, to this form and some of the chaetodontoid fishes, especially Holacanthus." He then referenced a footnote, which begins: "This condition of the mesethmoid must mean a very definite relationship between the forms that have it." A typical percoid mesethmoid is situated completely anterior to the lateral ethmoids, and dorsal to the vomer. Its antero-dorsal surface is convex in both lateral and anterior views. In Drepane, pomacanthids, and chaetodontids, the mesethmoid lies either between or completely posterior to the lateral ethmoids. Its antero-dorsal surface is concave, forming either a medial cavity between the orbits (Drepane, Pomacanthids, Parachaetodon, and Chaetodon sensu Burgess, 1978) or a foramen between the lateral ethmoids (all other chaetodontid genera). This cavity receives the long ascending processes of the premaxillae when the mouth is closed.

Starks conveyed the impression that the morphologies in Drepane and pomacanthids are more similar to each other than either is to the chaetodontid form. This is generally the case, but there is a similarity between pomacanthids and chaetodontids, exclusive of Drepane. In pomacanthids and

chaetodontids, the roof of the interorbital cavity is formed by the mesethmoid, which is then covered by the frontals. In Drepane, the anterior margins of the frontals are notched medially such that the interorbital cavity of the mesethmoid almost has no roof.

The differences among the derived ethmoid morphologies suggest a partial transformations series. It is clear that the pomacanthid morphology is intermediate between that in Drepane and those in chaetodontids. However, it is impossible to polarize this transformation series because none of the details that are unique to any two taxa leave the third with an obviously primitive morphology. For example, pomacanthids and Drepane have a prominent, dorsal median ridge on the vomer that continues posteriorly as a less prominent ridge on the mesethmoid. Chaetodontids lack this ridge entirely. However, neither "ridge-absent" nor "ridge-present" can be considered primitive relative to the other because the complementary state does not occur in other fishes. In fact, neither state can occur in the outgroups because the mesethmoid occupies this position. Other differences that exist among the ethmoids of these three taxa are similarly resistant to polarization. Therefore, I have not made a more detailed interpretation of this structure.

13) Mesethmoid with second posterior ossification center. Starks's descriptions and illustrations of the

ethmoid morphologies in chaetodontids, pomacanthids, and Drepane are generally detailed and accurate. However, he missed a potentially significant aspect of these morphologies because he examined only adult material. In all three taxa, there is a unique second ossification center on the posterior side of the ethmoid cartilage. In larvae and juveniles, a thin layer of bone is produced just ventral to the main ossification that intrudes between the orbits. The posterior ossification fuses with the anterior one later in ontogeny, but the size at which fusion occurs is variable among taxa. Although the ossification patterns in most percoids are unknown, it is likely that the most general mesethmoid ontogeny involves only a single ossification center on the antero-dorsal surface of the ethmoid cartilage.

14) Ascending process of premaxilla longer than the alveolar (descending) process. In lower squamipennians and most percoids, the length of the ascending process of the premaxilla is equal to or slightly less than the length of the alveolar process (e.g. Microcanthus, Fig. 6A). In Drepane, pomacanthids, and chaetodontids, the ascending process of the premaxilla is significantly longer than the alveolar process (Fig. 6B and D). This discrepancy in lengths results from both the lengthening of one process and the shortening of the other.

Fig. 6. Lateral Views of Left Maxilla and Premaxilla. A, Microcanthus strigatus, USNM 267047; B, Chaetodon capistratus, USNM 266896; C, Platax pinnatus; D, Drepane punctata, USNM 267052. In A and C, the long axis of the maxilla is oblique to plane of the illustration, and appears shorter than actual length. In B and D, the axis of the maxilla is nearly dorso-ventral, and in plane of illustration.

Abbreviations:

APP	ascending process of premaxilla
DPP	descending process of premaxilla
MX	maxilla

A

B

C

D

15) Maxilla short, oriented vertically in face. In most squamipennians and percoids with terminal mouths, the maxilla is relatively long and slender, and lies above and parallel to the alveolar process of the premaxilla. In Drepane, pomacanthids, and chaetodontids, the maxilla is very short, and its axis is vertical in the face, at an appreciable angle to the alveolar process of the premaxilla (Fig. 6B and D).

16) Frontals and supraoccipital with tubular cancellations. In most fishes, the external surfaces of the frontals and the supraoccipital are either relatively smooth or bear dermal ornamentation. In Drepane, ehippidids, scatophagids, and acanthuroids, the internal cancellations form tubes that are continuous with the external surface. Tyler et al. (MS) noted this similarity among the latter groups, but characterized Drepane as lacking this feature. While these cancellations are less well developed in Drepane, they are present, nevertheless.

17) Mesopterygoid with horizontal shelf narrow or absent, leaving a large gap between the parasphenoid and the mesopterygoid. In most percoids, lower squamipennians, pomacanthids, and chaetodontids, the mesopterygoid has two broadly laminar portions, one lies somewhat horizontally, forming the roof of the mouth between the parasphenoid and the cheek, and the other descends vertically along the side of the mouth, medial to the adductor mandibulae (Fig. 7A).

These two laminae join in an obtuse angle forming a more or less distinct edge that runs antero-posteriorly under the orbit. This edge marks the lateral extremity of the insertion of the adductor arcus palatini. The medial margin of the horizontal lamina approaches the parasphenoid. The horizontal lamina is reduced in Drepane and absent in ehippidids, scatophagids, and acanthuroids, leaving a large gap between the mesopterygoid and parasphenoid (Fig. 7B and C).

18) Interopercle narrow anteriorly, or foreshortened. In most percoids, the interopercle is roughly elliptical in shape, and the anterior end, which is joined to the angular by a short ligament, is broadly rounded. In Drepane, ehippidids, scatophagids, and acanthuroids, the anterior end of the interopercle is severely constricted, and almost no wider than the ligament which binds it to the angular. Tyler et al. (MS) described this derived condition as axe-shaped, although it is truly axe-shaped only in scatophagids and acanthurids. In ehippidids, the interopercle is short and triangular, and in siganids, it is long and its posterior end is also dorso-ventrally narrow. The most significant feature of the derived state is the increased length of the ligament that joins the interopercle to the angular. Tyler et al. did not diagnose Drepane as having a derived interopercle. In my view, including Drepane among the derived taxa does not significantly increase the amount

Fig. 7. Schematic Representation of Parasphenoid and Left Mesopterygoid in Cross-section from an Anterior View. A, a typical percoid; B, Drepane (and some ephippids); and C, scatophagids, and acanthuroids.

Abbreviations:

AAP	adductor arcus palatini
DLL	dorso-lateral lamina
HL	horizontal lamina
MPTG	mesopterygoid
PAR	parasphenoid
VL	vertical lamina

of variation that is already present among ehippidids, scatophagids, siganids, and acanthurids. More importantly, Drepane has a long ligament between the interopercle and angular.

19) Basihyal absent or reduced, and buried in thick connective tissue. Johnson (1984) interpreted the presence of thick connective tissue over the anterior surface of the hyoid apparatus to be a potential synapomorphy of Drepane and Coracinus. He further characterized this condition as including a ventrally directed basihyal that is well submerged in this connective tissue. I have not been able to examine specimens of Coracinus, but I have found Johnson's characterization of Drepane to be accurate. Johnson (1984) also diagnosed the ehippidids, exclusive of Drepane and Coracinus, by the reduction or loss of the basihyal (and two other features; see 22 and 23 below). The ehippidids I have examined (Chaetodipterus, Platax, and Rhinoprenes) also have thick connective tissue in front of the hyoid apparatus. I have, therefore, expanded the diagnosis of this derived character state to include Drepane. This condition is unique among percoids, as far as known.

20) Mesopterygoid with a narrow, dorsally directed blade running between metapterygoid and palatine. In all percoids, and most squamipennians, there is no blade projecting dorsally from the edge which is formed by the

confluence of the horizontal and vertical laminae (see character 16). In Drepane, and ehippidids (except Rhinoprenes), the vertical lamina continues dorsally beyond the edge forming a blade (Fig. 7C). This blade marks the insertion of the adductor arcus palatini. Rhinoprenes has no horizontal lamina, and thus neither an edge, nor a dorsal extension of the vertical lamina. However, this condition is clearly not equivalent to the primitive one, and I hypothesize that it was derived from the ehippidid condition.

21) Proximal radials of soft dorsal and anal fins with symmetrical diamond-shaped heads. In most percoids, the heads of the median proximal radials are directed posteriorly, at an approximately 45 degree angle from the main axis of the proximal radial. The distal ends of these heads provide the articular surface for each distal radial and fin ray. The articular surfaces are relatively narrow in lateral profile. In ehippidids, the heads of the proximal radials are distinctly symmetrical and diamond shaped (cf. Rosen, 1984:15, fig. 15), thus the articular surfaces are much wider. The derived pterygiophore morphology seen in ehippidids is also present in Drepane.

22) Interopercle widely separated from the angular. In ehippidids, the interopercle is significantly foreshortened. Consequently, the ligament that binds the interopercle and angular is longer than in the other taxa.

In Drepane, both the shape of the interopercle and the length of the ligament are distinctly ehippidid-like.

23) Coracoids not extending antero-ventrally to meet the cleithra mid-ventrally. In many percoids and all lower squamipennians, the antero-ventral tips of the coracoids approximate or actually touch the cleithral symphysis. This condition also occurs in all higher squamipennians except the ehippidids and Drepane. In these latter fishes, the coracoids do not extend ventrally beyond the pelvic bone. This condition is considered to be derived among the higher squamipennians.

24) Hyperostosis occurs in large individuals.

Hyperostosis is the term applied to a phenomenon in which one or more bones become hyper-ossified. It is rare among teleosts, but does occur in a number of other percoid families (Fierstine, 1968; Smith-Vaniz and Kaufman, 1988). In Drepane and ehippidids, individuals that are larger than approximately 20 cm (SL) frequently exhibit hyperostosis in one of several possible bones (the lacrimal, supraoccipital crest, dorsal and hemal spines, and the anterior dorsal and anal pterygiophores). The physiological cause of hyperostosis is unknown, but the similar nature of hypertrophied bones indicates that these fishes may share a physiological pathway or "strategy" of calcium storage (Smith-Vaniz and Kaufman, 1988).

25) Dorsal lamina of ceratohyal abuts against ventral hypohyal. In squamipennians, the antero-dorsal portion of the ceratohyal is laminar (see Fig. 20). This lamina never abuts the hypohyal except in ehippidids, where the anterior face of the ventral hypohyal is slightly expanded laterally, and covers the lamina's anterior edge.

26) Flattened recurved gill rakers on first epibranchial. Gill rakers are typically filamentous or conical structures, variously ornamented with smaller spinules. In all ehippidids, the gill rakers born on the first epibranchial are flattened and their ventral tips are curled posteriorly so that they look blunt from an anterior perspective (Johnson, 1984).

27) Interarcual cartilage absent. In most percoids, a cartilaginous element forms in the ligament that joins the uncinata processes of the first epibranchial and second pharyngobranchial. The interarcual cartilage is lost in a few percoid groups (Johnson, 1984), and in the present study this loss characterizes the ehippidids, scatophagids and acanthuroids (Tyler et al., MS).

28) Premaxillae not protrusible, or only slightly so, and tightly bound to maxillae. In most percoids, the ascending processes of the premaxillae are relatively long, and slide along the medial articular surfaces of the maxillae during jaw protrusion. In ehippidids, scatophagids, and acanthuroids, the ascending processes of

the premaxillae are short, and do not slide along the maxillae. Therefore, the jaws do not protrude significantly when the mouth is opened (Tyler et al., MS).

29) Articular length equal to or less than dentary length. In most percoids, the antero-posterior length of the articular is greater than that of the dentary (Fig. 8A, C, and D). In ehippidids, scatophagids (Fig. 8B), and acanthuroids, the length of the articular is equal to or less than that of the dentary (Tyler et al., MS).

30) Gill filaments not attached to dorsal margins of epibranchials, instead free dorsally. In most fishes, the ascending rows of gill filaments follow the curvature of the branchial arches medially along the dorsal margins of the epibranchials. In ehippidids and acanthuroids (but not scatophagids), the rows of gill filaments do not curve medially, but instead proceed dorsally, free from the epibranchials (Tyler et al., MS).

31) Vertebral formula 10 + 13. The vertebral formulae (number of precaudal + number of caudal vertebrae) encountered among percoids are reported by Johnson (1984). The number of precaudal vertebrae is never less than 10 (but usually not more than 14), and the number of caudal vertebrae is usually 14 or more. The vertebral formula in Scatophagids and acanthuroids is uncommonly low, 10 + 13. Among percoids, only priacanthids have this same formula.

Fig. 8. Mesial View of Left Lower Jaw. A, Microcanthus strigatus, USNM 267047; B, Selenotoca multifasciata, USNM 245703; C, Pomacanthus imperator, AMNH 88360; D, Chaetodon rafflesi, AMNH 88387.

Abbreviations:

ANG	angular
ART	articular
DEN	dentary
Q	quadrate

32) Posterior uroneurals absent. The primitive percoid caudal skeleton contains two pairs of uroneurals (Johnson, 1984). Scatophagids and acanthuroids have only one pair of uroneurals. This reduction is not rare among percoids, but all other squamipennians, except girellids and toxotids, have two pairs.

33) Predorsal bones two or fewer. Most percoids (Johnson, 1984), lower squamipennians, Drepane, and ehippidids, all have three predorsal bones. Chaetodontids, pomacanthids, scatophagids, and acanthuroids have two or fewer predorsal bones.

34) Parietals narrow antero-posteriorly. Most percoids, lower squamipennians, Drepane, and ehippidids, have parietals that are large and of roughly equal size along the longitudinal and transverse axes. Chaetodontids (Figs. 35 and 36), pomacanthids, Zanclus, and acanthurids have parietals that are distinctly shorter antero-posteriorly than they are medio-laterally. Scatophagids, siganids, lack parietals completely (see below). Within the Squamipennes, it was assumed that parietal loss occurred through an antero-posterior reduction. Thus, scatophagids and siganids were also coded as having reduced parietals.

35) Parietals absent. Parietals are present in most teleosts, percoids, and squamipennians, including Zanclus and acanthurids. (Parietals are also present in the larvae of Luvarus.) Parietals are absent in both larval and adult

scatophagids and siganids. They are also absent in some percoid derivatives, and some non-perciform fishes (Tyler et al., MS), but these losses are assumed to be convergent.

36) Principal caudal fin rays 16. Most percoids and all other squamipennians have 17 principal caudal fin rays. Scatophagids, Zanclus, and acanthurids, have only 16. (Note that siganids also have 17.)

37) Siganid, Zanclus, and acanthurid synapomorphies (one binary character given a weight of 11). Tyler et al. present eleven synapomorphies that unite siganids with Luvarus, Zanclus, and the acanthurids (to form the acanthuroids). This relationship is not an issue here, and these characters were incorporated into the present analysis as a single character with a weight of eleven.

Problematic Characters

Several osteological features that are variable among taxa were excluded from this analysis because the phylogenetic interpretations of these characters were judged to be unreliable. The problematic natures of these characters are discussed below.

Mok and Shen (1983) described three kinds of articulations between the pelvic spine and the pelvic bone among squamipennians. In most percoids, the pelvic spine articulates with the pelvic bone by grasping a small

postero-ventrally projecting blade. According to Mok and Shen (1983), two other morphologies represent sequentially derived conditions in a three-state transformation series. In the intermediate state, there is a foramen in the postero-ventral blade of the pelvic bone (between the grasping processes of the pelvic spine), and in the most derived state, the grasping processes fuse with each other through this foramen. Mok and Shen characterized lower squamipennians as lacking the foramen, Drepane and the ephippidids as having the foramen, and all of the remaining higher squamipennians as having fused grasping processes. Tyler et al. (MS) followed Mok and Shen so far as to use "foramen present" as a character state that unites higher squamipennians.

However, the states of this character are difficult to diagnose because the ontogeny of this character may not be complete in smaller specimens. Mok and Shen apparently arrived at their diagnoses by examining cleared and stained material, which is generally immature, and by extrapolating each primitive familial morphotype from the examination of only a few species within each family. Mok and Shen characterized pomacanthids and chaetodontids as having the most derived state. Contrary to their findings, Pomacanthus imperator (UH uncat., 42 mm) and P. paru (USNM 263253, 29 mm) do not have foramina in their pelvic bones. Geniacanthus melanospilos (AMNH 43415, 89 mm) also has the

most primitive state. Three small specimens of Holacanthus tricolor (AMNH 22935, 23, 25, and 29 mm) have foramina, but some have fused, while others have separate, grasping processes. A large dry skeletal preparation of H. tricolor (AMNH 2918, approximately 250 mm) has a small foramen on one side and none on the other. Fully fused grasping processes are present in specimens of Centropyge, Chaetodontoplus, and Pygoplites. (An 11 mm Centropyge larva shows separate grasping processes, but this condition was assumed to reflect an earlier state in the expected ontogenetic series.) Thus, there is evidence for at least one homoplastic step (independent origin or reversal) within the pomacanthids, and at least Holacanthus tricolor is polymorphic for all three states.

There is similar evidence for homoplasy in this character within the Chaetodontidae. However, the situation is further complicated by an apparently reversed ontogeny in at least one species, Chelmonops truncatus. Two specimens less than 70 mm show foramina in their pelvic bones (grasping processes separate) while three specimens larger than 70 mm all show pelvic bones without foramina. Except for Amphichaetodon, which may show the same ontogeny, all other chaetodontid specimens examined, from 15 mm juveniles to 150+ mm adults, have grasping processes that are fused.

Without a priori resolution of relationships within the Pomacanthidae and Chaetodontidae, the primitive morphotypes

of these families must be considered unknown.

Reconstruction (or optimization) of the character state changes on a cladogram is therefore ambiguous, and ambiguous character state changes cannot support specific sister group relationships. These problems were deemed to be sufficient justification for excluding this character from the analysis.

Similar polymorphism within species, or variability within families (that are clearly monophyletic) occurs in two other characters. A small, bony or cartilaginous element, just posterior to the last proximal radial in both the dorsal and anal fins (fin stay) is present in most percoids (Johnson, 1984). Most higher squamipennians lack dorsal and anal fin stays. However, median fin stays appear irregularly in Chaetodipterus, Platax, Drepane, and are present in scatophagids. The reconstructions of some familial morphotypes in this character are ambiguous, so the character was excluded.

Smith and Bailey (1962) noted that the presence, absence, and morphology of the subocular shelf was a potentially useful systematic character. But the variability in the subocular shelf of higher squamipennians is very similar to that seen in the median fin stays. A subocular shelf is present in most basal percoids, including lower squamipennians. It is also present in pomacanthids, chaetodontids, Platax, scatophagids, Zanclus

and some acanthurids. It is absent in Drepane, Chaetodipterus, Rhinoprenes, siganids and some acanthurids (Tyler, 1970; and pers. obs.). While none of the species examined appears to be polymorphic, there is variability within two of the higher squamipennian families (ephippidids and acanthurids). Further, this character has a low degree of congruence with the other characters. It may thus be inferred that presence or absence of the subocular shelf is too labile to meet the assumption of phylogenetic inference by parsimony, that the rate of character evolution be relatively slow (Felsenstein, 1978; Sober, 1983, 1985).

Results

Terse descriptions of the derived character states are listed in Table 2. The data matrix (Table 1) was analyzed by PAUP (D.L. Swofford, 1985, version 2.4), using the "Branch and Bound" option to obtain all most parsimonious trees (phylogenetic hypotheses). The data set yields two equally parsimonious trees (64 steps). The only difference between these trees concerns the position of Microcanthus. In the first tree, Microcanthus is the sister group of Kyphosus, and in the second, it is the sister group of the higher Squamipennes. In either of these positions, Microcanthus does not affect the interpretations (reconstructions) of other characters in the out-group

Table 1. Distribution of Character States in the Outgroup Analysis

Taxon	Character Number																																							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	0	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	3				
Hyp. Per. Anc.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
<u>Kyphosus</u>	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
<u>Microcanthus</u>	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
POMACANTHIDS	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	
CHAETODONTIDS	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	
<u>Drepane</u>	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
<u>Platax</u>	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0		
<u>Chaetodipterus</u>	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0		
<u>Rhinoprenes</u>	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0		
SCATOPHAGIDS	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0		
SIGANIDS	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	
ACANTHURIDS	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1

Table 2. List of Characters in the Outgroup Analysis

- 1) No tooth plate on second epibranchial.
- 2) First epipleural rib broad.
- 3) Comma-shaped tooth patches on infrapharyngobranchials
- 4) Branchiostegal rays six or fewer.
- 5) Opercular membranes attached to isthmus anteriorly.
- 6) Parashpenoidal apophysis present.
- 7) Vacant interneural space present.
- 8) Opercular membranes attached to isthmus posteriorly and laterally, resulting in a restricted opercular aperture.
- 9) Tooth replacement occurs in waves.
- 10) Pteroshpenoids touching medially creating foramen above basishpenoid.
- 11) Pharyngobranchials further reduced to very narrow, laterally aligned rows of very fine teeth.
- 12) Mesethmoid inverted, between or posterior to lat. ethm.
- 13) Unique second posterior ossification center,
- 14) Ascending premaxillary processes longer than alveolar processes.
- 15) Maxillae short, vertically oriented in face.
- 16) Frontals with tubular cancellations.
- 17) Mesopterygoid with reduced or absent horizontal shelf.
- 18) Anterior end of interopercle constricted.

- 19) Articular length equal to or less than dentary length.
- 20) Basihyal lost, or reduced and buried in connective tissue.
- 21) Mesopterygoid with vertical lamina extending into dorsal blade.
- 22) Proximal radials w/ symmetrical heads.
- 23) Ligament between angular and interopercle long.
- 24) Coracoids not reaching cleithral symphysis.
- 25) Hyperostosis in large individuals.
- 26) Ceratohyal - hypohyal joint.
- 27) Gill rakers, flattened, recurved.
- 28) Interarcual cartilage absent.
- 29) Premaxillae only slightly or non-protruible, and tightly bound to maxillae.
- 30) Gill filaments not attached to epibranchials, instead free dorsally.
- 31) Caudal vertebrae 13.
- 32) Posterior uroneurals absent.
- 33) Predorsal bones two or fewer.
- 34) Parietals reduced (shared by scatophagids and siganids)
- 35) Parietals absent.
- 36) Principal caudal fin rays 16.
- 37) Siganid, zanclid, and acanthurid syapomorphies (weighted by 11).

analysis, nor does it affect the polarity determinations of characters used in the analysis of chaetodontid relationships. Therefore, the relationships of Microcanthus are not discussed further. The strict consensus tree of the completely bifurcating trees is shown in Fig. 9, and referred to hereafter as hypothesis #1.

The combined length of the 37 characters is 47, and thus the consistency index is 0.712 (47/64). While this consistency is relatively high for 12 taxa, it indicates only that the data have a hierarchical structure. It does not measure the confidence that can be placed in this phylogenetic hypothesis relative to alternatives that are slightly less parsimonious. (This consistency value is also inflated by the exclusion of the labile characters discussed above.)

Many slightly less parsimonious trees can be obtained through trivial rearrangements of hypothesis #1 (for example, slightly greater tree lengths can be obtained by altering the relationships within the ehippidids). Because such changes do not significantly affect the outgroup relationships of the chaetodontids, they are not particularly relevant here. There are, however, three slightly less parsimonious hypotheses (Fig. 10) that do present different taxa as the second outgroup of the chaetodontids. Hypotheses #2 requires 66 steps, #3 requires 67, and #4 requires only 65.

Fig. 9. Consensus Tree of Two Maximally Parsimonious Cladograms of the Higher Squamipennes. The first outgroup of the Chaetodontidae is the hypothetical ancestor of the Pomacanthidae. The second outgroup is the hypothetical ancestor represented by node 3.

Fig. 10. Simplified Representations of Alternative Outgroup Hypotheses.

Several monophyletic groups are common to all four of these hypotheses (i.e. the strict consensus tree of all four hypotheses contains these groups). The common groups and the characters that support them will be discussed first so that comparisons among the alternative hypotheses may be simplified.

The higher Squamipennes (node 3, Fig. 9) is monophyletic in all four hypotheses. This relationship is supported by three "a posteriori synapomorphies" (characters whose reconstructions unambiguously infer that the derived state originated in the hypothetical ancestor of all higher squamipennians), characters 4, 5, and 6. This relationship is also supported by three characters (3, 7, and 8) whose reconstructions are ambiguous on some of the hypotheses, but constrained to change at this node on others. (Note that even though the reconstructions of these characters may differ among the outgroup cladograms, the number of steps required by each character does not change among the alternative cladograms.)

The four outgroup hypotheses vary only with respect to the relationships within the higher squamipennians. Therefore I have simplified the diagrams of the competing hypotheses (Fig. 10) by combining the lower squamipennian representatives, Kyphosus and Microcanthus, with the hypothetical percoid ancestor to form a general outgroup (Hyp. Percoid Anc.).

The three ehippidid genera, Chaetodipterus, Platax, and Rhinoprenes, form a second group common to all four hypotheses. The monophyly of the Ehippididae is supported by two characters that are unique among percoids, the peculiar ceratohyal-hypohyal joint (25), and the distinctive gill raker morphology (26). In Fig. 10, these three genera are represented as a single terminal taxon (Ehippididae).

The third common group is formed by the scatophagids and the acanthuroids. This relationship is supported by two characters, the presence of only 13 caudal vertebrae (31), and the loss of the posterior uroneurals (32). Ambiguous support is also offered by characters 35 and 36 (discussed in the character descriptions above). In the simplified cladograms, scatophagids are included with acanthuroids in the terminal taxon (Acanthuroidei, Fig. 10).

The last feature that is common to all four hypotheses is the sister group relationship between the pomacanthids and chaetodontids. This relationship is supported by 3 characters, the organization of tooth replacement and the resultant distribution of jaw teeth (10), the reformed optic foramen (pterosphenoids that make contact medially, 11), and the extremely reduced pharyngobranchials (12). The Pomacanthidae and Chaetodontidae are retained as separate taxa in Fig. 10 so that the differences among the outgroup hypotheses are clearly depicted as involving only the second and more distant outgroups.

The four hypotheses differ as follows. In the most parsimonious hypothesis, #1, Drepane is the sister group of the ehippidids, and these two form the sister group of the acanthuroids. The second outgroup to the Chaetodontidae is the monophyletic group comprising all three.

Hypotheses #2 differs from #1 only by the placement of Drepane; in #2, it is the second outgroup of the chaetodontids. The ehippidids and acanthuroids form the third outgroup. (Note that if Drepane did not exist, hypotheses 1, 2, and 3 would be equivalent, and there would be at least seven fewer character conflicts.)

In hypothesis #3, Drepane is the sister group of the ehippidids plus the acanthuroids. This hypothesis is very similar to #1 in that the same three taxa form the second outgroup of the Chaetodontidae. Only the relationships within the second outgroup are different.

Hypothesis #4 places the acanthuroids as the second outgroup of the chaetodontids. Drepane and the ehippidids form the third outgroup.

Discussion

Of the 37 characters, 18 have reconstructions that differ on the four competing hypotheses, 12 through 24, 27, 28, 29, 33, and 34. The remaining characters have equivalent transformations on each of the four trees, and are therefore irrelevant to the contrasts between them. The

evidence for and against the four hypotheses is listed in Table 3. This table summarizes the relevant character state transformations that are required by each hypothesis. Characters that require a single transformation support a particular hypothesis, while those that require extra steps detract from it (i.e. infer a relationship not contained in that hypothesis). There are five blocks of characters in which all characters have the same distributions. The taxonomic group inferred by each block is given on the far right. The numbers of a posteriori synapomorphies, homoplasies, and the contributions of the relevant characters to total tree length, are given under each hypothesis.

While the most parsimonious hypothesis is only one to three steps shorter than the others, it becomes clearly more preferable than the alternatives if the characters that support each hypothesis are examined more closely. This is particularly apparent in the contrast between hypotheses #1 and #2, which differ only by the placement of Drepane. A functional relationship has been proposed among three of the four characters that support Drepane's position as the sister group to the pomacanthids and chaetodontids (hypothesis #2). According to Gosline (1985) the inverted mesethmoid (12), the long ascending premaxillary process (14), and the short, vertically oriented maxilla (15), are all associated with increased jaw protrusion in deep bodied

Table 3. The Number of Transformations Required by Competing Outgroup Hypotheses

Block	Character	#1	#2	#3	#4	Taxa United
I	12	2	1	2	2	<u>Drepane</u> + Pomacanthids Chaetodontids
	13	2	1	2	2	
	14	2	1	2	2	
	15	2	1	2	2	
II	16	1	2	1	2	<u>Drepane</u> + Ehippidids + Acanthuroids
	17	1	2	1	2	
	18	1	2	1	2	
III	19	1	2	2	1	<u>Drepane</u> + Ehippidids
	20	1	2	2	1	
	21	1	2	2	1	
	22	1	2	2	1	
	23	1	2	2	1	
	24	1	2	2	1	
IV	27	1	2	1	2	Ehippidids + Acanthuroids
	28	1	2	1	2	
	29	1	2	1	2	
V	33	2	2	2	1	Acanthuroids + Pomacanthids + Chaetodontids
	34	2	2	2	1	
TOTALS						
Synapomorphies		9	7	6	8	
Extra Steps		9	11	12	10	
Contribution to Tree Length		27	29	30	28	
Total Tree Length		65	67	68	66	

fishes. Additionally, character 14, the second ossification center of the mesethmoid, may be structurally or developmentally related to the inversion of the mesethmoid.

The co-occurrence of these morphologies in the deep-bodied percoids with highly protrusible jaws supports the hypothesis that they are functionally correlated. However, this putative functional correlation does not preclude interpreting the entire complex as a potential synapomorphy of these fishes. Therefore, the complex must be represented by at least one character in the data matrix (in contrast to Gosline [1985: 351, 356], who dismissed these features completely). When these four characters are recoded as one, hypothesis #2 becomes "worse" than #1 by five steps instead of two. This difference is significant enough to eliminate hypothesis #2 from further consideration. However, the reinterpretation of characters 12 through 15 (to be a single character) affects hypotheses #3 and #4 in the same way that it affects #1. Therefore, it does not enhance the contrasts between them.

The acceptance of Drepane's upper jaw morphology as convergent does, however, indirectly affect hypothesis #3. There are six characters (19-24) that unite Drepane to the ehippidids, exclusive of acanthuroids. There are three conflicting characters (27-29) that unite ehippidids to the acanthuroids exclusive of Drepane. One of them, 28, also concerns upper jaw morphology. Ehippidids and acanthuroids

(including scatophagids) have ascending premaxillary processes that are shorter than those in other percoids. The ligaments joining the medial ends of the maxillae to the premaxillae are also shorter, and thus the jaws are less protrusible. If Drepane's highly protrusible jaw morphology is interpreted as not being homologous with that found in pomacanthids and chaetodontids (a conclusion that arises from the rejection of hypothesis #2), it must have been derived independently from either the oppositely extreme ehippidid-acanthuroid condition, or the intermediate, primitive percoid condition. The intermediate condition is the more likely ancestral candidate. However, the ehippidid-acanthuroid condition cannot be excluded with certainty because jaw morphology appears to be somewhat labile (note that jaw morphology is not consistent with any cladogram except #2). If Drepane's jaw morphology were derived from the ehippidid-acanthuroid condition, this character would not support an ehippidid-acanthuroid relationship that excludes Drepane. Regardless of the transformation series that is chosen to represent the evolution of jaw morphology, the acanthuroid-ehippidid sister group relationship of hypothesis #3 is supported by at most only three characters, while the Drepane-ehippidid relationship (#1) is supported by twice this number.

The contrast between hypotheses #1 and #4 focuses on two different conflicting blocks of characters. Block II

(Table 3, characters 16-18) unites the acanthuroids, ehippidids, and Drepane, whereas block V (33 and 34) unites the acanthuroids with the pomacanthids plus chaetodontids. Character 33 (predorsal bones 2 or fewer) is a "loss character", and thus the homology of the derived state cannot be evaluated by an analysis of fine structure (cf. Remane, 1957). It is clear, however, that there is a reductive trend in the predorsal bones within the families of the higher Squamipennes. Both pomacanthids and chaetodontids have two predorsal bones, primitively. A further reduction to a single predorsal bone occurs within the pomacanthids, and a fusion of the two predorsal bones occurs within the chaetodontids. Scatophagids also have two predorsal bones primitively, but at least one species, Selenotoca multifasciata, is polymorphic for presence of the second predorsal bone (which may be present, weakly developed, or absent; pers. obs.). Siganids and Zanclus have only one predorsal bone, and acanthurids have none. If one assumes that each of these families is monophyletic (an assumption that is well supported), one is forced to accept no fewer than five independent reductions in predorsal bone number. This reductive trend compromises the homology of the loss shared by acanthuroids, pomacanthids, and chaetodontids.

Similar instability characterizes the reduction and loss of the parietals, character 34. The parietals are

antero-posteriorly narrow in pomacanthids, chaetodontids, Zanclus, and acanthurids, but completely absent in scatophagids and siganids. Moreover, a further dorso-ventral reduction occurs within the Chaetodontidae. While the reconstruction of parietal evolution is somewhat ambiguous, the labile nature of this character is not. Thus, both characters of block V are impugned by their relatively high rates of change.

The preceding discussion shows that the less parsimonious hypotheses are also less preferable because the character evidence that supports them is problematic. It is easier to accept the characters of blocks I, IV, and V, as homoplastic, than those of blocks II and III. Therefore, hypothesis #1 (Fig. 9 and 10A) is accepted here as the best summary of chaetodontid outgroup relationships. The Pomacanthidae is assumed to be the first outgroup of the Chaetodontidae. The monophyletic group composed of Drepane, the Ehippididae, Scatophagidae, and Acanthuroidei, is assumed to be the second outgroup.

CHAPTER III

OSTEOLOGY AND PHYLOGENY OF THE CHAETODONTIDAE

Introduction

Previous treatments of chaetodontid anatomy and osteology have been restricted to either a particular anatomical system or a limited number of species. Starks included chaetodontid representatives in his surveys of teleostean ethmoid (1926) and posttemporal (1930) morphology. Gregory (1933) included a superficial treatment of a chaetodontid (Chaetodon ocellatus) in his broad survey of fish skulls. Similar chaetodontid representation appeared in the surveys of teleostean caudal skeletons (Monod, 1967) and urohyals (Kusaka, 1974).

Burgess (1975, 1978) provided an anatomically more comprehensive review of chaetodontid osteology, but his taxonomic coverage within the family was limited, and his purpose was simply to highlight the numerous differences that exist between pomacanthids and chaetodontids. His revision of the family (Burgess, 1978) was based exclusively on external morphology, and contained no formal statements of relationships beyond the recognition of genera and subgenera. Motta (1982) presented the most thorough

description of a chaetodontid skull, but again described only a single species, Chaetodon miliaris. Similarly detailed work on other species is lacking. Motta's comparative work (1985) has been restricted to jaw morphology.

Mok and Shen (1982) surveyed gross kidney morphology and patterns of intestinal coiling in a commendably broad range of chaetodontids. Nalbant (1974, 1986) superficially described the morphology of the dorsal pterygiophores, predorsal bones, and caudal skeleton (the latter from radiographs) in approximately 20 species. Although the studies by Mok and Shen (1982) and Nalbant (1986) employed cladistic methods, neither has significantly advanced our knowledge of chaetodontid interrelationships nor affected chaetodontid taxonomy because the number of characters surveyed was too few.

The only hypotheses of chaetodontid phylogeny that have included all genera were presented by Nalbant (1973, 1986).

The first of Nalbant's phylogenies was presented in the manner typical of classical taxonomy (a near-bush), and contains relatively few statements of relationship. His figure specified close relationships between Heniochus and Hemitaurichthys, Coradion and Parachaetodon, Johnrandallia and Chaetodon, and portrayed the genus Chaetodon as monophyletic, but none of these relationships were supported with specific character evidence. Nalbant's second version

of chaetodontid phylogeny (Nalbant 1986, fig. 30) was not presented as a standard cladogram, and is difficult to interpret fully. Nevertheless, it differs substantially from the first. Forcipiger is the sister group of Chelmon, and members of the genus Chaetodon (sensu Burgess, 1978) are placed in different sections of the tree (i.e. Burgess's Chaetodon would be polyphyletic). Hemitaurichthys, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and a more restricted version of Chaetodon comprise a phylogenetic sequence, as do Amphichaetodon, Prognathodes, Roa, and Roaops (the latter three were part of Chaetodon according to Burgess, 1978).

The only similarity between Nalbant's 1973 and 1986 phylogenies is the close relationship between Coradion and Parachaetodon. Nalbant attempted to interpret characters cladistically, but his interpretations were not always evident in his conclusions. For example, he interpreted the predorsal bone morphology of Parachaetodon as primitive, but did not use the derived condition to unite Coradion with all other chaetodontids, as Coradion remained the sister-group to Parachaetodon. His conclusions were further compromised by his failure to determine character polarities by outgroup comparison whenever possible (e.g. he mistakenly assumed that a low number of dorsal fin spines is primitive).

Thus, despite the efforts of previous workers, a well supported phylogenetic hypothesis of the Chaetodontidae is lacking. The following survey of chaetodontid osteology

represents the first attempt to survey all osteological systems in all supraspecific taxa.

Materials and Methods

Most of the specimens examined in this survey were cleared and stained according to the procedure of Dingerkus and Uhler (1977). The generally smaller (sub-adult), cleared and stained material was supplemented wherever possible with larger dry skeletal preparations and disarticulated skeletons (the latter prepared by boiling fresh and preserved specimens in solutions of 1-5 percent potassium hydroxide). A list of the cleared and stained material examined is presented in Appendix A. The breadth of the survey can be assessed more easily in Table 4, which reveals the coverage of the family in two ways. For each supraspecific taxon in Burgess's classification, the proportion of species examined is given, and for each valid species, the number of individuals examined is given.

The skulls of cleared and stained specimens were dissected according to the method of Weitzman (1974, pp. 342-3), or a slight modification of it (which entailed the complete removal of the hyo-branchial apparatus). Weitzman's method maximizes the exposure of the suspensorium, neurocranium, and the hyoid and branchial arches, while minimizing the number of severed articulations. Additional dissections were performed as

necessary. Illustrations were prepared from a stereo dissecting microscope (Wild M-7A) with a camera lucida.

Morphological features found to vary qualitatively among the higher chaetodontid taxa were evaluated against two inclusion criteria before they were admitted into the analysis. These criteria were that, for each character, 1) variation among taxa be clearly greater than variation within taxa, and 2) easily recognizable gaps be present between adjacent character states. The first criterion was used to exclude characters that may be unstable and may have evolved too rapidly to meet the assumptions of phylogenetic inference by parsimony (Felsenstein, 1973, 1978, and 1983).

The second criterion was used to enhance the likelihood that the interpretations of morphology made here might be repeated or deemed acceptable by subsequent workers.

Whenever more than two states were present in a single structure, a transformation series between states was hypothesized on the basis of similarities among the various morphologies. The major differences between this approach and that in which each individually recognizable attribute is given a separate code are that, 1) several attribute changes may be subsumed under a single state change (those attributes explicitly assumed to be correlated), and 2) homoplasy among the attributes of a single character is identified by congruence or compatibility among other attributes of the same character rather than with all other

characters (in the final parsimony analysis). If the similarities among character states did not strongly suggest a transformation series, the character was included as unordered.

Character polarities were inferred by the method of outgroup comparison set forth by Maddison et al. (1984). Outgroup taxa were surveyed for each character to be used in the ingroup analysis. The character state present at the first outgroup node, the hypothetical ancestor of the pomacanthids and chaetodontids, was determined by reconstructing character evolution (optimizing) the character on the outgroup cladogram. Characters used to resolve chaetodontid interrelationships were polarized by including this reconstructed hypothetical ancestor in the Wagner parsimony analysis of the ingroup. This method is guaranteed to produce cladograms that are globally parsimonious (Maddison et al., 1984) provided the relationships among the outgroups are correct and the ingroup is monophyletic (Clark and Curren, 1985).

Support for the outgroup relationships was presented in the previous chapter. However, the latter assumption, monophyly of the ingroup, was not tested in the outgroup analysis as all terminal taxa in that analysis, including the Chaetodontidae, were assumed to be monophyletic. Also note that the method of ingroup analysis described above, rooting the ingroup cladogram by a single outgroup, does not

test the assumption of ingroup monophyly. Thus, the outgroup and ingroup analyses reported here would, by themselves, leave the assumption of chaetodontid monophyly untested. It is, therefore, appropriate to review the evidence that supports this assumption as a logical antecedent to the analysis of the ingroup relationships. Because of its logical precedence, such evidence must be independent of ingroup relationships. Characters that satisfy this criterion of independence are those in which a single derived state (or a series of sequentially derived states) is present in all chaetodontids. The morphological features that satisfy these criteria and convincingly demonstrate the monophyletic nature of the Chaetodontidae are discussed below.

Monophyly of the Chaetodontidae

Any taxon can be made monophyletic by altering its membership (i.e. by including or excluding taxa of lesser rank). Burgess (1978) made the last adjustment to the Chaetodontidae by transferring the genus Vinculum to the Scorpionidae. Although other recent treatments of the Chaetodontidae (Nalbant, 1971, 1973, 1974, 1984, 1986; Mok and Shen, 1982; Maugé and Bauchot, 1984) have not varied from Burgess's concept of the family, a cladistically-framed diagnosis of the family is still lacking.

Perhaps the most obvious osteological character unique to chaetodontids is the sequential articulation between the first dorsal pterygiophore, the predorsal bones, and the supraoccipital crest. The posterior tip of the supraoccipital is forked (furca spinae supraoccipitalis of Nalbant, 1974, 1986), and embraces the shaft of the first predorsal bone just below its laterally expanded head (caput pterygiophori, Nalbant, 1974: 313, figs. 1-4; Figs. 2 and 15-18, here). In all other percoids examined, except Rhinoprenes, these bones are not articulated. In Rhinoprenes (not illustrated) the predorsal bones make contact with each other, but they are separate from the supraoccipital and the first dorsal pterygiophore. Moreover, the caput pterygiophori are much thinner laterally than they are in chaetodontids. In Rhinoprenes the contact between predorsal bones results from the presence of both anterior and posterior processes on the heads of the predorsal bones, whereas in chaetodontids contact results from only anterior processes and the crowding of the predorsal bones between the supraoccipital and the dorsal fin. The conditions in Rhinoprenes and chaetodontids are judged not to be homologous.

Nalbant (1986) noted that the pattern of interdigitation between the neural spines and the proximal ends of predorsal bones and dorsal pterygiophores differs in chaetodontids from those present in pomacanthids and

scorpidids. However, he was apparently unaware of Johnson's (1984) comprehensive review of percoid morphology, including predorsal formulae. Johnson argued, by comparison to beryciforms and "common equals primitive", that the primitive percoid predorsal formula is 0/0/0+2/1/1. In these formulae (originated by Ahlstrom et al. 1976) the anterior is to the left, slashes represent neural spines, and integers represent the dorsal elements. A predorsal bone is indicated by a "0", a normal pterygiophore bearing one spine by a "1", and a compound pterygiophore bearing two supernumerary spines (if present, always the first) by a "2". Primitive squamipennians show a variety of conditions, one of the more common being 0/0+0/2/1+1/1 (e.g. Microcanthus, Drepane, and some ehippidids). This condition differs from the primitive percoid condition in having the third predorsal bone shifted to the anterior side of the second neural spine, and pterygiophores two and three inserted in the third interneural space. Chaetodontids actually show two predorsal formulae, 0/0+2/1/1 and a second one which defies representation by this formula because the single predorsal bone straddles the first neural spine. Except for the presence of a single predorsal bone and its position, the second chaetodontid formula is identical to the first. The chaetodontid formulae differ from both the common percoid and the primitive squamipennian conditions in that the number of predorsal bones is reduced from three to

two (or one), and the first and second dorsal pterygiophores are both moved forward into the first and second interneural spaces, respectively. Pomacanthids also show a reduction from three to two predorsal bones (and then a further reduction to one within the family), but retain the more posterior origin of the dorsal fin, and two pterygiophores in the third interneural space. Nalbant (1986) was correct in contrasting chaetodontids to pomacanthids and scorpidids.

The primitive chaetodontid formula is not unique, however, as it occurs in some scatophagids (Johnson, 1984).

Nevertheless, reconstruction of predorsal formula on the outgroup cladogram indicates that the scatophagid and chaetodontid conditions were derived in parallel.

The pleural ribs of chaetodontids bear laminae that extend forward from the medial edges of the descending shafts (Fig. 12). If a horizontal cross-section is made through a descending shaft, the flattened rib and the anterior lamina join at right angles, somewhat like an angle-iron, with the angle opening antero-laterally. These laminae are well developed in all chaetodontids except Parachaetodon ocellatus and Chaetodon (Megaprotodon) trifascialis. In these species, small laminae are present only in larger specimens. The conditions found in these two species can be interpreted as either partial derivations or reversals. In either case, the presence of at least small laminae can be considered a synapomorphy of the family.

Fig. 11. Anterior Axial Skeleton of a Pomacanthid.
Centropyge loriculus, AMNH 88351, 40 mm.

Abbreviations:

BPT	Basipterygium
NS XIII	Neural Spine (thirteenth)
PC II	Second Postcleithrum
PR	Pleural Rib
PT I	First Dorsal Pterygiophore
SOC	Supraoccipital

A Centropyge loriculus

Fig. 12. Anterior Axial Skeleton of a Chaetodontid.
Chaetodon ulietensis, AMNH 88384, 55 mm.

Abbreviations:

BPL	Basipterygio-postcleithral Ligament
BPT	Basipterygium
NS XIII	Neural Spine (thirteenth)
PC II	Second Postcleithrum
PR	Pleural Rib
PT I	First Dorsal Pterygiophore
SOC	Supraoccipital

B Chaetodon ulietensis

The exceptional length of chaetodontid pleural ribs is also derived (Fig. 12). In chaetodontids, the pleural ribs extend ventrally almost to the mid-line. By far, the more common length among percoids is only about two thirds of the distance between the vertebral column and the ventral mid-line, as shown in Centropyge (a pomacanthid, Fig. 11). Microcanthus strigatus also has long pleural ribs, and thus this feature is not unique to chaetodontids. However, the pleural ribs in Microcanthus do not have anterior laminae, and the lack of a close relationship between Microcanthus and chaetodontids indicates that the similarity was derived in parallel.

All chaetodontids have a ligament that connects the anterior edge of the second post-cleithrum to the basipterygium (Fig. 12). The insertion of the ligament on the basipterygium is just anterior to the origin of the pelvic spine, and marked by a ventro-lateral apophysis. Neither the ligament nor the apophysis has been observed in any other fishes.

The branchiostegal rays of most fishes articulate proximally with the ceratohyal. In chaetodontids, the two anterior branchiostegals (or, if only five are present, the single most anterior one) do not make contact with the ceratohyal, but rather, lie free in the opercular membrane (Fig. 21). This feature was also noted by Mok and Shen (1983).

Finally, all chaetodontids, as far as known, have a specialized post-larval, but still pelagic, form known as a tholichthys larva. Individuals in this phase possess a unique suite of hypertrophied skull bones. Detailed figures of their osteology are lacking, but see Burgess (1978, p. 86) and Johnson (1984; fig. 262 A-C) for examples of gross morphology. The most dramatically hypertrophied bone is the preopercle, which is expanded antero-dorsally almost to the margin of the orbit, and ventro-medially under the head, so that the left and right antimeres are juxtaposed mid-ventrally. Further, the preopercle bears a large posterior projection that is attenuated into either a sharp or blunt spine. The posttemporals and the supracleithra exhibit large, plate-like, expansions that extend posteriorly over the trunk. The frontals are slightly expanded such that they cover the parietals posteriorly, and more of the orbit laterally than they do in post-metamorphic individuals. The nasals, lacrimals, and dermosphenotics (last circumorbital bone) are also hypertrophied such that they fill the gaps between the larger bones already mentioned, and form an almost complete casing of dermal armor around the head.

The only other fishes that have been said to have a tholichthys-like larva are scatophagids. However, scatophagid larvae show only superficial similarity to chaetodontid larvae, and lack almost all of the specific characters mentioned above. The gross similarities are the

overall shape of the larva, and that some of the skull bones are hypertrophied. However, there is little correspondence between the bones that are hypertrophied in the two larval types. Both types have ornamentation that projects posteriorly from the back of the head. In scatophagids, it consists of a strong blunt spine formed through hypertrophy of the pterotic. In chaetodontids, it consists (in part) of a broad, flat, occasionally sculptured, plate, formed through hypertrophy of the posttemporal. In chaetodontids, the pterotic are not hypertrophied in any way. In scatophagids, the dorsal arm of the posttemporal is slightly thickened, but does not bear a lamina. Moreover, in scatophagids, the lacrimals, nasals, dermosphenotics, and supracleithra are all more or less proportioned as they are in post-metamorphic individuals. Most of the bones that are hypertrophied (posttemporal, pterotic, and frontal) are thickened, not marginally expanded, as they are in chaetodontid larvae. The only bone that shows a chaetodontid-like marginal expansion in scatophagids is the preopercle, but it is only slightly expanded ventrally. Finally, there is a strong difference between the surface textures of hypertrophied bones in chaetodontids and scatophagids. In all tholichthys larvae examined, the hypertrophied bones have a rugose or knobby surface texture. This texture is present on virtually all dermal bones, from fin spines to the nasal bones. In scatophagid larvae, the

surfaces of the hypertrophied bones are smooth in comparison.

The contrasts above show that the similarity between chaetodontid and scatophagid larvae does not withstand a comparison of detail. Scatophagids do not have a tholichthys larva, and the presence of a true tholichthys larva may be cited as a synapomorphy of chaetodontids. It should be noted, however, that while all known chaetodontid larvae have the tholichthys characters, the larvae of many chaetodontids remain unknown.

Three of the seven characters reviewed above represent complex modifications of structures found more generally among percoids or teleosts (articulation between the dorsal fin and supraoccipital, predorsal formula, and larval morphology). The more simple characters are all novel additions. None of these seven features can be characterized as a simple reduction. This suite of seven characters thus provides ample evidence that the Chaetodontidae form a monophyletic group. Moreover, all of these characters are either unique to chaetodontids, or at most rare among percoids. This demonstration of chaetodontid monophyly is thus independent of the outgroup relationships that were proposed in the previous section. (The polarities of unique characters cannot be reversed by outgroup substitution; see Donoghue and Cantino, 1984.)

Operational Taxa Used in the Ingroup Analysis

The most widely recognized classification of chaetodontids (Burgess, 1978) was used to guide the acquisition of species for osteological examination. Burgess's classification of the family is shown in Table 4.

Because many chaetodontid species are rare or absent in systematic collections, specimens of only 57 of the 120 valid species were available for osteological preparation, dissection, and examination. However, these 55 species include at least one representative from each of the supraspecific taxa recognized by Burgess. Most taxa are represented by multiple species.

The operational taxonomic units (OTUs) used in this analysis were defined by phenetic similarity. All species found to be identical in qualitative features of osteology were grouped into a terminal taxon. Most of Burgess's supraspecific taxa were found to be osteologically homogeneous, but two of his subgenera within Chaetodon were found to be heterogeneous. Chaetodon (sensu stricto) was found to contain four osteological groups, and the subgenus Roa Jordan 1922 was found to contain two. Chaetodon (sensu stricto) was made homogeneous by removing 17 species under the name Exornator Nalbant 1971, by transferring Chaetodon kleinii and C. trichrous to the subgenus Lepidochaetodon Bleeker 1876, and by transferring Chaetodon melannotus and C. ocellicaudus to the subgenus Rabdophorus Swainson (1839).

Table 4. Number of Species and Specimens Examined Per Taxon. The 120 valid chaetodontid species are classified according to Burgess (1978). All changes in alpha level taxonomy are noted. The number of cleared and stained specimens examined is given opposite each species, and the proportion species examined is given opposite each higher taxon. Species for which only radiographs were examined are indicated with an "R".

FAMILY CHAETODONTIDAE (after Burgess, 1978)

GENUS <u>Chelmon</u>	3/3	GENUS <u>Heniochus</u>	3/8
<u>C. marginalis</u>	1	<u>H. accuminatus</u>	
<u>C. mulleri</u>	2	<u>H. chrysostomus</u>	6
<u>C. rostratus</u>	5	<u>H. diphreutes</u> ^b	1
		<u>H. intermedius</u>	(R)
		<u>H. monoceros</u>	
GENUS <u>Chelmonops</u>	1/2	<u>H. pleurotaenia</u>	
<u>C. curiosus</u> ^a		<u>H. singularis</u>	
<u>C. truncatus</u>	5	<u>H. varius</u>	3
		GENUS <u>Parachaetodon</u>	
GENUS <u>Coradion</u>	2/3	<u>P. ocellatus</u>	5
<u>C. chrysozonus</u>	2		
<u>C. melanopus</u>		GENUS <u>Amphichaetodon</u>	1/2
<u>C. altivelis</u>	1	<u>A. howensis</u>	3
		<u>A. melbae</u>	(R)
GENUS <u>Forcipiger</u>	1/2		
<u>F. flavissimus</u>	8	GENUS <u>Johnrandallia</u>	
<u>F. longirostrus</u>		<u>J. nigrirostris</u>	1
GENUS <u>Hemitaurichthys</u>	2/4		
<u>H. multispinosus</u>			
<u>H. polylepis</u>	3		
<u>H. thompsoni</u>	1		
<u>H. zoster</u>			

^a Kuitert, 1986.

^b Allen and Kuitert, 1978.

Table 4. (continued) Number of Specimens Examined

GENUS <u>Chaetodon</u>		Subgenus <u>Gonochaetodon</u> 1/3
Subgenus <u>Prognathodes</u> 1/8		<u>C. baronessa</u> 4
		<u>C. larvatus</u> (R)
<u>C. aculeatus</u>		<u>C. triangulum</u> (R)
<u>C. aya</u>	3	
<u>C. dichrous</u>		Subgenus <u>Tetrachaetodon</u> 3/4
<u>C. falcifer</u>		<u>C. bennetti</u> 2
<u>C. quezei</u> ^c		<u>C. plebeius</u> 5
<u>C. guyanensis</u>		<u>C. speculum</u> 3
<u>C. guyotensis</u> ^d	(R)	<u>C. zanzibariensis</u> (R)
<u>C. marcellae</u>		
<u>C. obliquus</u> ^e		
Subgenus <u>Roa</u> 3/7		Subgenus <u>Corallochaetodon</u> 2/3
<u>C. burgessi</u>	(R)	<u>C. austriacus</u> (R)
<u>C. declivis</u>		<u>C. melapterus</u> 1
<u>C. exelcsa</u> ^f	2	<u>C. trifasciatus</u> 3
<u>C. flavocoronatus</u> ^g		
<u>C. jayakari</u> ^f		Subgenus <u>Citharoedus</u> 3/3
<u>C. mitratus</u>		<u>C. meyeri</u> 1
<u>C. modestus</u>		<u>C. ornatissimus</u> 4
<u>C. nippon</u>	4	<u>C. reticulatus</u> 3
<u>C. tinkeri</u>	1	
Subgenus <u>Rhombochaetodon</u> 2/5		Subgenus <u>Chaetodontops</u> 3/8
<u>C. argentatus</u>	(R)	<u>C. adiergastos</u> 1
<u>C. madagascariensis</u>	(R)	<u>C. auripes</u>
<u>C. mertensii</u>	1	<u>C. collare</u> (R)
<u>C. paucifasciatus</u>		<u>C. fasciatus</u> (R)
<u>C. xanthurus</u>	1	<u>C. flavirostris</u> 1
		<u>C. lunula</u> 2
		<u>C. semilarvatus</u> (R)
Subgenus <u>Megaprotodon</u>		<u>C. wiebeli</u> (R)
<u>C. trifascialis</u>	2	

^c Maugé and Bauchot, 1976.

^d Yamamoto and Tameka, in Okamura et al., 1982.

^e Lubbock and Edwards, 1980.

^f Elevated from synonymy by Klausewitz and Fricke, 1985.

^g Meyers, 1980.

Table 4. (continued) Number of Specimens Examined

Subgenus <u>Rabdophorus</u> 6/16		Subgenus <u>Chaetodon</u> 13/28	
<u>C. auriga</u>	4	<u>C. assarius</u>	
<u>C. decussatus</u>		<u>C. blackburnii</u>	(R)
<u>C. ephippium</u>	3	<u>C. capistratus</u>	2
<u>C. falcula</u>	(R)	<u>C. citrinellus</u>	2
<u>C. gardineri</u>	(R)	<u>C. daedalma</u>	2
<u>C. leucopleura</u>		<u>C. dolosus</u>	(R)
<u>C. lineolatus</u>	(R)	<u>C. fremblii</u>	2
<u>C. mesoleucos</u>	(R)	<u>C. guentheri</u>	(R)
<u>C. nigropunctatus</u>	2	<u>C. guttatissimus</u>	(R)
<u>C. oxycephalus</u>		<u>C. hoefleri</u>	(R)
<u>C. rafflesii</u>	1	<u>C. humeralis</u>	
<u>C. selene</u>	(R)	<u>C. kleinii</u>	3
<u>C. semeion</u>	(R)	<u>C. litus</u>	
<u>C. ulientensis</u>	7	<u>C. marleyi</u>	
<u>C. vagabundus</u>	2	<u>C. melannotus</u>	6
<u>C. xanthocephalus</u>		<u>C. miliaris</u>	1
		<u>C. multicinctus</u>	5
		<u>C. ocellatus</u>	1
Subgenus <u>Lepidochaetodon</u>		<u>C. ocellicaudus</u>	(R)
<u>C. unimaculatus</u>	7	<u>C. pelewensis</u>	4
		<u>C. punctatofasciatus</u>	(R)
		<u>C. quadrimaculatus</u>	1
		<u>C. robustus</u>	
Subgenus		<u>C. sanctaehelenae</u>	(R)
<u>Discochaetodon</u>	3/4	<u>C. sedentarius</u>	
<u>C. aureofasicatus</u>	2	<u>C. smithi</u>	
<u>C. octofasciatus</u>	1	<u>C. striatus</u>	2
<u>C. rainfordi</u>	1	<u>C. trichrous</u>	1
<u>C. tricinctus</u>	(R)		

All species in Burgess's subgenus Roa were found to be similar, except Chaetodon excelsa, the type species. Thus, Chaetodon excelsa retains the name Roa, and the remaining six species, Chaetodon burgessi, C. declevis, C. flavocoronatus, C. mitratus, C. nippon, and C. tinkeri, are recognized here under the name Roaops Maugé and Bauchot 1984.

All nominal taxa that were found to be osteologically identical were combined (operationally synonymized) in order to reduce the number of taxa in the analysis. Keeping them separate would serve no cladistic purpose, as there were no osteological characters with which to resolve the relationships among taxa. Because the solution(s) to a Wagner parsimony analyses can only be demonstrated by the enumeration of alternatives, reducing the number of taxa in an analysis decreases the number of trees that must be examined, and thus increases the likelihood of finding the most parsimonious tree(s).

The species of Rhombochaetodon Burgess (1978) were found to be indistinguishable from those of Exornator, and thus included among the latter. The species of Chaetodontops Bleeker (1876) were found to be indistinguishable from those of Rabdophorus Swainson. The operational taxonomic units (OTUs) used in this analysis, and the species they contain, are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Operational Taxonomic Units and Contained Species.

The supraspecific taxa listed below are either potentially or demonstrably monophyletic. No characters are known to infer that any taxa are paraphyletic. Two subgenera that Burgess (1978) included in Chaetodon are elevated to generic rank, Prognathodes and Roa. One genus, Parachaetodon, is reduced to subgeneric rank within Chaetodon.

FAMILY CHAETODONTIDAE

GENUS Amphichaetodon

- A. howensis
- A. melbae

GENUS Chelmonops

- C. curiosus
- C. truncatus

GENUS Chelmon

- C. marginalis
- C. mulleri
- C. rostratus

GENUS Coradion

- C. altivelis
- C. chrysozonus
- C. melanopus

GENUS Forcipiger

- F. flavissimus
- F. longirostrus

GENUS Johnrandallia

- J. nigrirostris

GENUS Heniochus

- H. accuminatus
- H. chrysostomus
- H. intermedius
- H. monoceros
- H. pleurotaenia
- H. singularius
- H. varius

GENUS Hemitaurichthys

- H. multispinosus
- H. polylepis
- H. thompsoni
- H. zoster

GENUS Prognathodes

- P. aculeatus
- P. aya
- P. dichrous
- P. falcifer
- P. guezei
- P. guyanensis
- P. guyotensis
- P. marcellae
- P. obliquus

GENUS Roa

- R. excelsa
- R. jayakari
- R. modestus

Table 5. (continued) Operational Taxonomic Units

GENUS Chaetodon

Subgenus Roaops

Subgenus Chaetodon

C. capistratus
C. hoefleri
C. humeralis
C. marleyi
C. ocellatus
C. robustus
C. striatus

C. burgessi
C. declevis
C. flavocoronatus
C. mitratus
C. nippon
C. tinkeri

Subgenus Exornator

Subgenus Rabdophorus

C. adiergastos
C. auriga
C. auripes
C. collare
C. decussatus
C. ephippium
C. falcula
C. fasciatus
C. flavirostris
C. gardineri
C. lineolatus
C. lunula
C. leucopleura
C. melannotus
C. mesoleucos
C. nigropunctatus
C. ocellicaudus
C. oxycephalus
C. rafflesii
C. selene
C. semeion
C. semilarvatus
C. ulientensis
C. vagabundus
C. wiebeli
C. xanthocephalus

C. argentatus
C. assarius
C. blackburnii
C. citrinellus
C. daedalma
C. dolosus
C. fremblii
C. guentheri
C. guttatissimus
C. litus
C. madagascariensis
C. mertensii
C. miliaris
C. multicinctus
C. paucifasciatus
C. pelewensis
C. punctatofasciatus
C. quadrimaculatus
C. sanctaehelenae
C. sedentarius
C. smithi
C. xanthurus

Subgenus Lepidochaetodon

C. kleinii
C. trichrous
C. unimaculatus

Table 5. (continued) Operational Taxonomic Units

Subgenus Megaprotodon

C. trifascialis

Subgenus Parachaetodon

C. oligacanthus^a

Subgenus Gonochaetodon

C. baronessa
C. larvatus
C. triangulum

Subgenus Tetrachaetodon

C. bennetti
C. plebeius
C. speculum
C. zanzibariensis

Subgenus Discochaetodon

C. aureofasicatus
C. octofasciatus
C. rainfordi
C. tricinctus

Subgenus Corallochaetodon

C. austriacus
C. melapterus
C. trifasciatus

Subgenus Citharoedus

C. ornatissimus
C. meyeri
C. reticulatus

^a The name Chaetodon (Parachaetodon) ocellatus (Cuvier) 1831 is preoccupied by Chaetodon (Chaetodon) ocellatus Bloch 1781. The oldest available name is Chaetodon (Parachaetodon) oligacanthus Bleeker 1850.

Because phenetic similarity does not necessarily indicate an exclusive relationship (monophyly), it is possible, if not likely, that some of the OTUs used here are paraphyletic. However, a full assessment of evidence for OTU monophyly can only be done after the relationships are specified. (Homoplastic state changes, reversals and convergences, can be used as evidence of relationship, but can only be discovered by reconciliation with all characters.) The evidence for OTUs monophyly (or lack of it) is therefore discussed after their interrelationships.

Character Descriptions

The characters are presented below by anatomical region rather than by taxonomic group. This order was used because many of the characters are of a multistate, rather than binary, nature. A regional approach facilitates the comparison of states within a single character (morphological structure), and comparisons among states justify the ordering of transformation series by similarity.

Characters are grouped according to three gross morphological systems. These are, in order of presentation, the axial skeleton and associated soft anatomy, the branchial skeleton, and finally, the skull.

Character state distributions are given in Table 7. Three types of character coding were used to portray interpretations of morphology, binary (23 characters),

ordered multistate (9), and unordered multistate (2). Ordered multistate characters are represented (Table 6) in additive binary form because it accomodates branching as well as linear transformation series. In the text, the most primitive state for each character is described first. In ordered multistate characters (e.g. character 1), these taxa are indicated with a "0" in the first sub-character, "X.1". Each of the progressively more derived states (indicated by a "1" in succeeding sub-characters, X.1, X.2, etc.) is hypothesized to have been evolved from the preceeding state, unless specified otherwise. Binary and unordered multistate characters are represented as single columns. The taxonomic names used in the character descriptions refer to the OTUs listed in Table 7, rather than the genera or subgenera of previous authors.

1.0) First dorsal pterygiophore (4 states, ordered; Figs. 13 and 14). In all outgroup taxa (except Zanclus and the Acanthuridae, which are derived in different ways from chaetodontids; see Tyler 1970), the first dorsal pterygiophore is not sculptured such that the first dorsal spine can be erected further forward than approximately 45 degrees from the horizontal. The first dorsal spine bears no ventrally directed processes on either side of median fossa, and the median pin of the pterygiophore (possibly homologous to a medial radial) is not elevated above the anterior process.

Fig. 13. Predorsal Bones and First Dorsal Pterygiophore of Drepane punctata. USNM 267052, 49 mm. The lateral view is below, the dorsal view above. Anterior is to the right.

Abbreviations:

DS (I, II)	Dorsal Spine
NS (I-III)	Neural Spine
PD (I-III)	Predorsal bones
PT I	First Dorsal Pterygiophore
SOC	Supraoccipital

Drepane punctata

Dorsal
View

Lateral
View

Fig. 14. Predorsal Bones and First Dorsal Pterygiophore of Pomacanthus imperator. AMNH 88360, 42 mm. The lateral view is below, the dorsal view above. Anterior is to the right.

Abbreviations:

DS (I, II)	Dorsal Spine
NS (I-III)	Neural Spine
PD (I-III)	Predorsal bones
PT I	First Dorsal Pterygiophore
SOC	Supraoccipital

Pomacanthus imperator

Dorsal
View

Lateral
View

1.1) (Fig. 15) In all chaetodontids the median pin is elevated above the anteriorly directed process. In all chaetodontids (except members of Lepidochaetodon, which are hypothesized to possess a state derived through this one; see character 1.3 below), the first dorsal pterygiophore is sculptured on either side of the median pin to accommodate bilateral ventral processes on the first dorsal spine. The median fossa in the spine (directly above the median pin of the pterygiophore) is larger than in outgroup taxa. This morphology allows the first dorsal spine to be erected further forward than it can in outgroup taxa. The proximal end of the first dorsal spine is buttressed ventrally by lateral processes on the first dorsal pterygiophore. The erector dorsalis muscles pass dorsally just in front of the lateral processes. In outgroup taxa, these lateral processes, if present, are only weakly developed.

1.2) (Fig. 16) A further modification of the first dorsal pterygiophore is shared by Rabdophorus, Roops, Exornator, Lepidochaetodon, Megaprotodon, Gonochaetodon, Tetrachaetodon, Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus. In these taxa the median anterior process of the pterygiophore is dorsoventrally compressed and laterally expanded. The lateral expansion occurs just anterior to the erector dorsalis muscles. The anterior and posterior lateral processes on each side form a well defined groove that carries the erector dorsalis.

Fig. 15. Predorsal Bones and First Dorsal Pterygiophore of Coradion chrysozonus. AMNH 88396, 71 mm. The lateral view is below, the dorsal view above. Anterior is to the right.

Abbreviations:

DS (I, II)	Dorsal Spine
NS (I-III)	Neural Spine
PD (I-III)	Predorsal bones
PT I	First Dorsal Pterygiophore
SOC	Supraoccipital

Coradion chrysozonus

Dorsal
View

Fig. 16. Predorsal Bones and First Dorsal Pterygiophore of Chaetodon lunula. AMNH 88424, 47 mm. The lateral view is below, the dorsal view above. Anterior is to the right.

Abbreviations:

DS (I, II)	Dorsal Spine
NS (I-III)	Neural Spine
PD (I-III)	Predorsal bones
PT I	First Dorsal Pterygiophore
SOC	Supraoccipital

Chaetodon lunula

Dorsal
View

Lateral
View

1.3) (Fig. 17) The next more derived condition results from the lateral fusion of the anterior and posterior lateral processes. This fusion creates a foramen in the pterygiophore, through which the erector dorsalis passes. In adults, this condition is present in the subgenera Roops, Exornator, Lepidochaetodon, and Citharoedus. In the first three taxa, the development of this condition is either rapid or direct; the fusion is already complete in the smallest juveniles examined (and even in a 15 mm larva of Lepidochaetodon). In Citharoedus, the fusion does not take place until individuals are larger than 40 mm (approximately). This difference in ontogeny requires that the character state given to Citharoedus be a different than that given to the other three taxa. The state in Citharoedus may be either partially derived, partially reversed, or derived in parallel. The first case, which specifies a transformation series between "lateral processes unfused", "fused late in ontogeny", and "fused early in ontogeny", is the most direct interpretation of similarity. This series was initially used to represent the character. However, the number of conflicting characters in the remainder of the data set demonstrate that Citharoedus is not related to Roops, Exornator, and Lepidochaetodon, but is instead related to a series of other taxa that have the more primitive state, "lateral processes unfused". The condition in Citharoedus is therefore shown to be derived in

Fig. 17. Predorsal Bones and First Dorsal Pterygiophore of Chaetodon multicinctus. AMNH 88389, 54 mm. The lateral view is below, the dorsal view above. Anterior is to the right.

Abbreviations:

DS (I, II)	Dorsal Spine
NS (I-III)	Neural Spine
PD (I-III)	Predorsal bones
PT I	First Dorsal Pterygiophore
SOC	Supraoccipital

Chaetodon multicintus

parallel. The transformation series shown in Table 6 was recoded such that 1) the condition in Citharoedus is not represented as homologous to the condition in the other three taxa (and is therefore an autapomorphy), and 2) the change between "lateral process unfused" and "fused in early ontogeny" was counted as a single step (retaining the intermediate condition in the series would have doubled the weight of this state change).

The most derived condition of the first dorsal pterygiophore is restricted to the three species of Lepidochaetodon (Fig. 18). In these fishes, the median pin that anchors the first dorsal spine to the pterygiophore is significantly more robust (wider). In most chaetodontids, the median fossa in the first dorsal spine accommodates the median pin when the spine is erected forward to the horizontal (the posture assumed in threat displays). In the species of Lepidochaetodon, the median fossa in the spine is absent (the spine is therefore stronger), and full erection is permitted by an anterior recess at the base of the longitudinal pin. Because the three species that have this morphology are represented as a single taxon, the character state does not contribute to the resolution of intergroup relationships. The character state is an autapomorphy, and does not appear in the data matrix.

2.0) Predorsal bones (6 states, ordered; Figs. 13-18).

In pomacanthids and most percoids, the predorsal bones are

Fig. 18. Predorsal Bones and First Dorsal Pterygiophore of Chaetodon unimaculatus. AMNH 88342, 45 mm. The lateral view is below, the dorsal view above. Anterior is to the right.

Abbreviations:

DS (I, II)	Dorsal Spine
NS (I-III)	Neural Spine
PD (I-III)	Predorsal bones
PT I	First Dorsal Pterygiophore
SOC	Supraoccipital

Chaetodon unimaculatus

Dorsal
View

Lateral
View

simple, rod-like structures, with their distal ends bent sharply forward under the nape (Figs. 13 and 14). They usually lack thickenings or ornamentations. Unspecialized percoids have three predorsal bones (Johnson, 1984), but both pomacanthids and chaetodontids have only two, primitively. In all outgroup taxa, the predorsal bones do not articulate with each other, the supraoccipital, or the first dorsal pterygiophore.

2.1) (Fig. 15) All chaetodontids have a sequential articulation between the first dorsal pterygiophore, predorsal bones, and supraoccipital crest. The distal end of each predorsal bone is bent anteriorly, and expanded laterally into a cap, or thickened head. The head of each successively more posterior element overlaps the preceding element dorsally. The head of the first predorsal bone overlaps the supraoccipital, the second predorsal bone overlaps the first, and the first pterygiophore overlaps the second predorsal bone. In all chaetodontids, the postero-dorsal tip of the supraoccipital is forked medially, and grasps the shaft of the first predorsal bone. In the more primitive chaetodontids, the head of the first predorsal bone has a distinct postero-dorsal median groove. This groove receives the antero-ventral ridge, or keel, of the second predorsal bone. The most primitive chaetodontid predorsal bone morphology is present in Amphichaetodon,

Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, Hemitaurichthys, Roa, and Prognathodes.

2.2) (Fig. 16) In Chaetodon, Rabdophorus, Megaprotodon, Gonochaetodon, Tetrachaetodon, Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus, the head of the first predorsal bone is longer, flatter, and lacks the posterodorsal groove.

2.3) (Figs. 17 and 18) In Roaops, Exornator, and Lepidochaetodon, only a single predorsal bone is present. This single element may be explained by two alternative hypotheses, loss or fusion. There are, however, two features of the persisting bone that support the fusion hypothesis. The proximal end of the single remaining shaft is forked over the first neural spine, and thus retains the positions of the two original bones. There are also lateral grooves in the shaft, above the fork. These features are consistent with the fusion hypothesis, but would have to be interpreted as de novo attributes in the loss hypothesis. Nalbant (1986) has also hypothesized (independently) that this condition is the result of fusion.

2.4) (Derived from 2.1; Fig. 15) The heads of the predorsal bones in Chelmonops, Chelmon, and Coradion lack the well developed lateral wings that are present in all other taxa (Figs. 16, 17, and 18). The heads are, instead, thicker dorso-ventrally (i.e. they are taller). Nevertheless, the head of the first predorsal bone does

retain the postero-dorsal groove that accepts the ventral keel of the second predorsal bone (described in character 2.1).

In Parachaetodon the heads of the predorsal bones are somewhat similar to those described here, they are dorso-ventrally thickened and show no lateral wings. However, the head of first predorsal bone lacks the postero-dorsal groove, and in this respect is similar to the derived condition, 2.4. Because the morphology of Parachaetodon does not match that in any other taxa, and because it shares attributes with two hypothetically unrelated morphologies, the ancestral morphology of Parachaetodon cannot be specified. Therefore, the predorsal morphology of Parachaetodon was not placed in the transformation series, but was instead coded as unknown. This coding precludes the morphology of Parachaetodon from influencing its cladistic position in the parsimony analysis.

3) Length of pleural ribs (Figs. 11 and 12). The pleural ribs in all of the outgroup taxa, except Microcanthus, extend ventrally about two thirds of the distance from the vertebral column to the ventral mid-line (Fig. 11). The pleural ribs of all chaetodontids extend almost to the ventral mid-line (Fig. 12). (Microcanthus also has very long ribs, but this condition is inferred to be convergent by reconstruction of the character on the outgroup cladogram.)

4.0) Anterior laminae on pleural ribs (3 states, ordered; Figs. 11 and 12). In all outgroup taxa, the descending shafts of the ribs are ovoid or antero-posteriorly flattened in cross section (Fig. 11).

4.1) The pleural ribs in Megaprotodon and Parachaetodon are strongly flattened (antero-posteriorly), and the descending shafts of the ribs bear small, anteriorly directed, laminae along their medial edges.

4.2) (Fig. 12) The pleural ribs of all other chaetodontids are also strongly flattened, and all, except the last vestigial rib (on the 10th centrum), bear well developed anterior laminae. A linear transformations series between laminae absent, laminae weakly developed, and laminae strongly developed was assumed.

5) Basipterygio-postcleithral ligament present (Fig. 12). All chaetodontids have a well defined ligament that connects the distal end of the basipterygium (pelvic bone) and the leading edge of the second postcleithrum (Fig. 12B). This ligament is unique to chaetodontids, as far as known.

6) Lateral line length. The lateral line in all outgroup taxa is complete, extending posteriorly to the base of the caudal fin. In Parachaetodon and all species of Chaetodon (sensu Burgess, 1978), the lateral line terminates under the last ray of the dorsal fin (or even more anteriorly in some species).

7) Scales small. Burgess (1978) reported lateral line scale counts for each of the known species he considered to be valid. He noted (p. 107; and table 1, p. 111) that Forcipiger and Hemitaurichthys have higher lateral line scale counts (68-83) than any other chaetodontids (22-60).

8.0) Swimbladder morphology (3 states, unordered; Fig. 19). The swimbladders in all outgroup taxa are either simple (with one chamber and no diverticula, Fig. 19A), or derived differently than they are in chaetodontids (e.g. pomacanthids have posterior diverticula which extend posteriorly on either side of the hemal spines).

8.1) (Fig. 19B) The swimbladders in Chaetodon, Rabdophorus, Roaops, Exornator, Lepidochaetodon, Gonochaetodon, Tetrachaetodon, Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus, have bilaterally paired, bulbous, antero-lateral diverticula, that are attached to the medial surfaces of the supracleithra. The attachment is just medial to the canal that conducts the lateral line through the supracleithrum, forward onto the head. In taxa that lack the antero-lateral diverticula, the supracleithral canal is completely enclosed in bone. In chaetodontids that have the diverticula, the supracleithral canal is incomplete medially; there is no bony septum between the swimbladder and the lateral line. This juxtaposition of the swimbladder and the lateral line is unique among fishes as far as known. It seems probably that this morphology enhances the

Fig. 19. Swimbladder Morphology. Schematic views of isolated swimbladders, in lateral (left) and dorsal (right) views, show the three morphologies encountered among chaetodontids. Anterior is to the right. A, simple; B, with large anterior horns; C, constricted with thin anterior horns.

A

B

C

Lateral
View

Dorsal
View

detection of pressure waves (sound), and thus comprises a novel "otophysic" connection.

8.2) (Fig. 19C) In Megaprotodon and Parachaetodon, the antero-lateral diverticula that connect the swimbladder to the supracleithra are much narrower than they are in other similarly equipped chaetodontids. In these two monotypic taxa, the diverticula take the form of long thin tubes.

9) Swimbladder constricted (Fig. 19C). In Megaprotodon and Parachaetodon, the swimbladder is constricted in the transverse plane, such that it appears to be divided into anterior and posterior chambers. However, the constriction is not complete, and the two chambers remain confluent. The anterior chamber is about half the volume of the posterior one.

Mok and Shen (1982) reported the two-chambered condition in Parachaetodon, and were aware that Shen and Lam (1979) had reported a similar condition in Megaprotodon. They did not, however, conclude that these species are closely related, and said only that their data did not refute such a relationship.

A similar constriction occurs in the Teraponidae (Vari, 1978). In these fishes, the anterior chamber is equipped with extrinsic muscles, and the entire apparatus functions as a sound producing organ. The swimbladders in

Megaprotodon and Parachaetodon lack extrinsic muscles, and the functional significance of the constriction is unknown.

10.0) Kidney morphology (3 states, ordered). Mok and Shen (1982, fig. 1) reported variation in chaetodontid kidney morphology in a broad survey of the family. They described three morphologies, referred to here as states 0, 1, and 2. Most basal percoids and squamipennians (kyphosids, enoplosids, scorpidids, pomacanthids, Platax, and scatophagids) have state 0. All of the chaetodontids they examined have either state 1 or 2, but these morphologies are not completely restricted to chaetodontids.

They occur in the outgroups, but not commonly enough to refute the hypothesis that state 0 characterizes the first outgroup node. In state 0, the posterior kidney is fused medially and does not extend posteriorly beyond the first hemal spine.

10.1) In Johnrandallia, Heniochus, Hemitaurichthys, and Forcipiger, the posterior kidney produces posteriorly directed, bilateral extensions on either side of the first hemal spine.

10.2) In all other chaetodontids examined by Mok and Shen (including at least one representative from every terminal taxon in the present analysis), the posterior bilateral extensions fuse on the posterior side of the first hemal spine.

The relative similarities among the adult kidney morphologies infer a linear transformation series, in which state 1 is intermediate between states 0 and 2. Mok and Shen also reported ontogenetic support for this assumption; an 11 mm Chaetodon capistratus had state 1, whereas 21 and 50 mm specimens had state 2. (This was the only ontogenetic variation they found, but the 11 mm specimen was also the smallest chaetodontid they examined.)

11) Anterior branchiostegal rays free (Figs. 20 and 21). In all chaetodontids, the two anterior branchiostegals are not attached proximally to the anterior ceratohyal (as in outgroup taxa; Fig. 20A), but rather, they are simply suspended in the opercular membrane (Fig. 21). The chaetodontid arrangement is uniquely derived among percoids, as far as known. The four posterior rays retain their usual positions, attached proximally to the lateral surface of the ceratohyals, ventrally, and near the joint between the anterior and posterior ceratohyals. Within chaetodontids, deviation from the derived condition is rare. The only observed reversion to the primitive state in the entire survey was a case of bilateral asymmetry (Chelmon marginalis, Fig. 20B). The left side of this individual exhibits the more typical chaetodontid condition.

12) Branchiostegals rays reduced to five (Fig. 21B). All higher squamipennians (except Zanclus and the acanthurids), and most chaetodontids have six branchiostegal

Fig. 21. Lateral View of the Right Hyoid Arch in Amphichaetodon and Chaetodon. The stippled areas represent cartilage. A, Amphichaetodon howensis, AM I.17260-002, 53 mm; B, Chaetodon pelewensis, AMNH 66405, 64 mm.

Abbreviations:

ACH	Anterior Ceratohyal
BB I	First Basibranchial
BF	Beryciform Foramen
BH	Basihyal
BR	Branchiostegal Ray
DHH	Dorsal Hypohyal
FHA	Hyoid Artery Foramen
VHH	Ventral Hypohyal

A Drepane punctata

5 mm

B Chelmon rostratus

5 mm

Fig. 21. Lateral View of the Right Hyoid Arch in Amphichaetodon and Chaetodon. The stippled areas represent cartilage. A, Amphichaetodon howensis, 53 mm; B, Chaetodon pelewensis, 64 mm.

Abbreviations:

ACH	Anterior Ceratohyal
BB I	First Basibranchial
BF	Beryciform Foramen
BH	Basihyal
BR	Branchiostegal Ray
DHH	Dorsal Hypohyal
FHA	Hyoid Artery Foramen
VHH	Ventral Hypohyal

rays. Among chaetodontids, the species of Chelmonops, Chelmon, Coradion, Roaoops, Exornator, and Lepidochaetodon have only five. From the positions of the five remaining branchiostegals, the most anterior ray appears to be the missing one (it is also the smallest in chaetodontids with six). Because this is a loss character, the homology of the derived state cannot be evaluated among the taxa with only five. Accordingly, all taxa with five were given the same code. However, there is a substantial body of evidence (conflicting characters) that indicates this reduction occurred twice, once in the first three taxa listed above, and again in the latter three.

13) Basihyal shape (Figs. 20 and 21). The basihyal in most percoids and lower squamipennians is rod-shaped. It is also rod-shaped in Drepane (Fig 20A), scatophagids, and most chaetodontids (Fig 21B). In ehippidids, the basihyal is absent. Among the higher squamipennians, basihyals that are not rod-shaped occur in acanthuroids (wedge-shaped), and the pomacanthids (short and dorso-ventrally flattened). Reconstruction of basihyal evolution on the outgroup cladogram infers that the basihyal was simple and rod-shaped at the chaetodontid outgroup node. In Amphichaetodon (Fig. 21A), Chelmonops, Chelmon (Fig. 20B), Coradion, Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys, the basihyal is larger, more robust, and bears a prominent ventral keel. The keeled form is considered to be derived.

14) Foramen for hyoid artery present in dorsal hypohyal (Figs. 20 and 21). In most teleosts, the hyoid artery passes from the posterior side of the hyoid arch to the anterior through a foramen in the dorsal hypohyal. When this foramen is present in chaetodontids, it is more dorso-laterally situated than it is in other teleosts (Fig. 20B and 21A). The altered position of the foramen is correlated with an altered ontogeny (Fig. 22). In a wide variety of teleosts, the foramen is located centrally within the dorsal hypohyal. Although I have not observed the ontogeny of these structures in outgroup taxa, the central position of the foramen suggests that the hyoid artery passes through the cartilaginous precursor of the hypohyal before ossification occurs. In chaetodontids, the eccentric foramen forms after the main body of the hypohyal has ossified. A process of cartilage grows laterally from hypohyal's postero-dorsal edge (Fig. 22A and B), and then joins a second process growing dorsally from the lateral surface (Fig. 22C). In chaetodontids without the foramen, the cartilaginous processes never appear, and the hyoid artery simply passes over the dorsal surface of the dorsal hypohyal. The derived condition, foramen absent, is found in Forcipiger, Roops, Exornator, Lepidochaetodon, Parachaetodon, Megaprotodon, Gonochaetodon, Tetrachaetodon, Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus. The potential difference in the outgroup and ingroup ontogenies

Fig. 22. Ontogeny of the Foramen for the Hyoid Artery in the Dorsal Hypohyal. Three individuals of Chaetodon melannotus (USNM 266894) are drawn to the same scale. A, 18 mm; B, 27 mm; C, 42 mm.

2 mm

notwithstanding, this appears to be a case in which polarity determination by ontogenetic and outgroup criteria contradict each other. The foramen is clearly present in all outgroup taxa. Absence of the foramen is therefore derived among chaetodontids. However, absence results from a terminal deletion in the chaetodontid ontogeny. Recapitulation is not observed in this character.

15) Shape and orientation of the dorsal hypohyal (Figs. 20 and 21). In most of the outgroup taxa and in most chaetodontids, the dorsal hypohyal has a somewhat cuboid shape (Fig. 21). The anterior ceratohyal covers the lateral face of the cube. Figure 21B shows a derived condition in which the dorsal hypohyal is much thinner in the postero-medial to antero-lateral dimension, and the previously anterior surface now faces almost laterally. This is the surface covered by the anterior ceratohyal. This derived condition is found in Chelmonops, Chelmon, Coradion, Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys. While Forcipiger has a flat hypohyal, it also lacks a foramen for the hyoid artery (character 14). The presence of both derived states in Forcipiger creates a conflict between characters 14 and 15.

16.0) First epibranchial shape (5 states, unordered; Fig. 23). The first epibranchial is essentially a flat structure, and significant variation is limited to its shape in anterior view. The rod-like first pharyngobranchial

projects dorsally from the medial (left, Fig. 23) end of the epibranchial, and the first ceratobranchial projects ventrally from the lateral (right) end. The articulating surfaces are cartilaginous (stippled) in these joints. A third marginal cartilage is located on the dorsal edge of the epibranchial, and marks the postero-medial articulation with the interarcual cartilage (not illustrated), which in turn articulates with the second pharyngobranchial. In most percoids and some higher squamipennians, the first epibranchial is much longer than it is high (e.g. Drepane, Fig. 23A). In other higher squamipennians, the difference between these dimensions is not so extreme (e.g. Pomacanthus, Fig. 23B). Amphichaetodon (Fig. 23C) has an epibranchial shape equivalent to that found in pomacanthids. Because no other chaetodontid has a first epibranchial more similar to those found in other outgroups, the shape found in Amphichaetodon was assumed to be primitive for the family (the outgroup node and Amphichaetodon were coded as having state 0).

16.1) (Fig. 23D) Forcipiger possesses a uniquely shaped first epibranchial. The height and width are about equal, the axis is slightly inclined medially, the dorsal cartilage is relatively wide, and protrudes above the dorsal margin, and the lateral cartilage is relatively tall. There are no other chaetodontids with epibranchials this shape.

Fig. 23. Anterior View of Left Epibranchial. The stippled areas represent cartilage. A, Drepane punctata, USNM 267052, 49 mm; B, Centropyge loriculus, AMNH 88351, 51 mm; C, Amphichaetodon howensis, AM I.17260-002, 53 mm; D, Forcipiger flavissimus, AMNH 88368, 88 mm; E, Chelmonops truncatus, AMNH 88377, 78 mm; F, Chelmon mulleri, AMNH 88376, 80 mm; G, Coradion altivelis, AMNH 88359, 54 mm; H, Heniochus varius, AMNH 88363, 54 mm; I, Hemitaurichthys thompsoni, AMNH 88395, 94 mm; J, Johnrandallia nigrirostris, SU 47435, 60 mm.

Abbreviations:

EB I	First Epibranchial
CB I	First Ceratobranchial
PB I	First Pharyngobranchial

Fig. 23. (continued) Anterior View of Left Epibranchial.
K, Chaetodon oligacanthus (=Parachaetodon
ocellatus), AMNH 88421, 84 mm; L, Prognathodes
(=Chaetodon) aya, USNM 266900, 54 mm; M, Roa
(=Chaetodon) modestus, CAS 15897, 48 mm; N,
Chaetodon nigropunctatus, AMNH 88386, 63 mm; O,
Chaetodon capistratus, USNM 266896, 43 mm; P,
Chaetodon adiergastos, USNM 267051, 52 mm; Q,
Chaetodon kleinii, AMNH 88430, 69 mm; R,
Chaetodon pelewensis, AMNH 88405, 64 mm; S,
Chaetodon multicinctus, AMNH 88389, 72 mm; T,
Chaetodon baronessa, USNM 266891, 55 mm; U,
Chaetodon rainfordi, AMNH 88398, 58 mm; V,
Chaetodon plebeius, AMNH 88438, 52 mm; W,
Chaetodon trifascialis, AMNH 88413, 55 mm; X,
Chaetodon trifasciatus, AMNH 88414, 43 mm; Y,
Chaetodon reticulatus, AMNH 88415, 49 mm.

16.2) The third state (2 in Table 6) is present in the genera Chelmonops, Chelmon, and Coradion (Fig. 23E, F and G, respectively). The height to width ratio is approximately 0.75, the axis is slightly inclined medially, and all of the cartilages are relatively small (particularly the dorsal and lateral ones).

16.3) The genera Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys (Fig. 23H, I, and J, respectively) share the fourth state (3). The height and width are about equal, the axis is horizontal, the medial cartilage is small, whereas the dorsal and lateral cartilages are wide and tall, respectively, and a sharp angle is formed by the margin of the bone between the medial and dorsal cartilages.

16.4) All of the remaining chaetodontids (Parachaetodon and all members of Chaetodon sensu Burgess [1978]) share state 5 (Fig. 23K-Y). The height to width ratio is slightly less than one, the axis is slightly declined medially, the medial cartilage is larger than in all other taxa, and the dorsal and lateral cartilages are of moderate size. There are many more species with this state than any other. Perhaps consequentially, there is more variation in this state than any other. However, despite its magnitude, the variation within state 4 is essentially continuous, whereas a discrete difference exists between these shapes and those of other states.

17) Third basibranchial and hypobranchial shapes (Fig. 24). In all higher squamipennians, the third basibranchial is broad and flat (Fig. 24, Microcanthus). The medial margin of the third hypobranchial is a smooth curve, and lacks any accessory processes. Similar shapes of both bones are also found in Amphichaetodon. In all other chaetodontids, the third basibranchial is not flattened, but narrow and rod-like (at least posteriorly; Fig. 24, Chaetodon). The third hypobranchial bears a medial flange that fills the space left by the laterally constricted hypobranchial. Because the third basi- and hypobranchials do not actually articulate with each other, one cannot be certain that the shapes of these bones are constrained to covary (developmentally, or otherwise). However, because the two elements are closely juxtaposed, these shape changes are treated here as a single character.

18.0) Jaw morphology, tooth arrangement, and tooth morphology (9 states, ordered; Figs. 25, 26, and 27; see Appendix B description of tooth replacement). All aspects of jaw morphology are interpreted as a single complex character. Within chaetodontids, it is apparent that the tooth arrangement changes in concert with tooth morphology, and jaw morphology changes in concert with tooth arrangement. Further, virtually all changes in the premaxilla are accompanied by equivalent or coordinated changes in the dentary. These observations support the

Fig. 24. Third Basi- and Hypobranchials. Figured are the third basibranchial and third left hypobranchial. The stippled areas represent cartilage, and the dotted lines indicate the extent of the posterior cartilaginous plug (where the hypobranchial is still perichondral). A, Microcanthus strigatus, USNM 267047, 34 mm, B, Amphichaetodon howensis, AM I.17260-002, 53 mm, C, Chaetodon rafflesii, AMNH 88387, 56 mm.

Abbreviations:

BB III	Third Basibranchial
HB III	Third Hypobranchial

assumption that a high degree of functional integration (and therefore transformational correlation) exists among the attributes of jaw morphology. Interpreting these attributes as a single complex character minimizes the potential for exaggerating their inference. A single branching transformation series was inferred from the similarities among forms.

Chaetodontids and pomacanthids share a unique process of tooth replacement. The arrangement of teeth within a given individual is expected to vary according to the cycle of tooth replacement. Care was taken to omit the variation induced by tooth replacement from the assessment of differences among taxa.

Pomacanthids and chaetodontids share several derived features of jaw morphology and tooth arrangement. There are approximately three bands of tooth rows that extend laterally from the median symphysis in both the premaxilla and dentary. The premaxilla is oriented almost horizontally, thus the teeth are produced anteriorly, and curve toward the vertical. The alveoli of the most lingual teeth extend anteriorly as far as the more labial alveoli. The largest teeth (the most labial along the symphysis) are at least five times longer than the shortest teeth (lingual and lateral). The orientation of alveoli, and range in tooth lengths are similar in the dentary.

18.1) (Fig. 25, A and B) The primitive tooth and jaw morphology of chaetodontids was assumed to have the following attributes: teeth setiform; tooth caps unicuspid and slightly spatulate; four to five fold length difference between the most labial and lingual teeth; axes of alveoli along the median symphysis parallel; teeth produced from the jaws anteriorly (about 30 degrees from the horizontal); three bands of tooth rows along the median symphysis; three overlapping rows in the most labial band (when complete); distance along the median symphysis between the lingual and labial margins of the jaw only slightly less than the width of the jaw (measured tangent to the lingual margin of the jaw).

Several of these features are plesiomorphic, or of unknown polarity. Among squamipennians, setiform teeth are found not only in chaetodontids, but also in Microcanthus, pomacanthids, Drepane, some ehippidids, and scatophagids. This distribution infers that setiform teeth are primitive for higher squamipennians. The tooth caps of the setiform teeth are tricuspid in pomacanthids Platax, and scatophagids, but unicuspid and slightly spatulate in Microcanthus, chaetodontids, and Drepane. This distribution makes it impossible to determine whether the presence of unicuspid teeth in chaetodontids is derived or plesiomorphic. In most chaetodontids and outgroup taxa, the descending process of the premaxilla is toothed, and the

Fig. 25. Tooth Arrangements in Chaetodon, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys. (See caption of Fig. 4 for general explanation.) A, Chaetodon (Chaetodon) capistratus, AMNH 88439, 78 mm premaxilla; B, same individual as in A, dentary; C, Heniochus varius, AMNH 88363, 54 mm, pemaxilla, view is much more ventral (note that ascending and articular processes of premaxilla are visible); D, Hemitaurichthys polylepis, AMNH 88442, 116 mm, premaxilla.

angle between the ascending and descending premaxillary processes is approximately 90 degrees.

Other attributes of the primitive chaetodontid morphology are not found in the outgroups, and are therefore derived for the family. The alveolar region of the jaw is significantly longer at the median symphysis than it is in pomacanthids or any of the other outgroup taxa (compare jaws of three outgroup genera, Chaetodipterus, Pomacanthus, and Chaetodontoplus, Fig. 4, with any chaetodontid, Figs. 25-7).

In pomacanthids, the positions of tooth rows and gaps indicate that the waves of tooth replacement in adjacent rows are nearly 180 degrees out of phase. There is little overlap between adjacent rows, thus each band is never more than two rows wide. In chaetodontids, the tooth rows and gaps are positioned such that there is almost always an overlap of at least three rows within each band.

The primitive chaetodontid jaw morphology occurs in Amphichaetodon, Prognathodes, Roa, Chaetodon, Rabdophorus, Roops, and Parachaetodon, as well as most species of Exornator, and Lepidochaetodon. Exceptions in the latter two subgenera are the members of the Chaetodon punctatofasciatus complex and Chaetodon unimaculatus (Motta, 1985; and pers. obs.). The morphologies in the latter exceptions are considered to be autapomorphies.

As interpreted here, the primitive chaetodontid state encompasses more variation than any other. For example,

cross-sectional tooth shape differentiates Amphichaetodon from most of the others listed above. The tooth shafts are round in Amphichaetodon, but laterally compressed in the others. Amphichaetodon was included in the primitive state because this attribute cannot be polarized. Most squamipennians with setiform teeth have round tooth shafts, but pomacanthids have teeth that are laterally compressed. Interpreting the primitive chaetodontid state broadly, in this case, minimizes the possibility of making an erroneous inference from a labile attribute.

The jaw and tooth morphologies observed in other chaetodontids were interpreted as resulting from three, lines of specialization, each derived independently from the primitive chaetodontid condition (all three lines are dissimilar).

18.2) (Fig. 26A) In Chelmonops, a significant elongation of the jaws affects the alveolar regions in several ways. The more labial alveoli are well anterior of more lingual ones. The teeth are produced from the jaws more dorso-ventrally (about 60 degrees from the horizontal), and the most labial teeth are only about three times the length of the most lingual teeth). The rows of teeth run in a more antero-posterior direction (but still follow the lateral margin of the jaw), thus there are more rows per band. In Chelmonops, the maximum number of rows per band is approximately 15, whereas in the primitive form it ranges

Fig. 26. Tooth Arrangements in Chelmonops, Chelmon, and Coradion. (See caption of Fig. 4 for general explanation.) In all photographs A-D, view is nearly from the vertical (ventral for premaxillae, A-C, dorsal for dentary, D). A, Chelmonops truncatus, AMNH 88375, 77 mm, premaxilla; B, Chelmon rostratus, AMNH 88371, 73 mm, premaxilla; C, Coradion chrysozonus, AMNH 88396, 71 mm, premaxilla, medial is to upper right; D, same individual as in C, dentary, medial is to lower right.

between 5 and 10. (The highest counts are always obtained in the most lingual band that still extends to the median symphysis.) It should also be noted that because of the potential for allometry between tooth size and jaw size, these counts may increase with size. In Chelmonops, the increased length of the alveolar region is also accompanied by an increase in the number of bands, from three to four.

18.3) (Derived from 18.2; Fig. 26B) In Chelmon, the length of the alveolar region is further increased, and virtually all of the features noted in Chelmonops are exaggerated. Most significantly, the teeth are shorter, produced from the jaws almost vertically, and there are six bands of teeth in the premaxilla.

In Coradion (Fig. 26, C and D), the teeth are so reduced in size and number that the dentition may be described as vestigial. Nevertheless, there are several features of the dentition and jaws that suggest the morphology of Coradion was derived from one like that in Chelmon or Chelmonops. A feature seen only in Coradion and Chelmon is the almost vertical orientation of the teeth. It is difficult to discern a pattern of tooth arrangement in the premaxilla of Coradion, but at least four bands are evident in the dentary. In most chaetodontids (including Chelmonops), the articular and ascending processes of the premaxilla are separated by a deep ventral groove. In Chelmon, the length of the groove is reduced anteriorly, and

the posterior end is closed by bone that joins the tip of the articular process to the ascending process. In Coradion, the groove is absent as the articular and ascending processes are completely fused.

The jaws of Coradion do not have the extreme length seen in Chelmon, but neither can its jaw morphology be considered intermediate between the primitive chaetodontid state and the long form. In some respects, Coradion is even more different from the primitive form than Chelmon. For example, the jaw teeth in Coradion are short, straight, and spike-like. The teeth in the long-jawed form have an intermediate form, short, but still curved.

The details of jaw morphology shared by Coradion and Chelmon are: the vertical orientation of the teeth, the shortened length of the teeth, the presence of more than three bands of tooth rows, and the partial fusion of the ascending and articular premaxillary processes. All of the features unique to Coradion, the completely fused ascending and articular processes, the anteriorly convex descending premaxillary process, and the disorganized tooth arrangement, are all consistent with a hypothesis in which the short-jawed form of Coradion was derived from a long-jawed (Chelmon-like) form by reduction. Coradion was considered to be autapomorphic relative to Chelmon, and was not given a separate character state in this analysis.

18.4) (Derived from 18.1; Fig. 25C) The jaw morphology in Heniochus is similar to the primitive chaetodontid condition, but slightly reduced. The teeth are shorter, straighter, and the alveolar region is only deep enough to contain two bands of tooth rows.

In Hemitaurichthys, the reductions seen in Heniochus are taken even further. The teeth are exceptionally short, round in cross-section, and the alveolar region of the jaw is only long enough to contain a single complete band of tooth rows (Fig. 25D). Hemitaurichthys was considered to be autapomorphic relative to Heniochus, and was not given a separate character state.

The jaw morphology of Forcipiger (not illustrated, but see Motta, 1988, fig. 9A and B) presents a combination of unique attributes and conflicting similarities to other genera. Chelmon is the only genus whose jaw length approaches that of Forcipiger. However, the arrangements of teeth in these genera are different. In Chelmon, the tooth rows are oriented almost antero-posteriorly, the bands of teeth are very wide, and at least six bands traverse the median symphysis. In Forcipiger, the tooth rows are oriented in the more typical antero-medial to postero-lateral direction, the alveoli are confined to a relatively narrow region at the tip of the jaw (and the jaw margins in F. flavissimus), and only three bands of teeth traverse the median symphysis. These are all primitive attributes, and

indicate that the jaw morphology of Forcipiger is not necessarily an elaboration of the Chelmon morphology.

The ontogeny of tooth arrangement in Forcipiger implies a different phylogenetic origin. In a 47 mm F. flavissimus post-larva (taken in a plankton tow, and bearing the full complement of hypertrophied dermal bones that characterize tholichthys larvae), the teeth are confined to the anterior tips of the jaw, the lateral margins of the jaws are edentulous, and only two bands of teeth traverse the median symphysis. In two smaller larvae, there are either no teeth (10.5 mm), or only a single row of teeth (13.8 mm). Larvae of Rabdophorus species that are 10 to 15 mm in length have already attained many of the adult dental characteristics, including three discrete bands of tooth rows across the median symphysis and teeth on the lateral margins of the jaws. The relatively delayed dental ontogeny in Forcipiger is similar to that seen in Heniochus and Hemitaurichthys. Because the jaw morphology immediately primitive to Forcipiger (i.e. from which it was derived) cannot be hypothesized with any confidence, Forcipiger was coded as "unknown" in all of the binary characters that represent derivations of jaw morphology beyond the primitive chaetodontid form. This coding technique allows the character to be treated as partially ordered, and precludes jaw morphology from affecting the cladistic position of Forcipiger.

18.5) (Derived from 18.1; Figs. 27 and 28) In Megaprotodon, Gonochaetodon, Tetrachaetodon, Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus, several attributes of jaw morphology combine to increase the number of bands along the median symphysis. The length of the alveolar region along the median symphysis is slightly increased. The number of teeth within a row is decreased, thus the rows are shorter, there is less overlap of tooth rows within a band, and the bands are more narrow. As each band is narrower and the medial depth of the alveolar region is increased, there is enough room for more than three bands along the median symphysis in individuals larger than 50 mm. (The allometry between tooth size and jaw size, contributes to an increase in band number in larger individuals.) The factors responsible for the increased number of bands in these taxa are clearly different from those that contribute to the numerically similar increase in the Chelmon line.

A shorter jaw morphology in these taxa contributes to an overall reduction in snout length. The ascending and articular processes of the premaxilla, and the dentary are all relatively shorter. The alveoli in the premaxilla are positioned more posteriorly relative to the descending process. In the premaxilla of the primitive condition, the tips of the most labial alveoli extend forward to the anterior margin of the descending process. In these taxa,

Fig. 27. Tooth Arrangements in juvenile and sub-adult Discochaetodon. (See caption of Fig. 4 for general explanation.) A, Chaetodon (Discochaetodon) aureofasciatus, AMNH 88401, 47 mm (juvenile), premaxilla, immature (short) alveoli are visible on the lateral (left) ends of several tooth rows, partially resorbed tooth pedestals are visible on the medial ends. B, same individual as in A, dentary. C, Chaetodon (Discochaetodon) rainfordi, AMNH 88446, 76 mm, premaxilla. D, same individual as in C, dentary.

the alveoli extend to only the posterior margin of the descending process.

18.6) (Derived from 18.5) In Megaprotodon, Gonochaetodon, Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus, the individual teeth are straighter than they are in more primitive conditions, and the descending process of the premaxilla is edentulous.

18.7) (Derived from 18.6; Fig. 28, C and D) In Corallochaetodon and Citharoedus, there are usually only 3 or 4 teeth per row, there are many more rows per band, and there are more bands in each jaw. The bands do not curve ventrally toward the lateral edges in the premaxilla (or dorsally in the dentary), but instead traverse the jaw horizontally. Individual teeth are finer and straighter. (Their cross-sections have smaller dimensions, and although the enameloid tooth caps are more sharply hooked, the tooth shafts are virtually straight). Two attributes of jaw structure are modified to cause the teeth to coalesce distally into a tight brush. The lengths of the lingual and labial teeth are almost equal, and the alveoli are not parallel, but directed convergently, like the spokes in a bicycle wheel (from the rim to the hub).

The gross morphology of the upper jaw is also modified.

In all other chaetodontids, the angle between the ascending and descending processes of the premaxilla is equal to or less than 90 degrees. In Corallochaetodon and Citharoedus,

Fig. 28. Tooth Arrangements in Tetrachaetodon and Citharoedus. (See caption of Fig. 4 for general explanation.) A, Chaetodon (Tetrachaetodon) bennetti, AMNH 88448, 120 mm, premaxilla. B, same individual as A, dentary. C, Chaetodon (Citharoedus) ornatissimus, AMNH 88447, 146 mm, premaxilla. D, same individual as C, dentary.

this angle is significantly more obtuse (ca. 120°). In more primitive conditions, the ascending premaxillary process is significantly longer than the descending process. In this most derived condition, these two processes are of approximately equal length. Further, the articular process is extremely short and the articular surface, which rides across the top of the vomer, is at a significant angle to the ascending process.

19.0) Vomerine teeth (3 states, ordered). A cursory survey of percoids indicates that the presence of vomerine teeth is highly variable. Vomerine teeth appear to be gained and lost with relative ease. Among fishes more closely related to chaetodontids, vomerine teeth are present in the first and third outgroups, the Pomacanthidae, and lower squamipennians, respectively. But they are almost uniformly absent in the second outgroup, Drepane, ehippidids, scatophagids, and acanthuroids (being present among these fishes only in the ehippidid genus Platax). Reconstruction of gain and loss on the outgroup cladogram infers that the common ancestor of pomacanthids and chaetodontids had vomerine teeth.

Three conditions were scored within chaetodontids: vomer toothed (0), partially toothed (1), and toothless (2).

A linear transformation series was assumed between the three states. Well developed vomerine teeth occur in

Amphichaetodon, Parachaetodon, Roa, Chaetodon, Rabdophorus, Roops, and Exornator.

19.1) Partially toothed vomers occur in Lepidochaetodon, Gonochaetodon, and Tetrachaetodon.

19.2) Completely edentulous vomers occur in all other terminal taxa.

20) Ethmoid foramen for olfactory nerve. In most percoids and all higher squamipennians, the ethmoid foramen for the olfactory nerve is completely enclosed in the lateral ethmoid. This condition is also found in most chaetodontids. In Chelmonops, Chelmon, Coradion, Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys a derived condition is present, in which the medial margin of this foramen is formed by the mesethmoid. Thus, the olfactory nerve is not completely surrounded by the lateral ethmoid, but passes between the lateral and mesethmoids.

21.0) Quality of bone comprising the posterior face of the mesethmoid (3 states, ordered). In pomacanthids, the perichondral bone that comprises the posterior face of the mesethmoid is a solid sheet, without perforations of any kind. Among chaetodontids, similar membrane bone is present in Amphichaetodon, Forcipiger, Heniochus, Hemitaurichthys, Roa, Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus.

21.1) Posterior face of the mesethmoid sieve-like. In Johnrandallia, Parachaetodon, Megaprotodon, Gonochaetodon, and Tetrachaetodon, the bone comprising the posterior face

of the mesethmoid is not completely ossified, but is instead sieve-like, being perforated by numerous small holes. The morphology present in these taxa appears to be ontogenetically terminal as it is present in specimens ranging from 30 to over 100 mm SL.

21.2) Posterior face of the mesethmoid lace-like. In Chelmonops, Chelmon, Coradion, Prognathodes, Chaetodon, Rabdophorus, Roaops, Exornator, and Lepidochaetodon, the holes in the posterior face of the mesethmoid comprise a greater total area than does the bone. This condition is termed lace-like.

22) Posterior face of mesethmoid extends posterior to lateral ethmoids. In the other squamipennians with inverted mesethmoids, pomacanthids and Drepane, the mesethmoid extends posteriorly into the interorbital region, past the lateral ethmoids. Within chaetodontids, a second state is present, in which the mesethmoid is inverted but does not extend into the interorbital region. This condition occurs in Amphichaetodon, Forcipiger, Heniochus, Hemitaurichthys, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus. Because (1) taxa of the second and third outgroups have a third state, mesethmoids not inverted, and (2) there is no strong evidence for assuming a transformation series between the three states, the polarity of this character was determined using the algorithm for unordered characters presented by Maddison et al, 1984 (p. 101). The state present in pomacanthids,

mesethmoid extending posterior to lateral ethmoids, was assumed to be primitive.

23) Vertical ridges present on the anterior surface of the mesethmoid, lateral to the premaxillary fenestra. In pomacanthids, the anterior vertical face of the mesethmoid is flat. In Amphichaetodon, Chelmonops, Chelmon, Coradion, Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, Hemitaurichthys, Roa, and Prognathodes, the mesethmoid bears two well defined ridges on its anterior face. The ridges run vertically, one on either side of the premaxillary fenestra, and just medial to the suture between the lateral and mesethmoid. They also extend a small distance anteriorly, over the portion of the mesethmoid that roofs the anterior ethmoid cartilage. A morphology more similar to that in pomacanthids, ridges absent, is present in Parachaetodon and all species of Chaetodon (sensu Burgess, except Prognathodes and Roa). This condition was assumed to be primitive, and ridges-present was considered derived.

24) Ethmo-maxillary Ligament Absent. In the percoids examined, the ethmo-maxillary ligament originates on the anterior surface of the mesethmoid, near the mesethmo-nasal articulation. The ethmo-maxillary ligament descends laterally to the anterior end of the maxilla, where it inserts on the dorsal-lateral arm of the maxillary head. In ehippidids, and scatophagids (basal members of the second outgroup), an ethmo-palatine ligament branches from the

ethmo-maxillary ligament near its origin on the mesethmoid, and descends laterally, joining the fibers of the palato-palatine ligament near their origin on the palatine. The palato-palatine ligament originates on the medial surface of palatine at the base of the maxillary process, then arcs across the snout passing over the ethmo-maxillary ligament.

This is almost precisely the morphology Stiassny (1986) describes in Morone saxatilis. (Stiassny did not name the ethmo-palatine ligament, but refers to it as a "small branch" of the ethmo-maxillary ligament; p. 430.) The only difference between Morone and these members of the second outgroup is that, in the latter, the palato-palatine ligament passes over the ethmo-maxillary ligament instead of under it.

Pomacanthids have a derived set of dorsally directed palatine ligaments. Three ligaments originate medially at the base of the palatine's maxillary process. The smallest is the most posterior, and proceeds dorsally to insert on the ventro-medial surface of the nasal bone. A palato-nasal ligament was not seen in any other percoids examined. The palato-palatine ligament is present in pomacanthids as it is in other percoids. The third is one of two palato-maxillary ligaments, both of which insert on the lateral arm of the maxillary head. A standard one, found in most percoids, originates at the tip of the palatine's maxillary process. A novel one, not seen in any other squamipennians,

originates medially at the base of the palatine's maxillary process, near the origins of the palato-nasal and palato-palatine ligaments. (It may be homologous to the ethmo-maxillary ligament that is present in most percoids.) There are no buccal ligaments originating on the mesethmoid.

Among chaetodontids, the ethmo-maxillary ligament is present in Amphichaetodon, Chelmonops, Chelmon, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys. In these taxa, it originates on an apophysis located on the dorso-lateral margin of the mesethmoid's premaxillary fenestra. It inserts laterally on the lateral arm of the maxillary head. This condition closely approximates the condition found in the basal taxa of the second outgroup as well as most other percoids. The ethmo-maxillary ligament is absent in Coradion, Forcipiger, Parachaetodon, and all members of Chaetodon (sensu Burgess, 1978). Because this ligament is present in the second and more distant outgroups, but absent in the first outgroup, this character cannot be polarized. The character was coded as follows: outgroup node (?); ligament present (0); ligament absent (1).

25.0) Origin of the palato-palatine ligament and direction of the palatine's maxillary process (3 states, ordered; Fig. 29). In primitive chaetodontids, as in most squamipennians, the palato-palatine ligament originates medially at the base of the palatine's maxillary process

Fig. 29. Anterior Bones of the Palate in Rabdophorus. The right palatine, ectopterygoid, mesopterygoid, and quadrate are shown in medial view. Anterior is to the left. Chaetodon (Rabdophorus) rafflesi, AMNH 88387, 56 mm.

Abbreviations:

ECP	Ectopterygoid
MPP	Maxillary Process of Palatine
MSP	Mesopterygoid
PAL	Palatine
PPL	Palato-palatine Ligament
Q	Quadrate

Chaetodon rafflesi

(Fig. 29). The maxillary process projects from the basal portion antero-dorsally and laterally.

25.1) (Fig. 30) In Roaops, Exornator, Lepidochaetodon, Parachaetodon, Megaprotodon, and Gonochaetodon, a small dorso-laterally projecting apophysis is present at the base of the palatine's maxillary process. The fibers of the palato-palatine ligament originate either in a strip that extends from the postero-medial base of the maxillary process up the anterior side of the apophysis, or entirely on the small apophysis.

25.2) (Figs. 31, 32, and 33) In Tetrachaetodon, Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus the palato-palatine ligament originates exclusively on the apophysis, which is significantly taller than it is in the more plesiomorphic conditions. The palatine's maxillary process projects from the basal section anteriorly, instead of antero-dorsally as it does in the more primitive forms.

26.0) Ventro-medial palatine ligaments (3 states, ordered). In squamipennians, there are three ligaments that bind the palatine to the more medial skeletal elements. The most posterior ligament originates on the lateral ethmoid, and descends a short distance to the postero-dorsal edge of the palatine. The anterior ones are closely juxtaposed, originate on the vomer, proceed a short distance postero-laterally, and insert on the anterior edge of the palatine's base.

Fig. 30. Anterior Bones of the Palate in Gonochaetodon. The right palatine, ectopterygoid, mesopterygoid, and quadrate are shown in medial view. Anterior is to the left. Chaetodon (Gonochaetodon) baronessa, USNM 266891, 55 mm.

Abbreviations:

ECP	Ectopterygoid
MPP	Maxillary Process of Palatine
MSP	Mesopterygoid
PAL	Palatine
PPL	Palato-palatine Ligament
Q	Quadrate

Chaetodon baronessa

Fig. 31. Anterior Bones of the Palate in Tetrachaetodon. The right palatine, ectopterygoid, mesopterygoid, and quadrate are shown in medial view. Anterior is to the left. Chaetodon (Tetrachaetodon) speculum, AMNH 88408, 50 mm.

Abbreviations:

ECP	Ectopterygoid
MPP	Maxillary Process of Palatine
MSP	Mesopterygoid
PAL	Palatine
PPL	Palato-palatine Ligament
Q	Quadrate

Chaetodon speculum

Fig. 32. Anterior Bones of the Palate in Discochaetodon. The right palatine, ectopterygoid, mesopterygoid, and quadrate are shown in medial view. Anterior is to the left. Chaetodon (Discochaetodon) rainfordi, AMNH 88398, 58 mm.

Abbreviations:

ECP	Ectopterygoid
MPP	Maxillary Process of Palatine
MSP	Mesopterygoid
PAL	Palatine
PPL	Palato-palatine Ligament
Q	Quadrate

Chaetodon rainfordi

Fig. 33. Anterior Bones of the Palate in Corallochaetodon. The right palatine, ectopterygoid, mesopterygoid, and quadrate are shown in medial view. Anterior is to the left. Chaetodon (Corallochaetodon) trifasciatus, AMNH 88414, 43 mm.

Abbreviations:

ECP	Ectopterygoid
MPP	Maxillary Process of Palatine
MSP	Mesopterygoid
PAL	Palatine
PPL	Palato-palatine Ligament
Q	Quadrate

Chaetodon trifasciatus

Fig. 34. Anterior Bones of the Palate in Citharoedus. The right palatine, ectopterygoid, mesopterygoid, and quadrate are shown in medial view. Anterior is to the left. Chaetodon (Citharoedus) ornatissimus, AMNH 88417, 55 mm.

Abbreviations:

ECP	Ectopterygoid
MPP	Maxillary Process of Palatine
MSP	Mesopterygoid
PAL	Palatine
PPL	Palato-palatine Ligament
Q	Quadrate

Chaetodon ornatissimus

26.1) In chaetodontids, the two vomero-palatine ligaments are more widely separated, one becoming vertical, and the other remaining horizontal. The horizontal vomero-palatine ligament retains the more primitive sites of origin and insertion, while the vertical ligament originates slightly more anteriorly on the lateral face of the vomer, and inserts more dorsally on the palatine, at the base of the maxillary process.

26.2) In Chelmonops, Chelmon, Coradion, Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys, the vertical palato-vomerine ligament inserts well up on the palatine's maxillary process, and is more widely separated from the horizontal vomero-palatine ligament than it is in other chaetodontids.

26.3) (Derived from 25.1) In all species of Chaetodon (sensu Burgess) except those of Megaprotodon, Parachaetodon, Gonochaetodon, Tetrachaetodon, and Discochaetodon, the insertion of the vertical vomero-palatine ligament is marked by a distinct antero-ventrally directed apophysis on the palatine.

27) Shape of basal palatine. In most squamipennians, the base of the palatine is roughly triangular in sagittal view. The posterior edge of the triangle is oriented vertically. The mesopterygoid articulates with the palatine on the dorsal portion of this edge, and the ectopterygoid articulates with the palatine on the ventral portion. The

second edge of the triangle runs antero-dorsally from the postero-ventral articulation with the ectopterygoid to the antero-dorsal articulation with the vomer. The third edge of the triangle is oriented horizontally just lateral to the parasphenoid. The maxillary process arises from the anterior corner of the triangle. In Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys, a derived condition occurs in which the basal section of the palatine is dorso-ventrally narrow and almost rod-like, being approximately only twice the diameter of the maxillary process.

28) Ectopterygoid width (Figs. 29-34). The ectopterygoids in most percoids and squamipennians are flat, and boomerang-shaped, with one arm directed ventrally and the other directed antero-dorsally. The arms are approximately equal in size and thin in their antero-posterior dimension. In pomacanthids and chaetodontids, the antero-dorsal arm is distinctly shorter than the ventral one. In most chaetodontids, the ectopterygoid is further differentiated from the more general condition in that the ventral arm is very broad antero-posteriorly (Figs. 29 and 30). This broadening appears to be associated with the prognathous condition found in most chaetodontids. In the otherwise very derived taxa Tetrachaetodon, Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus, the jaws are not as produced as they are in more typical chaetodontids, and the ventral arm of the ectopterygoid reverts to a thinner form

(Figs. 31-34). The presence of a thin ectopterygoid in the short-snouted chaetodontids is apparently a reversal. The thin form found in the outgroups and four taxa listed above was coded as 0, and the wide form was coded as 1.

29) Second circumorbital excluded from margin of the orbit. In most of the percoids and all of lower squamipennians examined, the circumorbital bones are present in a simple series, with no overlap between adjacent elements. In particular, the second circumorbital separates the third from the lacrimal (first circumorbital), and the second lies along the orbital margin. This condition is also present in at least two members of the second outgroup, Drepane and Rhinoprenes. In other members of the second outgroup, (e.g. Platax and scatophagids), the third circumorbital makes contact with the lacrimal, medial to the second circumorbital. However, this contact does not displace the second ventrally. (The circumorbital morphologies in siganids and acanthurids are derived in a different way, and not relevant to polarizing the variation that occurs among chaetodontids.)

In pomacanthids, the contact between the third circumorbital and the lacrimal is extensive enough to displace the second ventrally. The second remains in the path of the of the sensory canal, but no longer lies in the margin of the orbit. In all chaetodontids, the lacrimal makes contact with third circumorbital medially. In

Parachaetodon and all species of Chaetodon sensu Burgess (1978), the second is reduced in size and excluded from the margin of the orbit (state 1, Table 6). In all of Burgess's other genera, the second is not reduced and remains in the margin of the orbit (state 0).

Outgroup comparison cannot polarize the character as state 1 is found in the first outgroup, and state 0 is found in the second and third. Therefore, the hypothetical ancestor was coded as ambiguous, or unknown. (The second circumorbital is absent in the three species of Citharoedus, but this unambiguously derived condition is an autapomorphy in this analysis.)

30) Third circumorbital bone with large ventral lamina. In all outgroup taxa, the ventral circumorbital bones are only slightly larger than the sensory canals they enclose (except the lacrimal, which contains two antero-ventral branches of the sensory canal and is therefore a large laminar ossification). In Johnrandallia, Heniochus, Hemitaurichthys, and Prognathodes, the third circumorbital bears a large, ventrally projecting, lateral lamina.

The lamina is largest in Prognathodes, being almost as tall as it is long, and extends more than half the distance from orbit to the horizontal arm of the preopercle. In the other three taxa, it is at most only two thirds as tall as it is long, and extends less than half the distance to the preopercle. The circumorbital morphology in Prognathodes is

further differentiated from the other three in that the second circumorbital is excluded from the orbit (see character 26, above), and it, too, bears a ventral lamina similar to that on the third (probably due to an expanded field of ossification). The presence of the lamina and the position of the second circumorbital (character 26) are incompatible within the chaetodontids; at least one of them has undergone homoplastic evolution.

31) Parietal reduced dorso-ventrally (Figs. 35 and 36). Pomacanthids and chaetodontids share an antero-posterior reduction of the parietal (Fig. 35). Within chaetodontids, a further dorso-ventral reduction occurs such that the ventro-lateral extent of the parietal is diminished (Fig. 36). The parietal remains in contact with the supraoccipital dorsally, but loses its ventral contact with the pterotic. The space left by the contracted parietal is filled by an antero-lateral expansion of the epioccipital (epiotic), which then contacts the posterior margin of the frontal. The epioccipital and frontal are primitively separate.

32) Lateral extrascapular not enclosing temporal canal (Fig. 37). The lateral extrascapular primitively encloses the junction of three sensory canals. It receives the posttemporal posteriorly, the supratemporal commissure dorsally, and the temporal canal antero-ventrally. In lower squamipennians, the lateral faces of these canals are either

Fig. 35. Lateral View of the Posterior Neurocranium in Chelmonops. Chelmonops truncatus, AMNH 88375, 77 mm. The epioccipital is confined to the posterior face of the neurocranium, and does not make contact with the frontal. The parietal contacts the pterotic ventrally.

Abbreviations:

ASP	Autosphenotic
BSP	Basisphenoid
BOC	Basioccipital
EPO	Epioccipital (=Epiotic)
EXO	Exoccipital
FR	Frontal
PAR	Parasphenoid
PTL	Parietal
PRO	Prootic
PTO	Pterotic
PTS	Pterosphenoid
SOC	Supraoccipital

Chelmonops truncatus

Fig. 36. Lateral View of the Posterior Neurocranium in Chaetodon. Chaetodon ulietensis, AMNH 88384, 55 mm. The lateral component of the epioccipital makes contact with the frontal, and separates the parietal from the pterotic.

Abbreviations:

ASP	Autosphenotic
BOC	Basioccipital
EPO	Epioccipital (=Epiotic)
EXO	Exoccipital
FR	Frontal
PAR	Parasphenoid
PTL	Parietal
PRO	Prootic
PTO	Pterotic
PTS	Pterosphenoid
SOC	Supraoccipital

Chaetodon ulietensis

completely enclosed, or a continuous small slit remains along the lateral faces of the horizontal canals (posttemporal and temporal). (The specimens in which the latter condition was observed are all small, and it is possible that this condition represents an earlier ontogenetic stage.) In the second outgroup, the former condition is consistently present; the lateral extrascapular encloses all three canals at their juncture. In pomacanthids, the lateral extrascapular encloses only the parietal canal, the horizontal canals remain completely exposed laterally. In chaetodontids, two conditions are found, one of which matches that found in the second outgroup (all canals completely enclosed; Fig. 37A). The second chaetodontid condition is characterized by both the temporal canal and the junction of all three being exposed laterally (Fig. 37B).

The second condition is found only in chaetodontids, which infers that it is derived. But it can also be interpreted as intermediate between the most primitive, completely enclosed condition, and the most derived, pomacanthid condition, where both of the horizontal canals are exposed laterally. In this 0-1-2 progression, where 0 occurs in the second outgroup, 0 and 1 in chaetodontids, and 2 in the first outgroup, the polarity between the two chaetodontid states is ambiguous. Accordingly, the

Fig. 37. Lateral View of the Right Lateral Extrascapular. A, Roa modestus, CAS 15897, 48 mm; the temporal, posttemporal, and supratemporal canals, and their triple junction are enclosed in the lateral extrascapular. B, Chaetodon ulietensis, AMNH 88384, 55 mm; the temporal canal and triple junction are exposed laterally.

Abbreviations:

LES	Lateral Extrascapular
PTC	Posttemporal Canal
SCM	Supratemporal Commissure
TC	Temporal Canal

A Roa
modestus

B Chaetodon
ulietensis

hypothetical ancestor used to root the ingroup cladogram was coded as unknown.

The intermediate condition, in which the temporal canal is exposed laterally, occurs only in chaetodontids that have the anterior diverticula of the swimbladder connected to the supracleithra, and the dorso-ventrally reduced parietals. Thus, it might seem reasonable to interpret all three of these structures as a single modification, or a complex of correlated features. However, because each of the changes occurs in separate morphological structures, and because the developmental and functional relationships among them are unknown, these three modifications were included here as separate characters.

33) Medial extrascapular disc-like. In all taxa of the first and second outgroups, the medial extrascapular is relatively simple and tubular. In chaetodontids, the extrascapulars develop narrow laminae that run along the margins of the sensory canals. In Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys, the laminar portions of the medial extrascapular are exceptionally well developed such that the bone is more like a canal-bearing disc than an ossified tube. No other chaetodontids have medial extrascapulars with such well developed laminae.

34) Posterior margin of the posttemporal smooth and semicircular. In all of the outgroup taxa and most chaetodontids, the posttemporal is antero-posteriorly

longest slightly above its base, which articulates with the supracleithrum. From this articulation, the posterior margin of the posttemporal proceeds a small distance postero-dorsally to a posterior apex, where it becomes serrated with several short flat spines, and then continues antero-dorsally towards its articulation with the epioccipital. The lateral profile of the posttemporal is roughly triangular. In Parachaetodon and Megaprotodon, the posterior margin is smooth (lacking any serration) and broadly semicircular. The posttemporal is longest well above the supracleithral articulation.

Results

A parsimony analysis of the characters (PAUP Version 2.4, run with a variety of branch swapping options in effect) yielded 12 strictly bifurcating, maximally parsimonious trees, with a length of 85 steps and a consistency index of 0.659. The strict consensus analysis of these trees (Fig. 38) indicates that they contain conflicting relationships at only three levels (indicated as polychotomies on the consensus tree).

The basal trichotomy among Amphichaetodon and two larger groups (Fig. 38, node 1) results from a character conflict, and has two equally parsimonious resolutions. The second polychotomy in the consensus tree (node 5) involves four taxa (Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and

Table 7. Characters Used to Infer Relationships Among the Chaetodontidae. See text for full character descriptions, and Table 6 for character state distributions.

- 1) First dorsal pterygiophore (four states, ordered):
 - 0 -Simple, no buttresses or lateral processes;
 - 1 -First dorsal spine buttressed ventrally by lateral processes of the pterygiophore;
 - 2 -First dorsal pterygiophore with lateral processes anterior to erector dorsalis;
 - 3 -Fusion of lateral buttresses and anterior lateral process to surround erector dorsalis (e.d. passes through foramen).
- 2) Predorsal bones (five states, ordered):
 - 1 -Sequential articulation between supraoccipital, predorsal bones, and first dorsal pterygiophore;
 - 2 -First predorsal bone flattened and lacking posterior groove for second PDB;
 - 3 -Single predorsal bone present (two fused to one);
 - 4 -Heads of predorsal bones thickened, but first retains postero-dorsal groove.
- 3) Pleural ribs extending almost to mid-ventral.
- 4) Pleural rib laminae (three states, ordered):
 - 0 -Pleural ribs without anterior laminae;
 - 1 -Pleural ribs with weakly developed anterior laminae;
 - 2 -Pleural ribs with well developed anterior laminae.
- 5) Basipterygio-postcleithral ligament present.
- 6) Lateral line truncated.
- 7) Scales small.
- 8) Swimbladder morphology (3 states, unordered):
 - 0 -Swimbladders without anterior bilateral diverticulae;
 - 1 -Swimbladder with bulbous antero-lateral diverticulae that attach to the supracleithra;
 - 2 -Swimbladder with narrow antero-lateral diverticulae.

Table 7. (continued) Characters in the Ingroup Analysis.

- 9) Swimbladder divided into anterior and posterior chambers.
- 10) Kidney morphology (three states, ordered):
 - 0 -Posterior kidney not extending beyond first hemal spine.
 - 1 - Posterior kidney with bilateral lobes;
 - 2 - Bilateral lobes fused around first hemal spine.
- 11) Anterior branchiostegal rays free in opercular membrane.
- 12) Branchiostegal rays reduced to five.
- 13) Basihyal large, with ventral keel.
- 14) Hyoid artery excluded from dorsal hypohyal.
- 15) Dorsal hypohyal flattened and swept posteriorly.
- 16) First Epibranchial Morphology (five states, unordered; letters refer to Fig. 23):
 - 0 -B, and C;
 - 1 -D;
 - 2 -E, F, G;
 - 3 - H, I, J;
 - 4 - K through Y.
- 17) Third basibranchial and hypobranchial shapes.
- 18) Jaw and Tooth Morphology (eight states, ordered):
 - 0 -Pomacanthid morphology;
 - 1 -Basal chaetodontid morphology (not found in out-group taxa, see text);
 - 2 -5 bands of teeth in jaws, jaw teeth shorter, but still curved, produced more dorso-ventrally, etc. (Chelmonops);
 - 3 -Jaw teeth still shorter, etc. (Chelmon and Coradion);
 - 4 -(derived from 1) Jaw teeth short and straight, only two bands or less (Heniochus and Hemitaurichthys);
 - 5 -(derived from 1) Jaw teeth straight and long, rows short, reduced row overlap (Megaprotodon, Gonochaetodon, Tetrachaetodon, Discochaetodon, Corallchaetodon, Citharoedus);
 - 6 -Teeth on descending premaxillary process absent (all taxa in 18.5 except Tetrachaetodon);

Table 7. (continued) Characters in the Ingroup Analysis.

- 18) (continued)
- 7 -Teeth of nearly equivalent length, coalesced into dense brush, number of bands increased (Corallochaetodon, Citharoedus).
- 19) Vomerine teeth (three states, ordered):
- 0 -Vomer with well developed tooth patch;
1 -Vomer only partially toothed;
2 -Vomer toothless.
- 20) Ethmoid foramen for olfactory nerve not completely enclosed in lateral ethmoid.
- 21) Quality of membrane bone composing the posterior mesethmoid (three states, ordered):
- 0 -Posterior face of mesethmoid solid;
1 -Posterior face of mesethmoid sieve-like;
2 -Posterior face of mesethmoid lace-like.
- 22) Position of posterior mesethmoid (0 - extends posteriorly beyond lateral ethmoids; 1 - between lateral ethmoids).
- 23) Vertical ridges present on anterior mesethmoid.
- 24) Ethmomaxillary ligament absent.
- 25) Palato-palatine ligament:
- 0 -Palato-palatine ligament originates on medial face of palatine's maxillary process.
1 -Palato-palatine ligament moves postero-dorsally, some fibers originating from small apophysis;
2 -Apophysis well developed.
- 26) Palato-vomerine ligaments (four states, ordered):
- 1 -Two palato-vomerine ligaments well separated;
2 -Vertical palato-vomerine ligament inserts on maxillary process;
3 -Apophysis present at insertion of vertical palato-vomerine ligament.
- 27) Basal portion of the palatine very narrow dorso-ventrally.

Table 7. (continued) Characters in the Ingroup Analysis.

- 28) Ectopterygoid wide.
- 29) Second circumorbital excluded from margin of orbit.
- 30) Third circumorbital with ventrally directed lamina.
- 31) Parietal reduced dorso-ventrally.
- 32) Lateral extrascapular not enclosing temporal canal.
- 33) Medial extrascapular disc-like
- 34) Posttemporal with large semicircular posterior lamina in adults.

Fig. 38. Cladistic Relationships among the Chaetodontidae. The terminal taxa are diagnosed by osteological features. The cladogram was derived from a strict consensus analysis of 12 equally parsimonious Wagner trees. The relationships shown are common to all trees.

Hemitaurichthys), but only two of the fifteen possible resolutions are equally parsimonious. The last unresolved node, a trichotomy (node 13) occurs among two monophyletic groups and Gonochaetodon, and results from a lack of synapomorphies rather than character conflict.

The number of terminal taxa in this analysis (23) is too large for the Branch and Bound algorithm that was implemented in PAUP (version 2.4, for the PC). However, a particularly strong suite of characters infers the monophyly of all taxa above node 8 (discussed below). This allowed the data set to be partitioned into two smaller groups (which did not exceed the limits of the branch and bound algorithm) with a high degree of confidence that a shorter tree could not be found by swapping members between the two groups. Thus, two smaller data sets were constructed, one containing all taxa below (or outside) node 9 (Hyp. Ancestor to Chaetodon), and the other containing all taxa above node 8 (Chaetodon to Citharoedus). Including Chaetodon in both data sets forces the analyses to connect a common point in data-space, and makes the smaller analysis comparable to the larger one. (Chaetodon has the same character states as the hypothetical ancestor at node 8.)

Each smaller data set was submitted to the branch and bound algorithm in order to test the results of the first analysis. The branch and bound analyses produced only those tree topologies already known to be minima from the first

analysis. It is, therefore, highly probable that all maximally parsimonious trees for this data set have been found.

Discussion: Relationships among the Chaetodontidae

The CSPOSS option of PAUP was used to produce all possible reconstructions of the hypothetical ancestors for each of the 12 equally parsimonious trees. Unless explicit statements are made to the contrary, the only character state changes that are used to support cladistic relationships here are those that can be unambiguously inferred to occur on a specific branch of the consensus tree (Fig. 38). The positions of these changes do not depend on the particular character optimization routine that was in effect when the data were analyzed.

Relationships among Supraspecific Taxa

Several synapomorphies of the Chaetodontidae were discussed at the beginning of this section. (Five of these were included in the data matrix as characters 2.1, 3, 4.1, 5, and 11.) The monophyly of the family is also supported by several characters that are reversed at some point within the family.

In the earlier discussion (not based on the cladistic relationships among chaetodontids), only the presence of partially developed anterior laminae on the pleural ribs

could be interpreted as a derived feature of all chaetodontids (character 4). The reconstruction of pleural rib evolution does not vary among the most parsimonious cladograms, and indicates that fully developed laminae were present in the common ancestor of all chaetodontids. The partially developed condition, which is more similar to that in the outgroups, is shown to be a reduction shared by two taxa higher in the cladogram (Megaprotodon and Parachaetodon).

Similarly, the antero-posteriorly wide ectopterygoid (character 28) was present in the ancestral chaetodontid, and the thinner ectopterygoid is shown to be a derived feature (a reversal) of Tetrachaetodon, Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus. The seemingly most derived conditions of kidney morphology (10.2) and mesethmoid morphology (23) are also indicated as synapomorphies of the entire family.

Amphichaetodon and all of the taxa above node 2 are inferred to be monophyletic by the shared derived shape of their basihyals. However, all chaetodontids except Amphichaetodon are inferred to be monophyletic by a modification of their third hypo- and basi-branchials. The conflict between these two characters creates the basal trichotomy. Unfortunately, both characters are rather simple and there is no reason to suspect that one of them

should be more susceptible to homoplasy than the other. This relationship must therefore remain unresolved.

It is clear, however, that Amphichaetodon is osteologically more primitive than any other chaetodontid genus, as it lacks virtually all of the apomorphies that characterize the two larger clades. The two species of Amphichaetodon are not completely devoid of apomorphies (ie. the genus is not paraphyletic), but their apomorphies are relatively minor. Therefore, this genus should serve well as a model of the primitive chaetodontid morphotype. It should also be noted that the evidence presented here strongly supports the generic distinction between Amphichaetodon and Chelmonops first proposed by Burgess (1978).

The clade containing seven of Burgess's ten genera (node 2) is unambiguously supported by three characters, compression and alignment of the dorsal hypohyal (15), olfactory nerve foramen between the lateral and mesethmoid (20), and insertion of the vertical palato-vomerine ligament on the maxillary process of the palatine (22.2). The close relationship among these taxa has gone unnoticed in all previous works (Ahl, 1923; Burgess, 1978; Nalbant, 1973, 1974, and 1986), but is well supported by these characters.

The monophyly of Chelmonops, Chelmon, and Coradion (node 3, the Chelmon clade) is supported by four characters, the distal morphology of the predorsal bones (2.4),

branchiostegal rays reduced to five (12), a unique shape of the first epibranchial (16.2), and a complex modification the jaws and dentition (18.2).

The single binary character among these four, the reduction in branchiostegal ray number, is not completely consistent with the cladogram as it also occurs in Exornator and Lepidochaetodon. There is, however, substantial evidence (the characters supporting node 2, discussed above, and those supporting nodes 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, and 11, discussed below) that the Chelmon and Exornator-Lepidochaetodon clades are not closely related. The conflict between all of these characters and branchiostegal number is thus inferred to result from at least two parallel reductions of branchiostegal number. Given the likelihood of parallel reduction, it is appropriate to ask whether more than two derivations are indicated. However, the Chelmon and Exornator-Lepidochaetodon clades are both morphologically homogeneous. Thus, there are no characters to infer that more than one reduction occurred in either clade. It is then appropriate to apply Hennig's rule (Hennig, 1966; Farris, 1983; Meacham, 1984), which states that in the absence of contrary evidence, derived similarity should be interpreted as evidence of common ancestry. The two required reductions should both be interpreted as synapomorphies of their respective groups.

The other three putative synapomorphies of Chelmonops, Chelmon, and Coradion are steps within multi-state characters, two ordered, and one unordered. In the unordered character, shape of the first epibranchial (character 16.2), all three genera have the same state, and thus their most recent common ancestor is inferred to have had the same state. However, this unique shape cannot be unambiguously interpreted as derived because it is not certain that the next more primitive ancestor (node 2) did not also have the same state. It can only be concluded that the changes in the shape of the first epibranchial are consistent with this phylogenetic hypothesis.

The transformation series among the various predorsal bone morphologies was proposed on the basis of similarities among states (character 2). Because transformation series can be criticized for their inherently subjective interpretation of similarity, it should be noted that even if predorsal bone morphology had been treated as an unordered character, the morphology shared by Chelmonops, Chelmon, and Coradion would still have to be interpreted as a synapomorphy. This is because Amphichaetodon, Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys, as well as the primitive members of Chaetodon (sensu Burgess, 1978), all have the same morphology, the most primitive chaetodontid state. This distribution unambiguously infers

that derivation of the Chelmon morphology occurred in the common ancestor of the three genera.

The predorsal bone morphology of Parachaetodon differs from those in all other chaetodontids. It is somewhat similar to the morphology seen in the Chelmon clade, but it also shows a conflicting similarity to some members of Chaetodon (sensu Burgess, 1978). Because of this conflict, Parachaetodon was coded so that its predorsal bone morphology had no influence on its eventual cladistic position. The resultant cladograms indicate that the convergent attribute of predorsal bone morphology in Parachaetodon is the similarity to members of the Chelmon clade.

The final synapomorphy of Chelmonops, Chelmon, and Coradion, tooth and jaw morphology, is also part of an ordered multi-state character. But unlike the predorsal bone morphology, the interpretation of this character as a synapomorphy of all three genera does depend on the assumed transformation series. The similarities that justify this assumption (independently of other characters) were discussed above in the character description (18.2 and 18.3). It should be noted here that this interpretation of jaw morphology is corroborated by the congruence between this and most other characters.

The only character that supports the monophyly of Chelmon and Coradion (character 18.3) is also based on the

similarities between their tooth and jaw morphologies. This character is not contradicted by any other characters, but neither is it directly corroborated by them. The sister-group relationship between Chelmon and Coradion is, however, supported by a meristic character, the number of dorsal fin spines. These two genera have less than 10 spines in the dorsal fin, while virtually all other chaetodontids have 11 or more. (The only exception is Parachaetodon, which has six.) Nalbant (1986, p. 167) interpreted a low number of dorsal fin spines as being primitive (without explicit justification). Most pomacanthids have 11 or more (up to 15) dorsal fin spines. The only exceptions are the two caribbean Pomacanthus species, which have nine. Similarly, primitive members of the second outgroup have more than ten dorsal fin spines. It is also significant that within chaetodontids Amphichaetodon and Chelmonops have twelve and eleven dorsal fin spines, respectively. Therefore, outgroup comparison contradicts Nalbant's polarity assessment, and infers that less than ten dorsal fin spines is a derived condition within the Chaetodontidae. This synapomorphy directly corroborates the transformation series that was assumed for jaw morphology, and strengthens the proposed sister-group relationship between Chelmon and Coradion.

The monophyly of Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys is supported by two synapomorphies, the disc-shaped median extrascapular (character 33), and the

kidney morphology in which bilateral lobes extend posteriorly and flank the first hemal spine without fusing behind it medially (character 10.1). Kidney morphology is noteworthy because the transformation series that was inferred from the similarities among character states is contradicted by the topology of the cladogram. Instead of a 0-1-2 transformation, the cladogram infers a 0-2-1 transformation (see character 10).

The polychotomy among Forcipiger, Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys has only two equally parsimonious resolutions. In the first, Heniochus and Hemitaurichthys form the terminal sister-group, and Forcipiger is the sister group to the other three. In the second, Forcipiger and Hemitaurichthys form the terminal sister-group, and Johnrandallia is the plesiomorphic sister group of the other three. Because the sequential relationship among Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys is common to both hypotheses, the pivotal issue is clearly the position of Forcipiger.

Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys are inferred to be monophyletic, exclusive of Forcipiger, by the dorso-ventrally narrow base of the palatine, and the ventrally directed lamina on the third circumorbital. The circumorbital character shows a parallel derivation in Prognathodes, but the palatine character is uniquely derived. A single character, dentition, supports the

monophyly of Heniochus and Hemitaurichthys. As was the case with Chelmon and Coradion, the jaw morphologies of these genera are not equivalent, but do share similarities (see character 18.4) that indicate a close relationship.

Most previous workers have not advocated a close relationship between Forcipiger and Hemitaurichthys. Instead, they have implied a close relationship between Forcipiger and Chelmon (e.g. Nalbant, 1986). Burgess (1978) was the first to propose a close relationship between Forcipiger and Hemitaurichthys. As supporting evidence, he cited their higher lateral line scale counts, falcate pectoral fins, and a propensity to produce individuals or species that are completely dark and without a color pattern.

Forcipiger clearly has longer pectoral fins than any other chaetodontid, but Burgess's method for demonstrating that Hemitaurichthys and Forcipiger share a derived similarity, obscures the comparison. He expressed relative pectoral fin length as the ratio of standard length over fin length. But because the extremely long snout in Forcipiger inflates the "standard" measure of its size, its pectoral fins seem shorter than they really are. If pectoral fin length is standardized by a measure that excludes snout length, the largest gap separates Forcipiger from all other taxa. The character is more appropriately interpreted as an autapomorphy of Forcipiger. Moreover, Burgess's own data do

not support his conclusion. He reported ratios for some Heniochus species (H. chrysostomus, H. pleurotaenia, and H. varius), that are as extreme as those in Forcipiger and Hemitaurichthys.

The tendency toward melanism that Burgess cited is also hard to use as a systematic character. Most individuals of the two Forcipiger species are yellow, not black, and two of the four species of Hemitaurichthys are also not black. Although it is possible that a tendency toward melanism is a synapomorphy of the two genera, it is equally parsimonious to interpret this tendency as being derived in parallel.

Only one of Burgess's characters, the number of scales in the lateral line, prevails under closer scrutiny and remains to indicate a close relationship between Forcipiger and Hemitaurichthys. The other character that supports this alternative is the relatively more anterior position of the mesethmoid shared by Forcipiger, Hemitaurichthys, and Heniochus, but absent in Johnrandallia. The jaw and dental morphologies of Forcipiger were coded as unknown, therefore the dental character (18.4) that unites Heniochus and Hemitaurichthys does not effect the contrast between the two alternatives.

The most significant evidence against a close relationship between Forcipiger and Hemitaurichthys is the absence of the derived palatine and circumorbital morphologies in Forcipiger. It should be noted, however,

that in these characters, Forcipiger has either a unique (palatine) or intermediate (circumorbital) morphology. In general, the morphologies in Forcipiger were difficult to code, and the interpretations made here were intentionally conservative. Thus, the hypothesis in which Forcipiger is the sister group to the other three genera must also be considered conservative. Burgess's hypothesized sister-group relationship between Forcipiger and Hemitaurichthys clearly warrants further consideration. However, because Forcipiger is extremely derived morphologically, this hypothesis would be better tested by non-morphological data.

The second major clade in the family contains all the species of Burgess's Chaetodon, as well as Parachaetodon. This clade is unambiguously supported by only a single character, truncation of the lateral line (character 6), but three other characters, shape of the basihyal (character 12), loss of the ethmo-maxillary ligament (character 21), and exclusion of the second circumorbital from the margin of the orbit (character 26) differentiate these species from all other chaetodontids, even if only in a phenetic sense. Because homoplasy has occurred in these characters, the states present at the critical internal nodes (1 and 6) cannot be inferred. Thus, the location and direction of evolution in these characters cannot be determined by parsimony. There is some evidence, albeit problematical, for interpreting two of these characters, the circumorbital

modification and the loss of the ethmo-maxillary ligament, as synapomorphies of this group.

The circumorbital conditions in pomacanthids and the descendants of node 6 (Chaetodon sensu lato; = Chaetodon sensu Burgess plus Parachaetodon) may not be homologous. The surrounding bones and ontogenetic timing are rather different in the two groups. The more standard osteological environment and timing occur in pomacanthids. The pomacanthid morphology shows no ontogenetic transformation as it appears in larvae just as it does in adults. Ossification of the second circumorbital is coordinated with the other bones in the series, and all are present in larvae less than 10 mm SL. In contrast to this, development of the second circumorbital in Chaetodon (sensu lato) is perturbed by the dermal armor that characterizes their tholichthys larvae. In these species, the preopercle is expanded antero-dorsally so that it reaches the orbital margin and covers the more ventral circumorbital bones. The lacrimal is expanded postero-ventrally (medial to the preopercle where they overlap). The second circumorbital does not ossify until resorption of the dermal armor has begun, and well after the other circumorbitals have ossified. In the larvae of more plesiomorphic chaetodontids, the preopercle is not expanded antero-dorsally, nor is the lacrimal expanded postero-ventrally. In these species, ossification of the second circumorbital is undisturbed; its appearance

is coordinated with the others, and it lies along the margin of the orbit as it does in more primitive percoids. Thus, displacement of the second circumorbital appears to result from different ontogenies in pomacanthids and chaetodontids, and both can be considered derived.

Similarly, the buccal ligaments in pomacanthids differ from those in the second outgroup, and differ even more from those in chaetodontids (see character 21). Even though pomacanthids and some chaetodontids share the absence of an ethmo-maxillary ligament, the differences between their buccal ligament systems impugns the homology of this loss. In addition to the species of Chaetodon (sensu lato), the ethmo-maxillary ligament is absent in Coradion and Forcipiger. Both of these taxa have very derived jaw morphologies, and independent losses are easy to accept as consequences of these derivations. Parallel losses within the Chaetodontidae explain the evolution of this character more plausibly than do multiple origins. The multiple origin hypothesis (after a basal loss) requires the ligament to reappear a minimum of three times in taxa whose jaw morphologies are similar by plesiomorphy.

These characters (21 and 26) were coded as ambiguous so that their polarities would not unduly influence the result.

However, because the weight of evidence provided by the remaining characters does not contradict their interpretation as synapomorphies of Chaetodon (sensu lato),

it is reasonable (by the arguments presented above) to accept these characters as synapomorphies of this taxon.

A relationship between Prognathodes and taxa above node 8 (exclusive of Roa) is indicated only by modifications of the mesethmoid. This evidence is considered to be relatively weak because (1) both steps occur in the same character, and (2) the attributes of the mesethmoid, as interpreted here, are relatively labile (requiring a minimum of six steps to explain only two derived states). This relationship is accepted here only in the absence of contradictory evidence.

The monophyly of all taxa above node 8 is perhaps the most strongly supported relationship in the family. This strength comes not just from the number of supporting characters, but also the nature of one particular character, the connection of the swimbladder to the supracleithrum (character 8.1). This pseudo "otophysic connection" is unique, as far as known, and represents the most substantial modification of internal anatomy known to occur in the family. Although the function of this character has not been demonstrated, the repeated exploitation of the swimbladder (a gas-liquid phase barrier) as a hearing organ (e.g. clupeiforms, ostariophysans, myripristines, some priacanthids, teraponids, etc.) makes it reasonable to expect that the chaetodontid specialization serves the same function, the enhancement of hearing sensitivity. It is

then reasonable to expect that modifications of their nervous and acoustico-lateralis systems have also occurred.

However, the full complexity of the swimbladder-supracleithrum connection remains to be discovered.

Node 8 is also supported by four other characters, a flattening of the caput pterygiophori on the predorsal bones (character 2.2), loss of anterior ridges on the mesethmoid (character 23), dorso-ventral reduction of the parietal (character 28), and a shape change in the lateral extrascapular (character 29).

Node 9 is supported by only one character, the development of antero-lateral processes on the first dorsal pterygiophore (character 1.2), and is accepted in the absence of contradictory evidence. However, unlike the mesethmoid characters supporting node 7, the pterygiophore character is entirely consistent with the cladogram.

Node 10 is supported by two characters, exclusion of the hyoid artery from the dorsal hypohyal (character 14), and the more posterior origin of the palato-palatine ligament (character 23.1). This is a surprising relationship because although some of the subordinate groups have been recognized by previous workers (Nalbant 1973; Burgess, 1978; Maugé and Bauchot, 1983), there are no external similarities that unite these groups as a whole. The two skeletal characters occur in separate systems, and there are no characters that directly contradict them.

Further, both characters require only one or two steps to explain the distributions of the derived states. This indicates that they are relatively stable. (The only homoplastic step is the parallel loss of the foramen for the hyoid artery in Forcipiger.) Thus, there is no reason to suspect that the relationship is spurious.

Roops, Exornator, and Lepidochaetodon form a monophyletic group (node 11) supported by distal fusion of the predorsal bones (character 2.3), and enclosure of the erector dorsalis muscles within the distal portion of the first dorsal pterygiophore (character 1.3). Both characters are unique, and in the absence of conflicting characters provide strong evidence of relationship. Within this clade, Exornator and Lepidochaetodon are united by loss of the smallest, anterior-most branchiostegal ray (character 12). Meristic reductions such as this are generally not considered to be strong evidence of relationship. However, the ingroup cladogram indicates that branchiostegal ray number is relatively stable within the family, and that the only parallel reduction occurs in a distantly related group (node 3). There is no other evidence that contradicts the sister-group relationship between Exornator and Lepidochaetodon, and therefore the relationship should be accepted provisionally on the basis of this single character.

Node 13 is the third polychotomy in the consensus tree and joins three monophyletic groups. It is possible that as many as five derived characters support this relationship (18.5, 18.6, 19.1, 21.2, and 26.3), but the appearance of primitive states above this node causes reconstructions in three of the five characters to become ambiguous. Ambiguity in two of these characters, 19.1, a reduction in vomerine dentition, and 18.5, a straightening of the jaw teeth, is caused by the states in Parachaetodon; this highly autapomorphic species has either retained or reverted to the primitive conditions. Ambiguity in the third character, 18.6 (loss of teeth on the descending process of the premaxilla), is caused by the presence of primitive states in both Parachaetodon and Tetrachaetodon. The two characters that unambiguously support this node are both reversals of characters that were derived earlier in chaetodontid evolution. In taxa above node 13, the lace-like posterior face of the mesethmoid (character 21.2, derived at node 7) becomes sieve-like (more completely ossified), and the antero-ventral apophysis on the palatine (character 26.3, also derived at node 7) is lost.

The characters in this analysis do not resolve the relationships among the three taxa immediately above node 13. Although it is possible to reconstruct some characters such that state changes unite two of the three taxa, these reconstructions are all ambiguous. Therefore, any

resolution of this trichotomy by characters in this analysis would be arbitrary.

The most unexpected relationship discovered in this investigation is that between Parachaetodon ocellatus and Chaetodon (Megaprotodon) trifascialis (node 14). These species have never been considered closely related because they differ markedly in most aspects of external morphology, including overall body shape, meristics of the median fins, and color pattern. However, these are the only chaetodontid species with reduced laminae on the pleural ribs (character 4.1), narrow antero-lateral diverticula connecting the swimbladder to the supracleithra (character 8.2), a "two-chambered" swimbladder (character 9), and a broad semicircular posttemporal (character 34). Because these species are so different externally, it is appropriate to reiterate that Megaprotodon and Parachaetodon also share most of the derived characters that diagnose the more primitive nodes, including: truncation of the lateral line, exclusion of the second circumorbital from the orbit, loss of the ethmo-maxillary ligament, dorso-ventral reduction of the parietal, shape of the lateral extrascapular, exclusion of the hyoid artery from the dorsal hypohyal, and the posterior displacement of the palato-palatine ligament. The only contradictions of these lower-level, or more inclusive, synapomorphies are the seemingly primitive predorsal bone (character 2.2) and first dorsal pterygiophore (character

1.2) morphologies present in Parachaetodon. (Nalbant reported that Parachaetodon also lacks a forked supraoccipital (1986, p. 166), a derived feature present in all other chaetodontids. In contrast to his findings, the supraoccipital fork is well developed in the adult specimens of Parachaetodon examined here, even though it is weakly developed in individuals less than 35 mm SL). Despite the two seemingly primitive traits that are present in Parachaetodon and the external differences between Parachaetodon and Megaprotodon (mostly autapomorphies), a parsimonious interpretation of all characters requires that Parachaetodon and Megaprotodon be sister taxa and placed as a group at node 13. The four characters that specifically support this relationship are judged to be strong indicators of relationship because of their complexity, limited distribution, and congruence with most other characters in this analysis.

Tetrachaetodon, Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus are united at node 15 by two characters. The first of these consists of two attributes that (apparently) change in concert and were therefore interpreted as a single character. The dorsal apophysis of the palatine is enlarged, and the origin of the palato-palatine ligament becomes restricted to the tip of this apophysis (character 26.2). The second character is the narrowing of the ectopterygoid (28). The narrow form is more similar to that

found in the outgroups, but parsimony infers that the wide form was the primitive chaetodontid state and that the narrow form should be interpreted as derived among chaetodontids. Within the family, both characters that unite these four taxa are unique.

Discochaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Citharoedus are unambiguously united at node 16 by two characters, the complete loss of vomerine teeth (19.2), and the reappearance of an unperforated posterior mesethmoid (21.0). However, these characters do not provide strong evidence of relationship. The mapping of all character state changes over the twelve equally parsimonious trees shows that vomerine dentition is the most labile feature in the analysis. Nine state changes are required to explain the two derived conditions found in chaetodontids, and four of these changes occur at or above node 13. The degree of ossification in the posterior mesethmoid is also inferred to be a labile character. Six steps are required to produce the two derived states found in chaetodontids. (The step uniting these three taxa is a reversal to the most primitive condition.) It should also be noted, however, that the only uncertain element in this relationship is the position of Discochaetodon. The sister-group relationship between Corallochaetodon and Citharoedus is well supported by other characters.

Corallochaetodon and Citharoedus are united at node 17 by a profound restructuring of the premaxilla and dentary (character 18.7), a flattening of the posterior mesethmoid (character 22), and the reappearance of the ventral ligamentary apophysis on the palatine (which marks the insertion of the vertical palato-vomerine ligament, character 26.3). Of these characters, the modification of the premaxilla and dentary is the most complex, and therefore provides the strongest evidence of relationship. This single character encompasses changes in tooth morphology, tooth arrangement, and tooth number, as well as gross morphology of the upper jaw (relative lengths of the ascending, descending, and articular process, and the angles between these processes). The correspondence of detail in the jaw morphologies of these two taxa is almost complete. The only difference between them, (the slightly greater number of tooth bands at a given size in Citharoedus), is a case in which one taxon is more derived than the other. Both taxa have more bands of teeth than any other chaetodontid.

The most secure relationships above node 13 are the two between Megaprotodon and Parachaetodon (node 14), and Corallochaetodon and Citharoedus (node 17). The relationships of Tetrachaetodon and Discochaetodon are less secure for three reasons: they are supported by fewer characters, some of the supporting characters are inferred

to be labile, and these relationships are contradicted by three other characters. The conflicting characters concern vomerine dentition (19), jaw tooth morphology and number of tooth bands (18.5), and the loss of teeth on the descending process of the premaxilla (18.6). In defense of the relationships inferred by parsimony, it should be noted that the conflicting characters do not support a single alternative hypothesis; they conflict with each other as well. Therefore, despite the problematic nature of these relationships, they should be accepted until equal or greater evidence infers that they are false.

Monophyly of the Terminal Taxa

At the outset of this survey, osteological homogeneity was considered to be sufficient evidence for the recognition of operational taxonomic units (OTUs). This criterion leaves open the possibility that some OTUs might be paraphyletic. Autapomorphic features were not included in the data matrix as they provide no evidence of relationship among taxa. However, a number of autapomorphies were discovered in this anatomical survey and discussed in the character descriptions. The monophyly of some OTUs is also be inferred by homoplastic steps in characters with more general distributions. Both unique and homoplastic autapomorphies are discussed below. Taxa lacking autapomorphies are noted as potentially paraphyletic.

The genus Amphichaetodon Burgess 1978, contains two species, A. howensis and A. melbae. As noted above, the exact cladistic position of Amphichaetodon cannot be specified because of a conflict between characters 13 (basihyal shape) and 17 (third basi- and hypo-branchial shape). The conflict between these characters also causes their reconstructions to be ambiguous. Thus neither character can be cited as an autapomorphy of Amphichaetodon. However, A. howensis does show an osteological feature not seen in any other chaetodontid. The proximal radials of the soft dorsal fin have a symmetrical shape that approaches the morphology seen in Drepane and Platax. A radiograph of A. melbae reveals an identical morphology, and thus the derived state is shared by both species of the genus.

Chelmonops was thought to be monotypic until Kuitert (1986) separated C. curiosus from the type species C. truncatus. There are no qualitative osteological characters to demonstrate that the genus is monophyletic because its skeletal morphology was interpreted to be plesiomorphic relative to that in Chelmon and Coradion. Nevertheless, the monophyly of Chelmonops can be supported by the unique combination of elements that comprise its color pattern, and the profiles of its soft dorsal and anal fins.

No osteological features support the monophyly of Chelmon for reasons analogous to those above. The derived jaw morphology in Chelmon was interpreted as plesiomorphic

relative to Coradion. Moreover, the color pattern of Chelmon mulleri is similar to that in Chelmonops, while the color pattern in Chelmon rostratus and C. marginalis appears more similar to that in the species of Coradion. The monophyly of Chelmon seems probable given the similarity among the three species, but color pattern may be interpreted as indicating the genus is paraphyletic.

The close relationship among the three species of Coradion is supported by absence of the ethmo-maxillary ligament, reduced dentition, and the morphologies of the jaw and vomer. Only the first of these features is replicated in other chaetodontids.

The two species of Forcipiger are clearly demonstrated to be sister species by their unique jaw and suspensorium morphology, loss of the ethmo-maxillary ligament, and color pattern. Although the scales are smaller in Forcipiger than in most other chaetodontids, equally small scales are present in the species of Hemitaurichthys. Therefore, this feature cannot be considered an apomorphy of Forcipiger until the relationship between Forcipiger and Hemitaurichthys is settled.

All aspects of skeletal morphology in Johnrandallia are plesiomorphic with respect to Heniochus and Hemitaurichthys.

However, components of the color pattern (black snout with white lips, and the thin black line extending from the base

of the pectoral fin to the postero-dorsal border of the opercle) are obvious apomorphies of this monotypic genus.

The seven species of Heniochus can be diagnosed as a monophyletic group by the exaggerated length of their fourth dorsal spine. The species of Hemitaurichthys are shown to be monophyletic by their reduced dentition (clearly not homologous with that in Coradion). Reduced scale-size may also be an apomorphy of Hemitaurichthys (see above).

Roa may be regarded as containing three species, Chaetodon modestus, C. excelsa, and C. jayakari (Burgess, 1978), or a single species with three allopatric subspecies (Allen, 1980). The alpha-level taxonomy of Roa is a matter of contention, and resolving such questions was not the purpose of this survey. There are no osteological features that unambiguously diagnose this taxon as monophyletic. However, if the allopatric forms are indeed separate reproductive units, the similarity among them makes it very unlikely that the complex is paraphyletic.

Prognathodes contains eight species (including the recently described Chaetodon (P.) guyotensis Yamamoto and Tameka [in Okamura, et.al., 1982]). These species can be diagnosed as monophyletic by the large lateral laminae on circumorbitals II and III (which are visible even in unprepared material). An expanded lamina (on III) is also present in Johnrandallia, Heniochus, and Hemitaurichthys, but it is most pronounced in the species of Prognathodes.

(The distant relationship between the two groups unambiguously infers that their circumorbital laminae were derived independently.) The absence of vomerine teeth also supports the monophyly of Prognathodes, but only weakly because this character is inferred to be labile.

Chaetodon (sensu stricto) lacks osteological apomorphies, but Burgess (1978, p. 657) expressed the opinion that Chaetodon hoefleri, C. marleyi, C. striatus, C. capistratus, C. ocellatus, C. robustus, C. humeralis, C. melannotus, and C. ocellicaudus form a species group. I concur with this opinion, except for the inclusion of the two Indo-Pacific species, C. melannotus and C. ocellicaudus.

Their more derived first dorsal pterygiophore morphology sets them apart from the other members of the complex, and unites them instead with taxa above node 8. Removing the Indo-Pacific species gives the Chaetodon complex a peculiar Afro-American distribution, the south and west coasts of Africa plus the east and west coasts of the Americas.

Rabdophorus is the most speciose OTU in this analysis (26 species). It is composed of several species complexes that are diagnosable by color pattern (e.g. the falcula complex, vagabundus complex, lineolatus complex, and selene complex), as well as divergent species with no obvious affinities (e.g. Chaetodon mesoleucos, and C. nigropunctatus). Even though Rabdophorus is osteologically

homogeneous, no features were discovered to diagnose it as monophyletic.

Roaops can be diagnosed phenetically by a combination of two osteological characters, fused predorsal bones and six branchiostegal rays. However, both features are plesiomorphic relative to Exornator and Lepidochaetodon. Therefore, Roaops lacks characters that unambiguously diagnose it as monophyletic. Roaops does, however, contain a complex of five deep-water species, which is easily diagnosed by an underlying theme in their color patterns and a median fin profile that is not seen in closely related taxa. This complex is almost certainly monophyletic. A sixth species, Chaetodon nippon, was included in Roaops here because its osteology is qualitatively identical to that seen in the five deep-water species. However, Chaetodon nippon lacks the external features that characterize that species complex. Further study may clarify its relationships to taxa above node 11, and justify its exclusion from Roaops.

Exornator is the second most speciose terminal taxon in this analysis (22 species), and, as was the case with the most speciose taxon, Rabdophorus, osteology cannot infer that Exornator is monophyletic. All of the characters that are derived in Exornator are either present, or more derived, in Lepidochaetodon. Exornator is also similar to Rabdophorus in that it contains several species pairs and

complexes that are easily diagnosable by color pattern, as well as species that have intermediate and divergent color patterns.

Chaetodon (Lepidochaetodon) unimaculatus is distinct from all other chaetodontids in that its jaws contain two kinds of teeth (the most labial teeth are significantly larger and stouter than more lingual ones [see Motta, 1985, and 1987]). This feature and its generally more robust external appearance have led previous workers to recognize C. unimaculatus as subgenerically distinct from other members of Chaetodon. Chaetodon kleinii and C. trichrous lack the apomorphic dentition of C. unimaculatus, but all three species share the most derived first dorsal pterygiophore morphology (see character 1.3). Therefore, C. kleinii and C. trichrous were included in Lepidochaetodon. Character state optimization also indicates that loss of vomerine teeth is a derived character shared by these species. Although the significance of this character is diminished by its apparently rapid evolution, the loss of vomerine dentition is corroborated in this case by a modification of the surrounding vomer. In all other chaetodontids without vomerine teeth, a ventrally projecting V-shaped ridge usually remains to demarcate the formerly dentigerous area. In Lepidochaetodon this ridge is absent, and the vomer has a distinct, somewhat spherical, contour. The three species of Lepidochaetodon are also inferred to be

monophyletic by a unique feature of the caudal skeleton. In all other chaetodontids (as well as outgroup taxa), the hypurapophysis is present as a simple postero-laterally projecting hook. In Lepidochaetodon, the otherwise normally shaped hypurapophysis also bears a small anteriorly directed blunt process. (All other qualitative variations in chaetodontid caudal skeletons appear to be polymorphisms within species.) These three features (first dorsal pterygiophore shape, loss of vomerine teeth and shape of the vomer, and the anterior projection on the hypurapophysis) strongly indicate that Chaetodon unimaculatus, C. kleinii, and C. trichrous form a monophyletic group.

Parachaetodon and Megaprotodon are both monotypic taxa, and differ markedly from each other as well as all other chaetodontids. The most obvious features that set each of these taxa apart are the meristics of their median fins (Burgess, 1978). Parachaetodon has only six dorsal fin spines, whereas counts in the remainder of the family ranges from 9 to 16 (usually 10 to 13). Megaprotodon differs from other chaetodontids in the opposite direction, having more median fin spines than usual (13-15). Megaprotodon is also one of only three chaetodontid species that have more than three anal fin spines. Megaprotodon has four, while the other two, Chaetodon plebeius and Hemitaurichthys multispinosus, have 4 and 5, respectively. Parachaetodon and Megaprotodon are also oppositely derived with respect to

vomerine dentition. The hypothetical common ancestor of Parachaetodon and Megaprotodon (node 14), as well as the next more primitive hypothetical ancestor (node 13), are both inferred to have had partially toothed vomers. Parachaetodon has a fully toothed vomer, and Megaprotodon lacks vomerine teeth completely.

Gonochaetodon is a complex of three allopatric species that differ only in minor aspects of color pattern. The similarities among their color patterns are much more striking. In all three species, the body is traversed by alternating black (dark) and white stripes that form chevrons. The posterior portion of the body becomes progressively darker as the white stripes become thinner and fade. Chaetodon (Gonochaetodon) larvatus differs from C. baronessa and C. triangulum in having a red head, without a vertical eyebar, and a posterior dark portion that is distinctly jet black. C. triangulum differs from the other two in having white stripes along dorsal and ventral edges of the caudal fin that meet each other anteriorly on the caudal peduncle to form a boomerang-shaped wedge. Also, the chevron stripes in C. triangulum have slightly different widths such that the pattern appears more as black stripes on a white background than the reverse, which occurs in the other two species. Except for these minor differences, the color patterns of the Gonochaetodon species are identical and distinct from all other chaetodontids. The lateral

profile of these species also sets them apart from all other species of Chaetodon (sensu lato), and is approximated only in the species of Chelmon and Chelmonops. The more posterior soft dorsal and anal fin rays are longer than preceding ones, and proportionally longer than those in other species. This proportional difference gives these species a distinct triangular profile. Although the species of Gonochaetodon have no osteological synapomorphies, their distinctive color pattern and lateral profile strongly infer that they form a monophyletic group.

The species of Tetrachaetodon are osteologically distinct from all other species above node 13 (except Parachaetodon) in retaining teeth on the descending process of the premaxilla. However, optimization of this character yields ambiguous reconstructions in the ancestors immediately below Tetrachaetodon (15 and 13). Therefore, this feature may be plesiomorphic. Nevertheless, the four species of Tetrachaetodon share two basic elements of color pattern that indicate the group is monophyletic. The background color in all four species is yellow, and all exhibit a large elliptical dark blotch mid-laterally on the body. Although the color pattern is simple, it is repeated in only one other species, Chaetodon (Lepidochaetodon) unimaculatus. The species of Tetrachaetodon are inferred by osteology to be distantly related to C. unimaculatus. Therefore, the color pattern must be interpreted as

convergent in the two lineages, and a shared derived character among the species of Tetrachaetodon.

The four species of Discochaetodon are distinct from all other Chaetodon (sensu lato) species in that the lateral profile of their body (excluding the median fins) is almost disc-shaped. Relative lengths of the median fin spines further differentiate this group. Two dorsal fin profiles are common in other chaetodontids; either the last, or the fourth or fifth dorsal spine is longest. In both of these more broadly distributed profiles, the last dorsal spine is shorter than the longest anal spine. In Discochaetodon, the height of the dorsal spines increases smoothly to a maximum at the sixth (or seventh), and decreases slightly in the more posterior spines. The last dorsal spine is longer than any of the anal spines. The species of Discochaetodon have color patterns that are composed of simple vertical stripes, and are not found in any taxa above node 10. Three broad stripes are present in C. tricinctus, and eight narrow ones are present in C. rainfordi and C. octofasciatus. The fourth species, C. aureofasciatus, has only a single vertical stripe at the pectoral fin (in addition to the plesiomorphic eyebar), but it is assumed that at least this stripe is a shared derived character among the four species. There are no osteological characters that infer the monophyly of Discochaetodon. However, the combination of body profile, median fin spine proportions, and color

pattern is unique within the family, and interpreted here as sufficient evidence for the monophyly of this species complex.

The species of Corallochaetodon are united by a single osteological character and by a unique color pattern. The basal portion of the palatine is antero-posteriorly thinner and dorso-ventrally taller than in any other chaetodontid. The shape present in Corallochaetodon is interpreted as the culmination of a trend that begins at node 14. The basal section of the palatine appears to become progressively shorter in Tetrachaetodon, Discochaetodon, Citharoedus, and Corallochaetodon. However, the variation within taxa seems to obscure all of the gaps between successive taxa except the last. Although the trend is completely consistent with the cladogram, it was not incorporated into the ingroup analysis because the placement of discrete steps (which would be relevant to relationships among the OTUs) could be argued. The degree of shortening present in Corallochaetodon clearly separates these species from all others, and may be confidently interpreted as an autapomorphy of this taxon. The unique element of the color pattern present in Corallochaetodon is the set of 13 to 15 thin stripes along the body that are almost arranged as "concentric" ellipses. Stripes in the dorsal half of the body are convex dorsally, and stripes in the ventral half are convex ventrally. The straightest stripes are the fifth

to seventh, and these traverse the length of the body obliquely, rising posteriorly. The color pattern and shape of the palatine are unique among chaetodontids, and infer that Corallochaetodon is monophyletic.

The members of Citharoedus are the most derived of the corallivorous chaetodontids, and their monophyly is strongly inferred by their osteology. The suspensorium in the Citharoedus species is extremely short. Reduction is particularly evident in the mesopterygoid and ectopterygoid (Fig. 34). The second circumorbital is absent and represents a condition unique among chaetodontids. The lateral processes on the first dorsal pterygiophore (which surround the erector dorsalis muscles) become fused in a condition that resembles that in taxa above node 11 (Fig. 38; character 1.3). Because the fusion occurs much later in the ontogeny of Citharoedus species (at about 35 mm SL) than in taxa above node 11 (before 15 mm SL), the two conditions were not interpreted as homologous. However, even if this interpretation were reversed, the relatively distant relationship between Citharoedus and the others would not be changed, and the two conditions would have to be interpreted as parallel derivations.

Two of the three Citharoedus species, Chaetodon meyeri and C. ornatissimus, have color patterns that are strikingly similar, and unique among chaetodontids. The color pattern of the third species, C. reticulatus, is both radically

different from that in the other two, and very similar to the color pattern of a fourth species, C. collare. According to Ahl (1923) and all subsequent authors, C. collare is a member of Chaetodontops (which was synonymized with Rabdophorus here). Consequently, the classification of C. reticulatus has been a matter of contention among chaetodontid taxonomists. Ahl (1923) and Allen (1980) placed C. reticulatus in Chaetodontops, whereas Nalbant (1973) and Burgess (1978) placed this species in Citharoedus. The osteologies of Chaetodontops and Citharoedus are easily distinguished by the characters that diagnose nodes 10, 13, 15, 16, and 17 (Fig. 38). The osteology of C. reticulatus is identical to that seen C. meyeri, and C. ornatissimus, and therefore, C. reticulatus must be considered a member of Citharoedus. The similarity between the color patterns of C. collare and C. reticulatus must be interpreted as convergent.

Conclusions

The cladogram in Figure 38 is the most completely resolved statement of chaetodontid relationships that can be unambiguously inferred from the data set presented above. However, the lack of ambiguity is not a sufficient measure of the confidence that may be associated with a cladistic relationship. At present, confidence in cladistic relationships cannot be expressed metrically (for lack of a

unit measure of cladistic inference). Nevertheless, confidence in a particular relationship can be evaluated qualitatively by the number of supporting characters, the stability of these characters (inferred from their congruence with others characters or relationships), and, to a lesser degree, the complexity of these characters.

Two of the relationships indicated in Fig. 38 are not well supported by character evidence (nodes 7 and 16, discussed above). A more conservative hypothesis, which excludes these uncertain relationships, is presented in Fig. 39. Workers intending to draw inferences from the phylogenetic relationships among chaetodontids are encouraged to use the more conservative cladogram. It should also be noted that Chelmon, Rabdophorus, and Exornator may be paraphyletic groups.

Fig. 39. A Conservative Hypothesis of Chaetodontid Relationships. This cladogram of the Chaetodontidae contains only those relationships that are well supported by osteological evidence.

CHAPTER IV

PHYLOGENETIC CONGRUENCE BETWEEN OSTEOLOGICAL AND MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERS IN CORALIVOROUS CHAETODONTIDS

Introduction

At the outset of the investigation into chaetodontid relationships, species were sorted into groups that were osteologically indistinguishable. In the absence of osteological differences, the relationships within these terminal taxa remain unresolved. However, the species within most of these taxa are distinguishable by their shapes, meristics, and color patterns. The goal of this study was to quantitatively describe the shape differences that exist among 18 closely related species, and to infer their interrelationships by a cladistic analysis of these differences.

Although morphometric characters are routinely used in phenetics, they are largely avoided in cladistics. The disuse of morphometrics in cladistics seems to have three sources: a widely held prejudice that morphometric characters are phylogenetically unstable, persistent shortcomings in morphometric methods, and an incompatibility between continuous morphometric characters and the discrete

judgments of homology that are required for character-state-based cladistic analysis. The first objection is admissible only after a phylogenetic hypothesis has been assumed, and it should not be used as an a priori justification for the exclusion of morphometric characters from cladistics. However, the latter two objections are scientifically valid a priori reasons for not using morphometric characters in cladistic analyses. Shortcomings have been identified in many morphometric methods, and their appropriateness for phylogenetic inference may be criticized with good reason. Similarly, continuously described character states cannot be analyzed by algorithms developed for discrete states.

Two recently developed morphometric methods appear to have strong theoretical justification as techniques for describing biological forms, and thus avoid some of the problems associated with other morphometric methods. These new methods are, the truss measurement protocol of Strauss and Bookstein (1982), which provides explicit guidelines for the choice of morphometric characters, and the sheared principal components analysis of Humphries et al. (1981), which provides a multivariate method for describing shape differences among individuals and taxa. Archie (1985) has developed a method, generalized gap-coding, which attempts to objectively interpret continuous variables as discrete characters. To the extent that this technique produces a satisfactory representation of the continuous data, it may

be used to translate morphometric results into data that may be analyzed by standard, state-based (as opposed to distance-based) cladistic algorithms.

In the present study, these three methods were combined with a Wagner parsimony analysis in an attempt to infer the phylogenetic relationships among a group of closely related chaetodontids. Note, however, that these methods of shape description and character coding are relatively new and have not been explored thoroughly. More importantly, they were not developed jointly, and they have not been combined before. Therefore, this study is primarily an exploration of these methods rather than an attempt to infer relationships.

The 18 species included in this analysis are members of five closely related subgenera within the genus Chaetodon. In the previous chapter, these species were shown to be descendants of a single hypothetical ancestor (node 13, Fig. 38). The included subgenera are listed in Table 8, in ascending phylogenetic sequence (the most derived last). In all cases, the relationships of species within subgenera are unknown (the members of each subgenus are listed alphabetically).

The 18 species in this study do not, however, form a monophyletic group. A single descendent of node 13, Parachaetodon ocellatus, was inadvertently omitted from the

Table 8. Taxa Included in the Morphometric Study. Species are listed alphabetically within subgenera (in parentheses). The abbreviation used in figures is given for each taxon, and the sample size is given for each species.

Taxon	Abbreviation	Sample Size
(<u>Megaprotodon</u>)	M	
<u>trifascialis</u>	TFL	8
(<u>Gonochaetodon</u>)	G	
<u>baronessa</u>	BAR	16
<u>larvatus</u>	LAR	19
<u>triangulum</u>	TRG	4
(<u>Tetrachaetodon</u>)	T	
<u>bennetti</u>	BEN	24
<u>plebeius</u>	PLB	20
<u>speculum</u>	SPM	23
<u>zanzibariensis</u>	ZAN	13
(<u>Discochaetodon</u>)	D	
<u>rainfordi</u>	RNF	29
<u>aureofasciatus</u>	AUF	22
<u>octofasciatus</u>	OCT	31
<u>tricinctus</u>	TCT	4
(<u>Corallochaetodon</u>)	CO	
<u>melapterus</u>	MLP	25
<u>austriacus</u>	AUS	21
<u>trifasciatus</u>	TFT	21
(<u>Citharoedus</u>)	CI	
<u>meyeri</u>	MEY	4
<u>reticulatus</u>	RET	7
<u>ornatissimus</u>	ORN	6

morphometric analysis because its membership within this group was discovered only after the morphometric data had been collected. The omission of Parachaetodon biases the results of this analysis predictably, and the effect of this omission is discussed below.

Methods

Strauss and Bookstein (1982; see also Bookstein et al., 1985) recommended that morphometric data be collected according to a scheme of measurements that they termed a truss. This scheme has several advantages over conventional sets of variables. The lengths measured are always distances between homologous landmarks, and therefore contain more biological information than extremal measurements, such as the maximum body depth or the minimum depth of the caudal peduncle. Landmarks are chosen such that measurements span relatively short distances across the form. Using shorter distances allows deformations in shape to be localized more precisely. Each landmark serves as the terminus for more than one distance measure, thus the displacement of a landmark can be characterized unambiguously by a combination of distance measures. Finally, use of the truss enables the biological form to be archived more completely and efficiently, with less built-in correlation among variables.

Chaetodontids are highly compressed fishes, and thus radiographs nearly represent contact prints of an individual's lateral profile. In this study, 32 midsagittal landmarks were digitized from radiographs of 292 specimens. Landmarks were chosen to give an even coverage of the body (Fig. 40A; and Table 9). The X-Y coordinates representing the relative landmark positions in each specimen were checked visually (by plotting the data on a graphics monitor) to ensure that gross errors were not included in the data set. Euclidean distances among the landmarks were calculated according to the variable set shown in Fig. 40B, and Table 10.

The sheared principal components analysis of Humphries et al. (1981; see also Bookstein et al., 1985, and Rohlf and Bookstein, 1988) has several attributes to recommend it over alternative methods for describing shape differences among species. It employs the first eigenvector of the pooled within groups variance-covariance matrix (derived from the log transformed variables) as the measure of size. This measure is intended to estimate the latent factor (growth) that is responsible for the strong correlations typically present among measurements taken from organisms that get larger during ontogeny. Because this measure of size is derived from all variables, it estimates this factor more accurately than do any of the commonly employed univariate measures, such as standard length, snout vent length, or

Fig. 40. Midsagittal Landmarks and Distance Measures. The 32 midsagittal landmarks that were digitized from each radiograph are shown on a positive print (A). Short descriptions of the landmarks are given in Table 9. Landmarks that designate endpoints for each of the 73 distance measures are given in Table 10. These distance measures approximate a box truss (B), and comprise the set of original morphometric variables.

A.

B.

Table 9. Morphological Landmarks Digitized from Radiographs

1	Anterior Premaxilla (distal ends of teeth)
2	Anterior Frontals (suture between nasals and frontals)
3	Basioccipital (postero-ventral corner)
4	Neural Spine 1 (distal tip)
5	First Dorsal spine (proximal end)
6	Neural Spine 4 (distal tip)
7	8th Neural Spine (distal tip)
8	12th Neural Spine (distal tip)
9	Base of last Dorsal spine (distal tip)
10	16th Neural Spine (distal tip)
11	4th Vertebral Centrum (antero-dorsal corner)
12	8th Vertebral Centrum (antero-dorsal corner)
13	12th Vertebral Centrum (antero-dorsal corner)
14	16th Vertebral Centrum (antero-dorsal corner)
15	20th Vertebral Centrum (antero-dorsal corner)
16	24th Vertebral Centrum (antero-dorsal corner)
17	21st Neural Spine (distal tip)
18	Last Dorsal Ray (proximal end)
19	Dorsal Caudal Ray (intersection of posterior edge of hypural and dorsal most caudal ray)
20	Hypural Notch (between hypurals 2 and 3)
21	Ventral Caudal Fin Ray (intersection of posterior edge of hypural and ventral most caudal ray)
22	Last Ventral Ray (proximal end)
23	21st Hemal Spine (distal tip)
24	12th Hemal Spine (distal tip)
25	16th Hemal Spine (distal tip)
26	First Anal Spine (proximal end)
27	Last Anal Sine (proximal end)
28	Posterior Pelvic Bone
29	Ventral tip of Cleithrum
30	Anterior tip of Pelvic Bone
31	Posterior end of Angular
32	Posterior end of Basihyal

Table 10. Distance Variables in Truss. See Table 9 for precise description of terminal landmarks. Abbreviations: Ant, Anterior; Post, Posterior; Vent, Ventral.

Variable Number				Terminal Landmarks
1	Ant. Premax.	to	Ant. Frontal	1 2
2	Ant. Frontal	to	1st Dorsal Spine	2 5
3	Ant. Premax.	to	Post. Angular	1 31
4	Ant. Premax.	to	Post. Basihyal	1 32
5	Ant. Frontal	to	Post. Basihyal	2 32
6	Ant. Frontal	to	Post Angular	2 31
7	Post. Basihyal	to	Ant. Pelvic Bone	32 30
8	Post. Angular	to	Vent. Cleithrum	31 29
9	Post. Angular	to	Post. Basihyal	31 32
10	Post. Angular	to	Ant. Pelvic Bone	31 30
11	Ant. Pelvic Bone	to	Vent. Cleithrum	30 29
12	Basioccipital	to	Ant. Pelvic Bone	3 30
13	Vent. Cleithrum	to	Post. Pelvic Bone	29 28
14	Ant. Pelvic Bone	to	Post. Pelvic Bone	30 28
15	Basioccipital	to	Post. Pelvic bone	3 28
16	Ant. Frontal	to	Post. Basioccipital	2 3
17	1st Dorsal Spine	to	Last Dorsal Spine	5 9
18	Neural Spine 1	to	Neural Spine 4	4 6
19	Neural Spine 4	to	Neural Spine 8	6 7
20	Neural Spine 8	to	Neural Spine 12	7 8
21	Basioccipital	to	4th Vertebra	3 11
22	4th Vertebra	to	8th Vertebra	11 12
23	8th Vertebra	to	12th Vertebra	12 13
24	Post. Pelvic Bone	to	Hemal Spine 12	28 24
25	Post. Pelvic Bone	to	1st Anal Spine	28 26
26	Last Dorsal Spine	to	Last Dorsal Ray	9 18
27	Neural Spine 12	to	Neural Spine 16	8 10
28	Neural Spine 16	to	Neural Spine 21	10 17
29	12th Vertebra	to	16th Vertebra	13 14
30	16th Vertebra	to	20th Vertebra	14 15
31	20th Vertebra	to	24 Vertebra	15 16
32	4th Vertebra	to	Neural Spine 8	11 7
33	8th Vertebra	to	Neural Spine 12	12 8
34	12th Vertebra	to	Neural Spine 16	13 10
35	Hemal Spine 12	to	Hemal Spine 16	24 25
36	Hemal Spine 16	to	Hemal Spine 21	25 23
37	First Anal Spine	to	Last Anal Spine	26 27
38	Last Anal Spine	to	Last Vent. Ray	27 22
39	Post. Pelvic Bone	to	12th Vertebra	28 13
40	Basioccipital	to	First Anal Spine	3 26
41	Basioccipital	to	Neural Spine 1	3 4
42	4th Vertebra	to	Neural Spine 4	11 6
43	8th Vertebra	to	Neural Spine 8	12 7

Table 10. (continued) Distance Variables in Truss.

Variable Number				Terminal Landmarks
44	12th Vertebra	to	Neural Spine 12	13 8
45	16th Vertebra	to	Neural Spine 16	14 10
46	20th Vertebra	to	Neural Spine 21	15 17
47	12th Vertebra	to	Hemal Spine 12	13 24
48	16th Vertebra	to	Hemal Spine 16	14 25
49	20th Vertebra	to	Hemal Spine 21	15 23
50	12th Vertebra	to	Hemal Spine 16	13 25
51	Neural Spine 1	to	4th Vertebra	4 11
52	Neural Spine 4	to	8th Vertebra	6 12
53	Neural Spine 8	to	12th Vertebra	7 13
54	Neural Spine 12	to	16th Vertebra	8 14
55	Neural Spine 16	to	20th Vertebra	10 15
56	24th Vertebra	to	Neural spine 21	16 17
57	Hemal Spine 12	to	16th Vertebra	24 14
58	Hemal Spine 16	to	20th Vertebra	25 15
59	24th Vertebra	to	Hemal Spine 21	16 23
60	Neural Spine 1	to	First Dorsal Spine	4 5
61	Hemal Spine 12	to	First Anal Spine	24 26
62	Hemal Spine 12	to	Last Anal Spine	24 27
63	Hemal Spine 21	to	Last Vent. Ray	23 22
64	Neural Spine 12	to	Last Dorsal Ray	8 9
65	Neural Spine 21	to	Last Dorsal Ray	17 18
66	Last Dorsal Ray	to	Dorsal Caudal Ray	18 19
67	Neural Spine 21	to	Dorsal Caudal Ray	17 19
68	24th vertebra	to	Dorsal Caudal Ray	16 19
69	24th Vertebra	to	Hypural Notch	16 20
70	24th Vertebra	to	Ventral Caudal Ray	16 21
71	Hemal Spine 21	to	Ventral Caudal Ray	23 21
72	Last Ventral Ray	to	Ventral Caudal Ray	22 21
73	Ventral Caudal Ray	to	Dorsal Caudal Ray	21 19

even body weight (which can fluctuate with an individual's condition or reproductive state).

The use of an allometric size variable (PC I) has been criticized because it incorporates the shape change that occurs during ontogeny (e.g. Sommers, 1986; Rohlf and Bookstein, 1988). If a description of growth within a single species is the sole objective of a study, or if the allometric relationships are non-linear, an isometric size variable may be useful or necessary. In this study, however, the goal was to describe the shape differences among closely related species. An allometric size variable was judged to be the most appropriate measure of size precisely because it incorporates ontogenetic shape change into the size variable and thus precludes such shape differences from influencing the comparisons among species.

By using a size variable that incorporates all variation due to growth, the among-species shape variables are more robust to the confounding differences in average size that can occur among samples collected haphazardly from different species. It is acknowledged here that the use of an allometric size variable in this study assumes that the allometric trajectories are equivalent among species. This assumption was tested by calculating the angles between the within-group size variables (within-group first eigenvectors) for species with sample sizes greater than 16 individuals.

Humphries et al. (1981) noted that, in a standard principal components analysis, the components subsequent to the first (usually interpreted as shape variables) may be significantly correlated with (allometric) size if there are appreciable mean size differences among the species samples.

They developed a shearing procedure to remove any size correlation in these shape variables. The sheared principal components describe the directions of maximum variation among individuals that are orthogonal to size, as well as each other.

To the extent that the variance among individuals is anisotropic (greater in some directions than in others), the shape variables are more stable than those produced from a discriminant function analysis. (Discriminant variables may be unstable if suites of variables are highly correlated, and the determinant of the pooled within-groups variance-covariance matrix is close to zero [Humphries et al., 1981; Bookstein et al., 1985].)

It is also significant that sheared principal components analysis allows more than two individuals to be compared simultaneously. Therefore, the mean "shape" of a species can be estimated from a sample of individuals, more than two species can be compared in a single analysis, and the differences among species can be measured relative to the variation within species.

In this study, the original distances comprising the truss were log transformed and analyzed by the sheared principal components method (the specific algorithm was that written by Marcus and Swofford, and listed in Bookstein et al., 1985, pp. 243-245). Principal components two through five were sheared to produce four, size-free, shape variables (henceforth referred to as shape variables one through four).

Most of the sample sizes achieved here (Table 8) were comparable to those in other studies that have used the truss and shear methods (e.g. Humphries, 1984; Strauss and Bookstein, 1982; Bookstein et al., 1985). Some species, however, were rare in the two source collections (USNM and BPBM), and the sample sizes were consequently low.

Discrete shape characters were generated from the species means and standard deviations (on each of the four shape variables) using the generalized gap-coding method of Archie (1985; coding performed by MAPCODE, a Pascal program provided by J.W. Archie). In generalized gap-coding, the taxa are sorted according to their means on the continuous variable. The differences among taxa are then compared to an effective gap size, equal to the pooled within groups standard deviation multiplied by an arbitrarily chosen gap constant. This comparison produces a pattern of homogeneous subsets analogous to those produced by a posteriori multiple comparisons tests. Archie discussed three methods for

converting the pattern of homogeneous subsets into a discrete character (but did not name them). In the first, here termed the one-step method, the lowest ranking taxon is assigned state zero, and the discrete character is incremented by one unit for any change in subset membership that occurs between successively higher ranking taxon. Archie noted that when this method is used, the same discrete character can be produced by different subset patterns. Because this indicates that information has been lost, he considered the one-step method to be unsatisfactory. He then discussed two alternative methods that code subset patterns less ambiguously.

In the first of these methods, non-additive binary coding, each of the homogeneous subsets is represented by a single binary character. Members of the subset are given a "1", and non-members a "0". Archie cautioned against the use of non-additive binary coding, however, because the order among character states is not preserved in the set of binary characters. (Character state order is an integral part of the original character information because the pattern of homogeneous subsets is derived in part from that order.)

Archie proposed a third method, termed here the "two-step" method, that preserves both the subset information and character state order. This method differs from the one-step method only in that the discrete character is

incremented by one step for each and every change in subset membership. As either one or two changes can occur in subset membership between successive taxa, increments in the discrete character may be of one or two steps. In the one-step method, the discrete character is incremented by only one step even if two changes occur in subset membership.

Archie's implementation of the two-step method in MAPCODE (the "Ratio" option) increments the discrete character by 0.5 for each change in subset membership. Thus, some taxa are given non-integer codes. As only integers may be used to represent character states in a PAUP data set, an increment of one (1) was used here, so that only integer character states were produced. This doubles the length of each character (all character lengths are even numbers), but the relative lengths among characters remain unchanged.

The fundamental distinction between simple and generalized gap-coding is that the latter can detect significant divergence between taxa that are not adjacent. Simple gap-coding can only detect divergence between adjacent taxa. Large groups of taxa may receive the same code even when the extreme members are separated by many times the effective gap size (see Archie, 1985, fig. 2). However, the increased sensitivity of generalized gap-coding does not come without a cost. It was noted here that codes derived from homogeneous subsets can invert the relative

distances among taxa on the continuous and discrete characters. Figures 41 and 42 illustrate this counter intuitive result. Distance inversion is a possible outcome of both the one or two-step coding methods, but the two methods require different circumstances to produce the result.

At present, there is no coding method that (1) expresses divergence among taxa relative to variation within taxa, (2) expresses divergence discretely, (3) recognizes divergence in the presence of intermediate taxa, (4) produces a unique code for every pattern of divergence, and (5) will not invert the relative distances between taxa on the continuous and discrete variables. It may in fact be impossible to develop a relatively simple coding method that satisfies all of these criteria. In the absence of a perfect method, the two-step method of generalized gap coding was judged to be the least imperfect, and was therefore used here.

In most previous applications of gap-coding, the investigator(s) elected to use a gap constant of 1.00 (e.g. Mickevich and Johnson, 1976 [but see Riska, 1979]; Miyazaki and Mickevich, 1982; Thorpe, 1984; and Archie, 1985). However, as explicitly illustrated by Archie (1985, fig. 1 and table 1), two normally distributed populations with equal variance that have means separated by 1.00 standard deviation, will show approximately thirty percent overlap.

Fig. 41. Distance Inversion in Two-step Generalized Gap-coding. The conditions are described (distances between taxon means and the effective gap size) that cause the relative distances between some taxa to be inverted on the continuous and discrete characters. The continuous distance between T_2 and T_3 is less than that between either T_1 and T_2 , or T_3 and T_4 . On the discrete character, the number of steps between T_2 and T_3 is greater than that between either T_1 and T_2 , or T_3 and T_4 .

Abbreviations:

d_n	Distance Between Adjacent Taxa
G	Effective Gap Size
S_n	Discrete Steps Between Adjacent Taxa
T_n	Hypothetical Taxon

DISTANCE INVERSION IN TWO-STEP GENERALIZED GAP CODING

Distribution of taxa on
the continuous character:

IF d_1 and $d_3 > d_2$
 AND d_1 and $d_3 < G < (d_1+d_2)$ and (d_3+d_2)

 THEN S_1 and $S_3 < S_2$
 WHILE d_1 and $d_3 > d_2$

Fig. 42. Distance Inversion in One-step Generalized Gap-coding. The conditions are described (distances between taxon means and the effective gap size) that cause the relative distances between some taxa to be inverted on the continuous and discrete characters.

Abbreviations:

d_n	Distance Between Adjacent Taxa
G	Effective Gap Size
S_n	Discrete Steps Between Adjacent Taxa
T_n	Hypothetical Taxon

DISTANCE INVERSION IN ONE-STEP GENERALIZED GAP CODING

Distribution of taxa on
the continuous character:

Effective Gap size:

Subsets:

Codes: 0 0 1 2

Discrete distances
among taxa:

T_1, T_2 T_3 T_4

($S_1=0$) \rightarrow \leftarrow

IF $d_2 < d_1 < d_3$

AND $(d_1+d_2) < G < (d_2+d_3)$

THEN $S_1 < S_2$

WHILE $d_1 > d_2$

This amount of overlap probably exceeds the limits that are implied and accepted by morphologists making qualitative distinctions among taxa. For example, if species A and B were polymorphic for character states X and Y, and A showed 30 percent X, while B showed 30 percent Y, many workers would hesitate to code these species as having different character states. Therefore, a critical gap size of 2.00 standard deviation units (SDUs) was judged to be a better approximation of phylogenetically significant differentiation. It must be admitted, however, that within reasonable limits, the choice of gap size is arbitrary. The sensitivity of the results to this arbitrary choice was explored by examining the effect of gap size on character length, and then by completing two analyses that differed in the use of oppositely extreme (but still reasonable) gap sizes, 1.0 and 3.0 SDUs.

Most obviously, a change in gap size changes the power of the discrete character to discriminate among taxa. Less obviously, it can also change the balance, or weight, among the original characters. In any given case, the total number of steps in the discrete character is determined by the distribution of individuals on the continuous character as well as the gap size. Ultimately, character length will fall to zero if the gap constant is increased sufficiently.

But if taxa are widely separated on the continuous character, character length declines more slowly (relative

to the increasing gap constant) than when taxa are overlapping. A given increase in the gap constant can therefore produce disproportionate reductions in lengths among the different characters. Because the length of a discrete character determines its weight in a parsimony analysis, a disproportionate change in character lengths is equivalent to changing the weights among characters. The only way to separate the effect of altered resolution from that of shifted character weights is to maintain an a priori balance among character weights as the gap constant is varied. Therefore, two sets of analyses were conducted, one in which the relative character weights were held constant (in proportion to the standardized ranges of the corresponding continuous variables), and another in which no weights were applied.

All sets of discretely coded shape variables (produced by different gap sizes and weighting schemes) were submitted to equivalent parsimony analyses (PAUP version 2.41, for PCs, by David Swofford). The discrete characters were assumed to be ordered. The monotypic subgenus Megaprotodon was used to root the morphometric analyses.

This root differs from that indicated by osteological data (Fig. 43). The effect of this difference is to make the autapomorphic features of Megaprotodon and any synapomorphies of the remaining taxa indistinguishable. In essence, the monophyly of the remaining taxa is an artifact

Fig. 43. Alternative Placements of the Root in the Parsimony Analyses. The relationships among the six subgenera as inferred from osteology are shown in A. The basal trichotomy has three possible resolutions, B, C, and D. Rooting by a polytypic taxon (Gonochaetodon, C) or by a combination of subgenera (Megaprotodon plus Gonochetodon, D) precludes certain relationships from being tested by the analysis (solid black bars). They will be present all trees rooted in that way and are thus an artifact of root placement. Because rooting by the monotypic subgenus, Megaprotodon, generates only one artifactual relationship, the monophyly of all other species, Megaprotodon was used to root the morphometric analyses.

of the root choice. However, using Megaprotodon as the rooting taxon adds only one artificial relationship to results, whereas the other two possible alternatives add two (see Fig. 43).

The cladistic structures common to equally parsimonious trees, as well as trees produced by different coding and weighting schemes, were determined by strict consensus analysis (CONTREE version 3/86, by David Swofford).

The efficacy of these morphometric methods in phylogenetic inference was evaluated by comparing the results against three criteria: internal consistency (as measured by the consistency index), robustness of the results to variation in the gap constant (as measured by consensus among Wagner trees), and finally, congruence to the cladogram that resulted from qualitative osteological (more traditional) characters.

Results

The Principal Components Analysis

The standard lengths of individuals ranged from 34.7 to 163.7 mm. Because of this nearly five fold size range, the first principal component (of the total variance-covariance matrix) accounted for 90.6 percent of the variance among individuals (Table 11). The next four components (uncorrected shape variables) contained 56 percent of the variation among individuals that remained after "size" was

Table 11. Eigenvalues of First Five Principal Components

Principal Component	Eigenvalue	Percentage of Total Variance
I	1.08708	90.6578
II	0.0286606	2.39018
III	0.0170055	1.4182
IV	0.0102634	0.855924
V	0.00649353	0.541535

removed. (The eigenvalues and percentages of total variance from the original principal components analysis do not correspond exactly to those associated with the size and shape variables produced by the sheared principal components analysis, but may, however, serve as a rough approximations.)

The angles between within-group first eigenvectors (allometric, or growth trajectories) were compared in a pair-wise fashion, and are reported in Table 12. The average deviation from parallel is 7.07 degrees. The smallest angle between any pair of species, 3.73 degrees, occurs between two members of the subgenus Tetrachaetodon, Chaetodon (T.) speculum and C. (T.) plebeius. The largest deviation from parallel, 12.19 degrees, occurs between C. (Tetrachaetodon) bennetti and C. (Corallochaetodon) austriacus. Of these two species, the latter is inferred to be the more divergent because a larger than average angle of deviation results whenever this species is compared to any other. In general, the angles between species indicate that the growth trajectories are similar, and thus the corresponding assumption of the shear (Bookstein, et al., 1985, p. 105) is not violated.

Histograms were used to visualize the distribution of variable loadings on each of the shape components (Figs. 44, 46, 48, and 50). However, the ultimate discrimination between weak and strong loadings was made by ranking the

Table 12. Angles Between Species First Eigenvectors. See Table 8 for species abbreviations.

	LAR	BAR	BEN	PLB	SPM	AUF	RNF	OCT	TFT	AUS	MLP	CITH
LAR	0.00	5.39	7.57	5.71	5.92	5.78	6.92	6.01	6.50	7.74	6.08	6.42
BAR	5.39	0.00	6.24	5.68	6.09	6.07	5.52	5.70	6.75	9.02	5.63	5.24
BEN	7.57	6.24	0.00	5.69	5.48	7.06	6.52	6.51	7.72	12.19	8.79	6.96
PLB	5.71	5.68	5.69	0.00	3.73	6.38	7.02	7.08	5.07	9.31	6.15	6.68
SPM	5.92	6.09	5.48	3.73	0.00	6.37	5.75	6.78	5.68	10.88	7.02	6.87
AUF	5.78	6.07	7.06	6.38	6.37	0.00	6.67	6.56	8.05	9.57	8.13	7.61
RNF	6.92	5.52	6.52	7.02	5.75	6.67	0.00	6.86	7.21	11.09	7.44	6.16
OCT	6.01	5.70	6.51	7.08	6.78	6.56	6.86	0.00	7.66	10.13	8.18	7.69
TFT	6.50	6.75	7.72	5.07	5.68	8.05	7.21	7.66	0.00	9.76	5.97	7.88
AUS	7.74	9.02	12.19	9.31	10.88	9.57	11.09	10.13	9.76	0.00	8.41	9.21
MLP	6.08	5.63	8.79	6.15	7.02	8.13	7.44	8.18	5.97	8.41	0.00	7.13
CITH	6.42	5.24	6.96	6.68	6.87	7.61	6.16	7.69	7.88	9.21	7.13	0.00

Minimum Angle = 3.7281 (between PLB and SPM)

Maximum Angle = 12.1899 (between BEN and AUS)

Average Angle = 7.0761

variables according to their loadings and then identifying gaps between the actual loadings in the shoulders of these distributions. The variables that were selected to characterize each component are listed in Tables 13-16. Figures 45, 47, 49, and 51, show the variables with strong loadings as they occur on the box truss.

The variable loadings on the first shape variable (sheared PC II) extend equally in positive and negative directions, with minimum and maximum values of -0.263 and 0.270, respectively (Fig. 44, Table 13). Therefore, the second component identifies two sets of inversely correlated variables. The variable with the most extreme negative loading is X17, the distance between the first and last dorsal spines (the length of the spinous dorsal fin; Fig. 45). Other variables with strong negative loadings are generally oriented horizontally. The variable with the strongest positive loading is X26, the distance between the last dorsal spine and the last dorsal ray (the length of the soft dorsal fin). Other variables with strong positive loadings are generally oriented vertically. The first shape component thus confirms the impression gained from gross inspection; the largest aspect of shape difference among these species is a contrast between body length and depth. Some species are long and shallow (eg. Megaprotodon and the members of Tetrachaetodon), whereas other species are short and deep (eg. the members of Gonochaetodon and

Fig. 44. Histograms of Loadings on Shape Variable I
(Sheared Principal Component II).

Frequency Distribution of Original Variable

Loadings on Sheared PC II

Table 13. Loadings of the Original Variables on Shape Variable 1 (Sheared Principal Component II)

Original Variable	Loading	
17	-0.263	
20	-0.207	
25	-0.194	
72	-0.172	
66	-0.164	
71	-0.155	Strong
67	-0.152	
23	-0.138	Negative
29	-0.136	
22	-0.134	Loadings
24	-0.132	
18	-0.127	
5	-0.124	
30	-0.119	
10	-0.118	
21	-0.114	

65	-0.098	
31	-0.090	
.	.	
.	.	
.	.	
42	0.090	
15	0.091	

38	0.128	
43	0.131	
45	0.132	
55	0.142	
58	0.159	Strong
47	0.164	
48	0.167	Positive
54	0.169	
57	0.171	Loadings
44	0.174	
61	0.201	
60	0.216	
62	0.236	
26	0.270	

Fig. 45. Truss Variables that Load Strongly on Shape Variable I (Sheared Principal Component II). Truss variables with loadings near zero are shown in gray. Variables that have strong positive loadings are represented by solid black lines. Variables with strong negative loadings are represented by dashed black lines.

Discochaetodon). The first shape component also indicates that the lengths of the spinous and soft dorsal fins are inversely correlated (not an unexpected result as the dorsal fin covers almost the entire dorsal margin of the fish), and that long, shallow-bodied chaetodontids have more spines than do short, deep-bodied ones. It seems likely that the statistical correlations among these features are caused by a single morphogenetic process.

The distribution of loadings on the second shape variable (sheared PC III) has a strong negative tail (Fig. 46, Table 14). The two largest negative loadings have more than twice the magnitude of the largest positive loading. The five largest negative loadings (X63 to X4) all concern distances from the bases of the soft dorsal and anal fin rays to the tips of the neural and hemal spines, respectively (Fig. 47). These are roughly the lengths of the corresponding pterygiophores, which were not measured directly. The variables with the sixth and seventh largest negative loadings share a terminal landmark, the tip of the premaxilla, and the angle between them is relatively small (ca. 30 degrees). These latter two variables appear to represent variation in a single morphological structure, snout length. The variable with the largest positive loading is X42, the length of the fourth neural spine. The lengths of neural spines 1 and 8 also load positively, but their magnitudes are relatively small. The second and third

Fig. 46. Histograms of Loadings on Shape Variable II
(Sheared Principal Component III).

Frequency Distribution of Original Variable

Loadings on Sheared PC III

Table 14. Loadings of the Original Variables on Shape Variable 2 (Sheared Principal Component III)

Original Variable	Loading	
63	-0.511	
65	-0.392	Strong
62	-0.239	
61	-0.184	Negative
64	-0.174	
4	-0.168	Loadings
3	-0.147	

5	-0.122	
13	-0.118	
1	-0.085	
66	-0.082	
6	-0.077	
.	.	
.	.	
.	.	
71	0.111	
35	0.118	
43	0.122	
21	0.132	
68	0.139	

38	0.152	
31	0.174	Strong
46	0.184	Positive
42	0.193	Loadings

Fig. 47. Truss Variables that Load Strongly on Shape Variable II (Sheared Principal Component III). Variables with loadings near zero are shown in gray. Variables that have strong positive loadings are represented by solid black lines. Variables with strong negative loadings are represented by dashed black lines.

largest positive loadings are associated with variables X46 and X31, which also have a common terminal landmark (the 20th vertebral centrum) and a small intervening angle. Both of these variables traverse the last four vertebrae, but the larger magnitude is associated with the variable that is inclined from the horizontal. Other variables that traverse the caudal region in a horizontal direction (but not all of them) have weak to moderately positive loadings (X67=0.107; X68=0.139; X69=0.083). If the second shape component is interpreted as identifying a single factor, it must be variation in the lengths of the posterior pterygiophores. If it is interpreted as identifying several factors, the second shape component contrasts the correlated lengths of the pterygiophores and snout, against the oppositely correlated lengths of the caudal peduncle and fourth neural spine.

The third shape component (sheared PC IV) is similar to the second in two respects. The same two variables (X65 and X63) have loadings with the largest absolute magnitudes, and generally, variables in the head and tail have large and opposite loadings (Fig. 48, Table 15). The third and second shape components differ, however, in the suites of variables that load strongly with X65 and X63. For example, on shape component two, the eight variables that rank behind X63 and X65 as strongly negative (X62, X61, X64, X4, X3, X5, X13,

Fig. 48. Histograms of Loadings on Shape Variable III
(Sheared Principal Component IV);

Frequency Distribution of Original Variable

Loadings on Sheared PC IV

Table 15. Loadings of the Original Variables on Shape Variable 3 (Sheared Principal Component IV)

Original Variable	Loading	
65	-0.542	Strong
63	-0.407	
9	-0.166	Negative
67	-0.162	
68	-0.126	Loadings
71	-0.122	

51	-0.111	
42	-0.099	
70	-0.096	
.	.	
.	.	
.	.	
62	0.110	
13	0.111	
17	0.124	

61	0.135	
1	0.144	Strong
3	0.162	
64	0.172	Positive
5	0.194	
4	0.280	Loadings

Fig. 49. Truss Variables that Load Strongly on Shape Variable III (Sheared Principal Component IV). Truss variables with loadings near zero are shown in gray. Variables that have strong positive loadings are represented by solid black lines. Variables with strong negative loadings are represented by dashed black lines.

and X1) are all among the nine most positively loading variables on shape component three.

Snout and tail measurements again load strongly on shape component four (Fig. 50, Table 16), but in this case they are positively correlated (all of these variables have negative loadings). The snout and tail variables are contrasted against several trunk variables with horizontal directions (Fig 51). However, the variable with the largest positive loading, X9 (the distance between the posterior end of the basihyal and the posterior end of the lower jaw), has a dorso-ventral orientation. Variables X63 and X65, which had the largest negative loadings on the previous two shape components, have strong but opposite loadings on the fourth component (X65 has positive loading, and X63 a negative loading).

It is difficult to interpret shape components two through four because same variables emerge repeatedly with large non-zero loadings. This suggests that these shape components might in fact be correlated. Rohlf and Bookstein (1988) have commented that although subsequent components in a simple principal components analysis are orthogonal, the shearing procedure produces subsequent components, or shape vectors, that are not strictly orthogonal. However, the angles between these sheared components were checked, and they are all very nearly orthogonal (all cosines equal zero to the first four decimal places). Thus, correlation among

Fig. 50. Histograms of Loadings on Shape Variable IV
(Sheared Principal Component V).

Frequency Distribution of Original Variable

Loadings on Sheared PC V

Table 16. Loadings of the Original Variables on Shape Variable 4 (Sheared Principal Component V)

Original Variable	Loading	
8	-0.266	
65	-0.265	
4	-0.226	Strong
67	-0.220	
56	-0.209	Negative
5	-0.194	
1	-0.159	Loadings
71	-0.152	
10	-0.151	

31	-0.128	
64	-0.123	
59	-0.115	
68	-0.105	
.	.	
.	.	
.	.	
32	0.094	
17	0.115	
14	0.119	
22	0.125	
60	0.138	

13	0.161	
19	0.182	Strong
24	0.184	
25	0.233	Positive
63	0.267	
9	0.384	Loadings

Fig. 51. Truss Variables that Load Strongly on Shape Variable IV (Sheared Principal Component V). Truss variables with loadings near zero are shown in gray. Variables that have strong positive loadings are represented by solid black lines. Variables with strong negative loadings are represented by dashed black lines.

the shape vectors does not explain the repeated strong loading of certain variables.

An alternative explanation of the repeated strong loadings is that the random measurement error associated with these variables might be large in comparison to other variables. If all or most of the real shape variation among individuals has been explained by the first shape component, a large and random (nearly spherical) error variance would determine the directions of the next few components. However, it seems unlikely that measurement error would covary with species membership. As will be shown below, significant species separation occurs on all of the shape variables. More importantly, species rank is highly correlated with subgeneric membership on the fourth shape component. This implies that even the last shape variable contains significant taxonomic information. It then follows that measurement error is probably not the source of variation in the fourth component, and that it similarly plays a small role in the components with larger eigenvalues.

The Coding of Shape Variables

The coding of sheared principal component scores is illustrated in Fig. 52. The rank orders among species on each of the shape components, the homogeneous subsets formed by applying each of the three gap constants (1.0, 2.0, and

3.0), and the discrete character codes, are shown for each continuous shape variable.

On the first shape variable, the members of three subgenera, Tetrachaetodon, Corallochaetodon, and Gonochaetodon, rank sequentially (without the interposition of a species from another subgenus). The members of a fourth subgenus, Citharoedus, would also rank sequentially if Chaetodon (Discochaetodon) octofasciatus were not interposed between Chaetodon (Citharoedus) ornatissimus and the other two members of Citharoedus. Unlike the other four polytypic subgenera, the members of Discochaetodon are heterogeneous; Chaetodon (D.) tricinctus is separated from the more deep-bodied species (aureofasciatus and rainfordi) by more than one standard deviation, and Chaetodon (D.) octofasciatus is separated from tricinctus by more than two standard deviations. The similarity among species within most subgenera is noteworthy in light of the large differentiation that has occurred within this group of chaetodontids (the range between species means on the first shape variable is nearly 13 times larger than the pooled within groups standard deviation).

On shape components two and three, the standardized ranges among species means are substantially smaller, 5.58 and 3.56, respectively. The correlations between species rank and subgeneric membership are also reduced. Only Gonochaetodon and Corallochaetodon rank sequentially on the

Fig. 52. Discrete Coding of Continuous Shape Variable I. The rank order among species, the homogeneous subsets formed by each gap size, and the resulting discrete character codes are shown for each of the continuous shape variables. Species abbreviations: AUF, Chaetodon aureofasciatus; AUS, C. austriacus; BAR, C. baronessa; BEN, C. bennetti; LAR, C. larvatus; MEY, C. meyeri; MLP, C. melapterus; OCT, C. octofasciaus; ORN, C. ornatissimus; PLB, C. plebeius; RET, C. reticulatus; RNF, C. rainfordi; SPM, C. speculum; TCT, C. tricinctus; TFL, C. trifascialis; TFT, C. trifasciatus; TRG, C. triangulum; ZAN, C. zanzibariensis. In the first listing of rank order for each variable, the subgenus of each species is indicated by the following abbreviations: C, Corallochaetodon; CI, Citharoedus; D, Discochaetodon; G, Gonochaetodon; M, Megaprotodon; T, Tetrachaetodon.

SHAPE VARIABLE I

Pooled w/in Group Std Dev: 0.0457

Range of Means: 0.089 - 0.678

Gap Constant = 1.00

Gap Constant = 2.00

Gap Constant = 3.00

Fig. 53. Discrete Coding of Continuous Shape Variable II.
Explanation and abbreviations as in Fig. 52.

Fig. 54. Discrete Coding of Continuous Shape Variable III.
Explanation and abbreviations as in Fig. 52.

SHAPE VARIABLE III

Pooled w/in Group Std Dev: 0.0761 Range of Means: 1.148 - 1.419

Gap Constant = 1.00

Gap Constant = 2.00

Gap Constant = 3.00

Fig. 55. Discrete Coding of Continuous Shape Variable IV.
Explanation and abbreviations as in Fig. 52.

second component (Fig. 53), and none of the species within subgenera rank sequentially on the third (Fig. 54).

Although the eigenvalue associated with the fourth shape variable (fifth principal component before shearing) is smaller than the third's, the standardized range among species means is slightly larger on the fourth (3.82) than on the third (3.56). The correlation between species rank and subgeneric membership is much higher on the fourth component than it is on the third, and approximates that seen on the first (Fig. 55). The members of three subgenera, Citharoedus, Gonochaetodon, and Corallochaetodon, all rank sequentially. Only the ranks within Tetrachaetodon and Discochaetodon are disparate.

It was asserted above that the choice of gap size might influence the discrete character codes (and consequently the outcome of cladistic analysis) in ways that are not predicted from first principles (i.e. that bigger gap size simply produces a less resolved cladogram). The influence of gap size on cladistic analysis was examined in two ways.

The lengths of single discrete characters, and the balance among character lengths, were both examined as functions of gap size.

The effect of gap size on the length of the discrete character was examined by expanding the range of gap sizes used, and by incrementing gap size in finer steps. Several properties of this function should be noted before these

results are discussed. Character length is a discrete variable, and thus changes in a stair-step fashion rather than smoothly. The maximum character length ($2T-2$, in the two step method, where T is the number of taxa) is produced when all taxa are separated by at least the effective gap size. The minimum character length, zero, occurs when the effective gap size includes all taxa.

Table 17 shows the character lengths that result when the first shape variable was coded using the generalized gap method, two step coding, and the gap constant is varied between 0.5 and 12.0. The gap constant was not incremented evenly, but instead, an effort was made to locate the edges in the function, especially below a gap size of 2.5. Although character length generally decreases as gap size increases, the function includes local minima and maxima (also see Fig. 56). For example, the character length is 20 steps when the gap size is 1.00, decreases to local minimum of 16 steps between gap sizes of 1.65 and 1.95, and then increases again to a local maximum of 20 steps between gap sizes 2.10 and 2.15. The exact shape of this function depends, of course, on the distribution of individuals on the continuous character. However, local minima and maxima also occur on the analogous functions of shape variables 2, 3, and 4 (Table 17). The phenomenon appears to be a general result of the method rather than the particular distribution of individuals on a given variable. The phenomenon is also

Table 17. Character Length as a Function of Gap Size. For each shape variable, the length of the discrete character is given over a broad range of gap sizes. An asterisk marks the first point of a local maximum.

Gap Size	Length of Discrete Character	Gap Size	Length of Discrete Character
Shape Variable 1			
		2.10	20 *
0.50	26	2.15	20
0.55	26	2.20	18
0.57	24	2.25	18
0.59	22	2.30	18
0.60	20	2.35	16
0.65	24 *	2.50	16
0.75	22	2.60	16
0.80	22	2.70	14
0.85	20	2.75	14
0.90	20	2.85	16
0.95	20	2.90	18 *
1.00	20	2.95	18
1.10	18	3.00	18
1.15	18	3.25	16
1.25	18	3.50	14
1.35	18	3.75	16 *
1.50	18	4.00	14
1.65	16	5.00	12
1.75	16	6.00	10
1.85	16	7.00	10
1.95	16	8.00	6
2.00	18	10.00	4
2.05	18	12.00	2

Table 17. (continued) Character Length and Gap Size

Gap Size	Length of Discrete Character	Gap Size	Length of Discrete Character
Shape Variable 2		Shape Variable 4	
0.40	8	0.40	8
0.50	6	0.50	7
0.55	9	0.75	7
0.75	10 *	1.00	6
1.00	10	1.25	5
1.25	8	1.50	6 *
1.50	6	1.75	4
1.75	8 *	2.00	3
2.00	6	2.25	2
2.25	5	2.50	3 *
2.50	5	2.75	1
2.75	5	3.00	2 *
3.00	4	3.25	1
3.25	4	3.50	2 *
3.50	3	3.75	1
3.75	3	4.00	0
4.00	2		
Shape Variable 3			
0.40	8		
0.50	7		
0.75	6		
1.00	7 *		
1.25	5		
1.50	5		
1.75	5		
2.00	3		
2.25	3		
2.50	2		
2.75	1		
3.00	1		
3.25	1		
3.50	1		
3.75	0		

Fig. 56. Character Length as a Function of Gap Size in Shape Variable I. The upper figure displays the value of the function over the complete range of gap sizes examined (0.5 - 12.0). The lower figure the same function expanded in the region from 0.5 to 3.0. Note that the function is discrete and should ideally contain only vertical and horizontal segments. However, this approximate representation illustrates the presence of local maxima and minima in the function.

Character Length as a Function of Gap Size: Shape Variable I

not unique to the two-step method of coding homogeneous subsets, as it also occurs in one-step coding.

The lengths of the discrete characters produced by applying the three gap constants to the shape variables are reported in Table 18. The reduction in character length that accompanies an increase in gap size was grossly disproportionate across the shape components. The first shape variable loses only two steps (10 percent of its maximum length) between gap sizes 1.0 and 2.0, and none between 2.0 and 3.0. At the other extreme, the third shape variable loses 8 steps (57 percent of its maximum length) between gap sizes 1.0 and 2.0, then another 4 steps (to only 14 percent of its maximum length) between 2.0 and 3.0.

In a cladistic analysis of qualitative characters, it is common to treat all character state changes as being equally informative. If a character is defined as a collection of mutually exclusive states, a character's weight is then equal to its length. In another sense, each character is weighted by its ability to discriminate among taxa. In the present example, however, the length of the discrete character does not always accurately reflect the ability of the original continuous variable to discriminate among taxa. There is a strong interaction between the effective gap size, and the distribution of taxa in the determination of a discrete character's length. A more appropriate measure of a continuous variable's power to

discriminate among species, or at least its potential to discriminate, is its standardized range (the range between the largest and smallest means divided by the pooled within group standard deviation). This statistic measures the variance among species means relative to the variance of individuals within species. The standardized range measures discriminatory power independently of the gap constant, and was therefore used as a reference value in comparisons of the coding results.

The standardized range for each of the shape variables is reported in Table 18. The distribution of discriminatory power among the continuous variables (expressed as percentages of total) was used as a reference profile. Fifty percent of the total discriminatory power is provided in the first variable. The second variable separates species less than half as well as the first. The third and fourth variables have nearly equivalent discriminatory powers, and combine to provide nearly 30 percent of the total.

Similar profiles of discriminatory power (as measured by character length) were generated for each of the discrete-character data sets. In comparison to the reference profile, the data set produced by a gap constant of 1.0 under-emphasizes the first shape variable, while over-emphasizing subsequent ones, particularly shape variables two and three. The second and third data sets

Table 18. Standardized Ranges of the Shape Variables and Discrete Character Lengths. For each of the continuous shape variables, the standardized range (the range between the smallest and largest species means divided by the pooled within-group standard deviation) is reported. This measure of potential discriminatory power is compared to the discrete character lengths produced by coding the shape variables with gap sizes of 1.00, 2.00, and 3.00 standard deviation units. Percentages of the totals are given in parentheses.

Shape Variable	Standardized Range	Length of Discrete Character by Gap Size (SDUs)		
		1.0	2.0	3.0
1	12.89 (50)	20 (30)	18 (42)	18 (56)
2	5.58 (21)	20 (30)	12 (28)	8 (25)
3	3.56 (14)	14 (21)	6 (14)	2 (6)
4	3.82 (15)	12 (18)	6 (14)	4 (12)

(generated with gap sizes 2.00 and 3.00, respectively) have discriminatory profiles that match the profile of standardized ranges substantially better than does the first data set. However, they deviate from the reference profile in different directions and are thus different from each other. The second data set under emphasizes the first shape variable, over emphasizes the second, and weights the third and fourth almost perfectly. The third data set overemphasizes the first and second variables and under emphasizes the third and fourth.

The distribution of discriminatory power among the continuous variables was used as the model in the weighted parsimony analyses. Each discrete character was weighted so that its length multiplied by the weighting factor was equal to the percentage of discriminatory power provided by the continuous variable (Table 19).

The Parsimony Analyses

Six different parsimony analyses were performed, one weighted and one unweighted for each of the data sets produced by a different gap constant. More than one minimum length tree resulted from each of the six analyses. The numbers of trees and their consistency indexes are presented in Table 20.

Because a smaller gap constant generally produces a more finely resolved character, the data set generated by a

Table 19. Weights Applied to Discrete Characters.
 Character weights were calculated such that the length (L) multiplied by the weight (Wt) would be equal to the proportion (or percentage, %) of discriminatory power provided by the original continuous variable (desired weighting profile).

Character	Data Set (Gap Constant)						Desired Weighting Profile %
	1.00		2.00		3.00		
	Wt	L	Wt	L	Wt	L	
1	2.50	(20)	2.78	(18)	2.78	(18)	50
2	1.05	(20)	1.75	(12)	2.62	(8)	21
3	1.00	(14)	2.33	(6)	7.00	(2)	14
4	1.25	(12)	2.50	(6)	3.75	(4)	15

Table 20. Results of Parsimony Analyses

Unweighted Analyses

Data Set (Gap Size)	Consistency Index	Number of Equally Parsimonious Trees
1.0	0.420	2
2.0	0.494	4
3.0	0.615	24

Weighted Analyses

Data Set (Gap Size)	Consistency Index	Number of Equally Parsimonious Trees
1.0	0.464	2
2.0	0.509	3
3.0	0.603	6

gap constant of 1.00 should portray the continuous data with greater fidelity than the data sets generated by the larger gap constants. The most finely resolved data set yields the lowest consistency values (0.420 in the unweighted analysis, and 0.464 in the weighted analysis). These values are relatively low, and infer that a substantial amount of homoplastic evolution has occurred among the continuous shape variables. Given that homoplasy exists in the original shape variables, it follows that the less resolved data sets should also have higher consistency values (with fewer character states there is less opportunity for extra character state changes). The increase in consistency comes at the expense of resolution. The analysis with the highest consistency (0.615) also produces the greatest number of equally parsimonious trees (24).

Strict consensus trees summarize the cladistic relationships inferred by each of the coding and weighting schemes. The data set generated by a gap constant of 2.00 (analyzed with or without weights) produces the most familiar results (Fig. 58). Four of the five polytypic subgenera are inferred to be monophyletic in both consensus trees. Only Discochaetodon is represented as paraphyletic.

The data set produced by a gap constant of 1.00 infers that either two (in the unweighted analysis) or three (in the weighted analysis) of the subgenera are monophyletic (Fig. 57). The data set produced by a gap constant of 3.00 infers

Fig. 57. Strict Consensus of Trees Resulting from Parsimony Analyses of Data Set I (Gap Constant=1.00). Monophyletic subgenera are shown in bold lines. A, unweighted analysis; B, weighted analysis.

Data Set I, Gap Constant = 1.00

A: Unweighted Analysis
Consensus of 2 Trees

B: Unweighted Analysis
Consensus of 4 Trees

Fig. 58. Strict Consensus of Trees Resulting from Parsimony Analyses of Data Set II (Gap Constant=2.00). Monophyletic subgenera are shown in bold lines. A, unweighted analysis; B, weighted analysis.

Data Set II, Gap Constant = 2.00

A: Weighted Analysis
Consensus of 3 Trees

B: Weighted Analysis
Consensus of 6 Trees

Fig. 59. Strict Consensus of Trees Resulting from Parsimony Analyses of Data Set III (Gap Constant=3.00). Monophyletic subgenera are shown in bold lines. A, unweighted analysis; B, weighted analysis.

Data Set III, Gap Constant = 3.00

A: Unweighted Analysis
Consensus of 24 Trees

B: Weighted Analysis
Consensus of 2 Trees

that only one subgenus, Corallochaetodon, is monophyletic (Fig. 59).

No combination of gap constant and weighting scheme infers relationships among subgenera that are in accord with those revealed by osteology. In particular, osteological characters strongly infer that the subgenera Corallochaetodon and Citharoedus are sister taxa, and that they are the most derived of the corallivores. These two subgenera are never indicated as sister taxa in any of the trees generated from the morphometric data.

The trees inferred by the morphometric methods also lack congruence among themselves. A strict consensus analysis of the trees produced by the three unweighted analyses yields a consensus tree (Fig. 60A) that contains only four groups, and one of these, the most inclusive, is an artifact of the common rooting method. The consensus tree of the weighted analyses contains only five groups (Fig. 60B), only one more than the tree derived from the unweighted analyses. Only two different parsimony analyses produce trees that are perfectly congruent. These were the weighted and unweighted analyses of characters produced by a gap constant of 2.00. However, this congruence is not particularly meaningful because the weights applied to this data set altered the balance of characters weights the least.

Fig. 60. Consensus Trees across Gap Constants. Consensus trees were formed by pooling trees across gap constants. Weighted and unweighted analyses were kept separate. Monophyletic subgenera are shown in bold lines. A, unweighted analysis; B, weighted analysis.

A: Consensus of Weighted Analyses

B: Consensus of Unweighted Analyses

It could be argued that it is unreasonable to expect much congruence when the gap constant is varied by a factor of three and a significant amount of homoplasy exists among the continuous characters. Therefore, congruence was examined among three data sets produced by a much narrower range of gap constants, 1.75, 2.00, and 2.25. Parsimony analyses of these data, without weighting, produced 1, 2, and 20 minimum length trees (for gap constants 1.75, 2.00 and 2.25, respectively). The consensus analysis of these trees contained only six groups (Fig. 61). This is not an impressive gain in congruence for a four fold reduction in the range among gap constants. (The lack of resolution in the final consensus tree was not entirely due to the lack of resolution in the data set produced by a gap constant of 2.25, as the consensus tree of these 20 minimum length trees contained 13 groups.)

Discussion

Morphometric vs. Qualitative Data

Although the morphometric analyses did not produce a single result, a comparison of the osteological and morphometric characters shows that qualitative skeletal features and body shape (as represented by these four shape variables) have not evolved in concert. Moreover, the differences between osteology and body shape have not simply

Fig. 61. Consensus across a More Narrow Range of Gap Constants. Two additional sets of discrete characters were generated by coding the continuous shape variables with gap constants of 1.75 and 2.25. Trees produced from unweighted parsimony analyses of these data sets (1 and 20 trees, respectively) were combined with those produced from a gap constant of 2.00 (4 trees, unweighted). Monophyletic subgenera are shown in bold lines.

Gap Constants = 1.75, 2.00, and 2.25

Unweighted Analyses

Consensus of 25 Trees

resulted from a mosaic pattern of evolution, in which different suites of characters have evolved at different rates, while both reflect the same pattern of cladistic divergence. The differences between these data sets are extensive enough to infer that one (or both) of them does (do) not reflect the cladistic history of the group.

A comparison of the two data sets by their internal consistencies identifies the morphometric characters as the more labile and homoplastic. The highest consistency in any of the morphometric analyses was 0.615, but this value is inflated by lack of resolution and low weights assigned to the third and fourth shape variables. The consistency values from the data sets produced by gap constants of 1.00 and 2.00 are better approximations of the consistency among the original shape variables. In contrast, the consistency among osteological characters within the corallivores (i.e. the same taxa, plus Parachaetodon) is 0.875. The higher degree of internal consistency in the osteological characters infers that they are more stable, and more likely to reflect the true cladistic history of the group.

The potential for body shape to evolve rapidly is best demonstrated by a comparison of Megaprotodon and its sister taxon, Parachaetodon, on the first shape variable, the contrast between body depth and length. Note that this component represents the greatest amount of shape variability among these fishes (the eigenvalue associated

with the first shape component, before shearing, was 1.7 times larger than any subsequent eigenvalue), and that it provided more than twice the discriminatory power of any other component (as measured by the standardized ranges among species means). Although Parachaetodon was inadvertently omitted from the morphometric analysis, it is clear from inspection that Parachaetodon is one of the most deep-bodied of all chaetodontids. Had it been included in the morphometric analysis, it would have had a very high, if not the highest rank on the first shape variable.

Megaprotodon has the oppositely extreme body shape, and had the lowest rank on the first shape variable (Fig. 52).

Given their divergent body shapes, even the most conservative scenario (in which their common ancestor had an exactly intermediate form) requires an impressively rapid rate of evolution. Half of the range among all corallivores would have had to be traversed in each descendant lineage.

The omission of Parachaetodon from the morphometric analysis biased the results toward a higher congruence with the osteological characters. Because Parachaetodon and Megaprotodon have oppositely extreme overall body shapes, it is unlikely that the morphometric methods would have replicated their close relationship. The omission also biased the results toward a higher internal consistency. Adding a taxon to a parsimony analysis can only decrease consistency (if new characters are not added). Because the

internal consistency of the morphometric data is low, and its congruence with the osteological data is also low, the inclusion of Parachaetodon could only worsen the comparison of the morphometric data set to these criteria.

Effectiveness of the Methods

In this study, sheared principal components analysis effectively identified the greatest shape difference among species, the contrast between body depth and length. However, shape variables after the first could not be interpreted as representing specific morphological features.

The same snout and tail variables loaded heavily on all three subsequent shape variables. The repeated strong loadings of these variables and the orthogonal orientation of the components is paradoxical, and effectively renders the shape variables uninterpretable. The fact that these components are orthogonal seems to require that large suites of variables with smaller loadings play a large role in determining their directions and the scores of individuals on these components.

In hind sight, it also appears that principal component analysis and cladistics are incompatible despite the theoretical justifications for sheared principal components analysis as a tool for describing shape differences. The incompatibility arises from the restriction that principal components be orthogonal to each other (i.e. completely

uncorrelated). The statistical objective of a principal components analysis is to summarize suites of variables (characters) that have large partial intercorrelations. Within a cladistic context, this kind of summarization is desirable to the extent that certain morphometric variables are correlated morphogenetically or selectively. However, perfect cladistic data are structured hierarchically. Characters that are morphogenetically and selectively independent, but acquired sequentially through evolution, will have correlated distributions in terminal taxa. Summarizing these statistically correlated but biologically independent characters in a single variable causes the evidence for relationship among descendant taxa to be underestimated.

There are also several problems associated with generalized gap coding. Any translation of continuous variables into discrete characters entails a distortion of the original data space. The reduction of distance between some taxa is intentional; distances between taxa that are broadly overlapping are reduced to zero. However, the magnification of distances between other taxa (distance inversion) is counter-intuitive, and must be regarded as an undesirable distortion of the data.

The choice of gap constant is arbitrary and can profoundly affect the results of a parsimony analysis if the data do not have a high degree of internal consistency. In

this study, the disproportionate changes in character lengths that accompanied changes in the gap constant showed that generalized gap coding can distort the external dimensions of the data space. The characters were then weighted in an attempt to preserve the relative dimensions among characters. However, the lack of consensus among the weighted parsimony analyses shows that variable distortion occurs not just among characters, but also within characters. The distances between taxa on a single character can vary significantly when different gap constants are used. Therefore, an increase in the gap constant does not just simply reduce the resolution of the cladogram, but can significantly change the positions of resolved taxa (note the lack of resolution in consensus across gap constants, Fig. 60). This may not be surprising when the range among gap constants (2.00 standard deviation units) was equal to their mean. However, it also occurred when the range among gap constants was decreased to only 25 percent of their mean (Fig. 61). Clearly, the choice of gap constant has the potential to profoundly influence the outcome of a parsimony analysis. Given that the results may be sensitive to this choice, an investigator must either provide a convincing a priori justification for that choice, or demonstrate that the results are robust to deviation from that choice. In this study, the results were decidedly not robust to the choice of gap constant.

APPENDIX A

CLEARED AND STAINED MATERIAL EXAMINED

Locality and registration data are presented below for all cleared and stained material examined in this survey. Outgroup specimens are presented in Section I alphabetically by family, genus, and species. Chaetodontids are presented in Section II alphabetically by genus and species. Chaetodontid specimens that could not be identified to species (larvae) are listed at the end of Section II. Collection acronyms are as follows:

AM	Australian Museum, Sydney.
AMNH	American Museum of Natural History, New York.
ANSP	Academy of Natural Sciences, Philadelphia.
CAS	California Academy of Science, San Francisco.
SDB	Stanley D. Blum (personal collection).
UH	University of Hawaii, Honolulu (all material uncataloged, collection inactive)
USA	University of South Alabama
USNM	United States National Museum, Washington D.C.

The abbreviation "C&S" is used in reference to partial lots or parts of individuals that were cleared and stained.

After completing this dissertation, my personal collection (SDB) was deposited and cataloged at AMNH. I have added the AMNH numbers to this electronic version because I believe these ultimate references to voucher material are more important than fidelity to the original dissertation. Adding the numbers caused the text to be longer, so I reduced the line-spacing to keep the total number of pages constant. Nevertheless, the exact pagination in this section departs from the original. Some minor inconsistencies in formatting were also corrected. — *S.D. Blum*, August 14, 2003

SECTION I: OUTGROUP TAXA

ACANTHURIDAE

Zebrasoma veliferum: **AMNH 88346** (SDB 157), 73 mm, Oahu, Hawaiian Islands, 1985, aquarium specimen, parasitic isopod in gills.

CAPROIDAE

Antigonia combatia: **USNM 266901**, 39 mm, "Oregon II", Station 12509, 5°43'N, 51°15'W, 100 fathoms, 40' Shrimp trawl, Jul. 4 1972 (C&S one of approx. 30).

DREPANIDAE

Drepane punctata: **AMNH 13922**, 31 mm, Mouth of Padada R., Gulf of Davao, Celebes Sea, Philippines, by G.R. Oesch; **USNM 267052**, 49 mm, Shama Bay, Ghana, coll. Amegah, Field no. GWB 821, Jan. 26, 1961.

EPHIPPIDIDAE

Chaetodipterus faber: **AMNH 22054**, 48 and 59 mm, Glynn Co., Georgia, 3 mi. off St. Simon's Island; **AMNH 88441** (SDB 150), 197 mm, purchased at Tomashiro's Fish Market, Honolulu, Hawaii (from Florida), 1985, jaws removed for SEM.

Platax orbicularis: **AMNH 88357** (SDB 111), 16.5, 16.5, 17.0, 17.5, and 21.7 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Platax pinnatus: **AMNH 88344** (SDB 108), 57 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88348** (SDB 106), 39 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88449** (SDB 109), 38 and 41 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Platax tiera: **AMNH 88349** (SDB 107), 50 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88361** (SDB 110), 14.9 and 20.8 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Rhinoprenes pentanemus: **ANSP 134860**, 97 mm, Western Australia, Australia, off Joseph Bonaparte Gulf (formerly WAM-P21691-98).

KYPHOSIDAE

Kyphosus sectatrix: **AMNH 20855**, 60 and 62 mm, Zelaya, Nicaragua, Great Corn Island, J.D. Villa, Jan. 26, 1966.

MONODACTYLIDAE

Monodactylus argenteus: **USNM 266897**, 38 mm, Papua New Guinea, Central district, mangrove creek flowing into Bootless Bay, about 5 mi. E of Port Moresby, by Tyson Roberts, Jul. 12, 1975.

POMACANTHIDAE

Apolemichthys arcuatus: **AMNH 38135**, 50 mm, Philippines, Marine Tropical Imports, May 1978.

Centropyge flavissimus: **AMNH 88352** (SDB 86), 59 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Centropyge heraldi: **AMNH 88347** (SDB 85), 40 and 71 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Centropyge loriculus: **AMNH 88351** (SDB 83), 38, 39, 40, and 51 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Centropyge potteri: **AMNH 88350** (SDB 84), 55 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Centropyge vroliki: **USNM 263255**, 35 mm (approx.), Rabaul, New Britain, Simpson Harbor, near Malangan Mission, New Guinea, Bismark Arch., "Te Vega" Cr. #6, Station 236, Feb. 28, 1965, 4°13'14"S, 152°09'06"E.

Chaetodontplus sp.: **AMNH 88354** (SDB 158?), 87 mm, from
Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Genicanthus melanospilus: **AMNH 43415**, 89 mm, Philippines,
Cebu Island, Santo Rosa Lapu, Marine Tropical Imports,
May, 1980.

Holacanthus tricolor: **AMNH 22935**, 23, 25, and 29 mm,
Bahamas, Frazer's Hog Cay, S shore of Berry Isl., near
Texaco Sign, C.L. Smith et al., July 14, 1964.

Pomacanthus imperator: **AMNH 88360** (SDB 60), 42 mm, W. Samoa,
10 mi E. of Apia, by Snider, Jan. 4, 1965 (C&S one of
two).

Pomacanthus paru: **USNM 263253**, 29 mm, Caribbean, Puerto
Rico, San Juan, beach a Puerto Nuevo near Vega Baha, by
E. M. Nelson, Jul. 7, 1960; **AMNH 88443** (SDB 131), 160
mm, Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data (jaws removed
for SEM).

Pygoplites diacanthus: **USNM 261764**, 43 mm, Negros Island,
Philippines, off Bonbonon Pt., Rotenone, by Springer et
al., May 12, 1978, Station SP-78-9, 6-9 m deep,
9°2'27"N, 123°07'37"E.

Pomacanthid larva: **USNM 266899**, 11 mm, 7°56-7'S, 65°14-
51'E., by "Anton Bruun" Cr. 6 Station 341 B, Shallow
fraction, 10'IK Mid Wat. Trawl, June 1-2, 1964, depth
0-275 m.

SCATOPHAGIDAE

Scatophagus argus: **USNM 180300**, 18 mm, Kowloon, China, by
the "Albatross", Sep 9, 1908.

Selenotoca multifasciata: **USNM 245702**, 47 mm, Queensland,
Australia, Gulf of Carpenteria, Duyfken point, near

Weipa, "Alpha Helix" Cr., Collette and Ferrari, Jun. 4,
1969, 12°35'24"S, 141°36'12"E (C&S one of approx. 30).

SCORPIDIDAE

Microcanthus strigatus: **USNM 267047**, 34 mm, Queensland,
Australia, One Tree Island, tidal pool on reef flat on
SE side of island, Rotenone, by V. G. Springer, Nov.
27, 1966 (C&S one of 34).

SIGANIDAE

Siganus rostratus: **AMNH 88353** (SDB 114, UH), 104 mm,
Papeete, Tahiti, Quarentine Island, by J. E. Randall,
Feb. 26, 1956.

TOXOTIDAE

Toxotes chatareus: **AMNH 33638**, (5) 29, 30, 34, 35, 48 mm,
Western Australia, Australia, near Yeeda Homestead, by
Rosen, Nelson, Butler, April 19, 1969.

ZANCLIDAE

Zanclus cornutus: **BPBM 10630**, 65 mm, Oahu, Hawaiian Islands,
Hanauma Bay, by G. R. Allen, Nov. 7, 1965.

SECTION II: INGROUP TAXA (CHAETODONTIDAE).

Amphichaetodon howensis: **AM I.17260-002**, 53 mm, New South Wales, Australia, Seal Rocks, 31°26'S, 152°32'E, by R. Kuitert, May 6, 1964; **AM 24461-001**, 90 mm, New South Wales, Off Greenwell Pt., 34°31'S, 151°09'E, 139-142 m, by F.R.V. "Kapala", Feb. 23, 1982 (jaws removed for SEM); **AM I.17412-001**, 94 mm, Lord Howe Island, New South Wales, Rocks off Ball's Pyramid, 31°32'S, 159°04'E, 90-100 m, by B. Russell & J. Randall, Feb. 22, 1973.

Chaetodon adiergastos: **USNM 267051**, 52 mm, Borneo, Palau Gaya, Darvel Bay, East end of Borneo, Inside Lagoon, coral band 50-70 feet wide, 0-3 m Te Vega Cr. 6, Station 213, Feb. 1, 1965.

Chaetodon aureofasciatus: **AMNH 88400** (SDB 88), 62 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88401** (SDB 96), 47 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data (jaws removed for SEM).

Chaetodon auriga: **AMNH 88426** (SDB 14, UH), 28 and 32 mm, Sand Island, Palmyra, Line Islands Dec. 30, 1959; **AMNH 88420** (SDB 140), 76 mm, Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data, (jaws removed for SEM); **SDB 27**, 86 mm, Oahu, Hawaiian Islands, Kaneohe Bay, near Tom's Reef, mini-spear, by S. D. Blum, Jul. 1983 (gills and suspensorium C&S).

Chaetodon baronessa: **USNM 266891**, 55 mm, Papua New Guinea, Hermit Island, Amot Island, Ocean side of reef at drop off, by V. G. Springer, Oct 30, 1978, 1°33'S, 144°59'E, 0-15.2 m (C&S one of six); **AMNH 41597**, 42, 43, and 45

mm, Philippines, Cebu, Santa Rosa Lapu, Marine Tropical Imports, May 1980.

Chaetodon bennetti: **AMNH 88448** (SDB 33, UH), 120 mm, Onotoa, Gilbert Islands, (gills and suspensorium C&S, jaws removed for SEM); **AMNH 88394** (SDB 135), 89 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chaetodon capistratus, **USNM 266896**, 43 mm, Cabrana Island, Columbia, 0-1.5 m, 9°44.6'N, 75°41.1'W, Rotenone, by Les Knapp, Oct. 1, 1969 (C&S one of six specimens); **AMNH 88439** (SDB 129), 78 mm, Bocas Del Torro, Prov., Panama, Crinin Key, Lobster trap, by local fisherman (via P. Meylan), 20 May 1987 (jaws removed for SEM).

Chaetodon citrinellus: **AMNH 88428** (SDB 25, UH), 78 mm, Kwajalein, Japanese Pools, Ralston and Brock, Jul. 5-15, 1975, gravid female; **AMNH 88403** (SDB 69), 35 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chaetodon daedalma: **AMNH 88434** (SDB 153), 64, 93 and 99 mm, gift from Mitsuhiro Sano, no data.

Chaetodon ephippium: **AMNH 88425** (SDB 13, UH), 22 mm, Onotoa, Gilbert Islands, by J. E. Randall, 1951; **AMNH 88419** (SDB 139), 66 and 92 mm, Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chaetodon flavirostris: **USNM 266898**, 60 mm, Queensland, Australia, Great Barrier Reef, One Tree Reef, by V. G. Springer, Dec. 1, 1966, Coral outcrop about 1500' WNW of One Tree (Lagoon side of Island) 12 feet deep.

Chaetodon fremblii: **AMNH 88423** (SDB 5, UH), 42 mm, Diamond Head, Oahu, by J. Ludwig and C. Tamaru, Apr. 14 1974; **AMNH 88404** (SDB 126), 57 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chaetodon kleinii: **AMNH 88427** (SDB 22, UH), 42 mm, Onotoa, Gilbert Islands; **AMNH 88430** (SDB 94), 53 and 69 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chaetodon lunula: **AMNH 88424** (SDB 11, UH), 47 mm, no data; **SDB**, 120 mm, Kahe Pt., Oahu, Hawaiian Islands, by S. D. Blum, May 18, 1983, mini-spear (completely disarticulated).

Chaetodon melannotus: **USNM 266894**, 18, 27, and 42 mm, Ambon, Moluccas, Indonesia, Teluk Baguala off Suli, by V. G. Springer, Mar. 18, 1974, Rotenone and dip net, Lat. (ca) 003 38 00 S. Long. (ca) 128 17 30, (3 of about 50 C&S); **AMNH 88366** (SDB 143), 49 mm, Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88369** (SDB 141), 69 and 74 mm, Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data (jaws of larger removed for SEM).

Chaetodon melapterus: **AMNH 88412** (SDB 63), 65 mm, Tanjib, Saudi Arabia, Arabian Gulf, coral reef, 1-5 m, A.B. Tarr and K.E. Carpenter, Sep. 23, 1982.

Chaetodon mertensii: **AMNH 88412** (SDB 117, UH), 86 mm, Kwajalein, Japanese Pools, by Ralston et al. (jaws removed for SEM).

Chaetodon meyeri: **SDB 21** (UH), 130 mm, Onotoa, Gilbert Islands, (C&S branchial skeleton only).

Chaetodon miliaris: **AMNH 88402** (SDB 26, UH), 52 mm, no data.

Chaetodon multicinctus: **AMNH 88389** (SDB 71), 54 and 72 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88390** (SDB 93), 46, 53, and 55 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88343** (SDB 2), 48 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chaetodon nigropunctatus: **AMNH 88386** (SDB 62), 63 mm, from Tanjib, Saudi Arabia, Arabian Gulf, coral reef, 1-5 m, A.B. Tarr and K.E. Carpenter, Sep. 23, 1982; **AMNH 88429** (SDB 62) 30 MM, same local. as AMNH 88386.

Chaetodon nippon: **AMNH 88433** (SDB 113), 93 mm, Miyake Jima, Japan, Igaya Bay, about 50 m north of right pier, over boulders and sand, Barrier net, by Jack Moyer and Stan Blum, Jul. 25, 1985, 1730 hr; **AMNH 88397** (SDB 154), 69, 74, and 76 mm, gift from Mitsuhiro Sano, no data.

Chaetodon ocellatus: **USNM 068574**, 51 mm, Florida.

Chaetodon octofasciatus: **USNM 266890**, 44 mm, Indonesia, Southwest Coast of Karimundjawa Island (North of greater Mendjangan Island), 5°52'30"S, 110°25'40"E, 0-40 feet, Rotenone and dip net, by V. G. Springer, Mar. 29, 1974 (C&S one of ten specimens).

Chaetodon oligacanthus, **USNM 266892**, 30 mm, Pulau Seribu, Java, Indonesia; **USNM 181231**, (2) 10.0 and 11.7 mm (larvae), Port Dupon, Philippines, by the Albatross; **AMNH 88421** (SDB 115), 84 mm, fish market, Philippines, via K.E. Carpenter, summer, 1984; **AMNH 88422** (SDB 115), 76 mm, fish market, Philippines, via K.E. Carpenter, summer, 1984 (jaws removed for SEM).

Chaetodon ornatissimus: **AMNH 88418** (SDB 12, UH), 52 mm, Sand Island, Palmyra, Line Islands, Station A, by P. Helfrich et al., Jun. 20, 1962; **AMNH 88417** (SDB 98), 55 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **SDB 29**, 90 mm, Oahu, Hawaiian Islands, Kaneohe Bay, near Tom's Reef, mini-spear, by S. D. Blum, Jul. 1983, (gills and suspensorium C&S); **AMNH 88447** (SDB 37, UH), 146 mm, no

data (C&S gills and suspensorium, jaws removed for SEM).

Chaetodon pelewensis: **AMNH 88405 (SDB 70)**, 64 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88406 (SDB 92)**, 40, 45, and 46 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chaetodon plebeius: **USNM 266902**, 55 mm, Queensland, Australia, Heron Island, reef crest pool, by J. H. Choat, Feb 14, 1967 (C&S one of six specimens); **AMNH 88438 (SDB 72)**, 38, 46, 52, and 59 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data (skull of 46 mm specimen completely disarticulated).

Chaetodon quadrimaculatus: **SDB 34 (UH)**, 112 mm, Kauai, Hawaiian Islands, Na Pali coast, by Brock et al., Aug. 27, 1949, (C&S gills and suspensorium).

Chaetodon rafflesi: **AMNH 88387 (SDB 76)**, 56 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chaetodon rainfordi: **AMNH 88398 (SDB 87)**, 58 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88446**, 76 mm, Aq. mat, no data (jaws removed for SEM).

Chaetodon reticulatus: **AMNH 88415 (SDB 4, UH)**, 49 mm, Papaete, Tahiti, Quarantine Island, by J. E. Randall, Feb. 2, 1956; **AMNH 88416 (SDB 97)**, 37 and 59 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chaetodon speculum: **AMNH 88407 (SDB 73)**, 35 and 53 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88408 (SDB 73)**, 50 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chaetodon striatus: **USNM 178222**, 45 mm (approx.), Bermuda, by Beebe (originally New York Zoological Society, completely disarticulated); **AMNH 88440 (SDB 130)**, 96

mm, Bocas Del Toro Prov., Panama, Bocas Del Toro, Crinin Key, lobster trap, by local fisherman (via P. Meylan), May 20, 1987.

Chaetodon tinkeri: **AMNH 88436** (SDB 112), 104 mm, Oahu, Hawaiian Islands, off Kailua beach, by Frank Parrish, Jan., 1986.

Chaetodon trichrous: **AMNH 88431** (SDB 95), 40 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chaetodon trifascialis: **AMNH 88413** (SDB 3, UH), 55 mm, Kwajalein, Marshall Islands, Japanese Pools by Ralston et al.; **AMNH 88445** (SDB 35, UH), 117 mm, no data, (jaws removed for SEM).

Chaetodon trifasciatus: **AMNH 88414** (SDB 10, UH), 29 and 43 mm, no data; **AMNH 88411** (SDB 75), 40 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **SDB 28**, 99 mm, Oahu, Hawaiian Islands, Kaneohe Bay, near Tom's Reef, mini-spear, by S. D. Blum, Jul. 1983 (C&S gills and suspensorium).

Chaetodon ulietensis: **AMNH 88384** (SDB 68), 32 and 55 mm, Aq. mat., no data; **AMNH 88388** (SDB 145), 44 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88383** (SDB 146), 51 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88391** (SDB 133), 67 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88392** (SDB 147), 48 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **SDB 32** (UH), 106 mm, Onotoa, Gilbert Islands, (C&S gills and suspensorium).

Chaetodon unimaculatus: **AMNH 88399** (SDB 23, UH), 41 mm, Johnston Island, in lagoon SW of small boat channel, by Brock et al., Aug., 1968; **AMNH 88342** (SDB 1, UH), 45

mm, no data (looked like starved aquarium specimen, probably from Oahu); **AMNH 88432** (SDB 149), 42 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88409** (SDB 148), 46 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88410** (SDB 142), 65 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **SDB 16**, 146 mm, Oahu, Hawaii, near Tom's Reef, Kaneohe Bay, mini-spear, by S. D. Blum, Jul., 1983 (disarticulated).

Chaetodon vagabundus: **AMNH 88393** (SDB 138), 68 and 73 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88444**, 95 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chaetodon xanthurus: **AMNH 88435** (SDB 120), 82 mm, Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chelmon marginalis: **USNM 263254**, 51 mm, One Tree Islet, Queensland, Australia.

Chelmon mulleri: **AMNH 88373** (SDB 104), 55 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88376** (SDB 118), 80 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chelmon rostratus: **AMNH 88371** (SDB 80), 64 and 73 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, (jaws of 73 mm specimen removed for SEM); **AMNH 88355** (SDB 132), 68 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88356** (SDB 81), 53 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88358** (SDB 105), 48 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Chelmonops truncatus: **AM IB.8172**, 40 mm (estimated), Rottnest Island, Western Australia (completely disarticulated); **AMNH 88378** (SDB 103), 68 and 71; **AMNH 88375** (SDB 121), 77 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian

Fishes, no data (jaws removed for SEM); **AMNH 88377** (SDB 122), 78 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Coradion altivelis: **AMNH 88359** (SDB 102), 54 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Coradion chrysozonus: **USNM 266889**, 51 mm, Visayan Sea, Philippines, between northern Negros and Masbate Islands, E. of Tanguingui, 11°27'00"N, 123°49'11"E, by "Sting Ray V", 80' Otter trawl, 0-74.4 m deep, Jun. 6, 1978; **AMNH 88396** (SDB 79), 71 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data (jaws removed for SEM) [thesis says 74 mm];

Forcipiger flavissimus: **AMNH 88365** (SDB 125, UH), 75 mm, Oahu, Hawaiian Islands, Makua, by Leighton Taylor, May 7 1974; **AMNH 88370** (SDB 24, UH), 80 mm, Oahu, Hawaiian Islands, Makua, Rotenone, Sep. 14, 1973; **AMNH 88372** (SDB 124, UH), 10.5, 13.8, and 47 mm (larvae), by J. Fowler, Dec. 2, 1972, largest with data tag "TC-32-28", intermediate with "TC-32-33", and smallest with "TC-32-23" (TC="Townsend Cromwell"); **AMNH 88367** (SDB 119), 84 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88368** (SDB 119), 88 and 89 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Hemitaurichthys polylepis: **SDB 30** (UH), 112 mm, no data (C&S gill and suspensorium); **AMNH 88379** (SDB 99), 65 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88442** (SDB 151, UH), 116 mm, Kailua, Oahu, Hawaiian Islands, washed up on Kailua Beach during natural fish kill, winter 1985, via James Norris (jaws removed for SEM).

Hemitaurichthys thompsoni: **AMNH 88395** (SDB 116, UH), 94 mm, Johnston Island, NE or North Island, spear, by Dennis M. Devaney, Jun. 23, 1964.

Heniochus chrysostomus: **AMNH 88381** (SDB 61, UH), 39 and 42 mm, Quarentine Island, Papeete, Tahiti, by J.E. Randall, Feb. 26, 1956; **AMNH 88382** (SDB 77), 36 and 39 mm; from Gruaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88380** (SDB 100), 35 and 41 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data.

Heniochus diphreutes: **AMNH 88364** (SDB 15, UH), 41 mm, Oahu, Hawaii, by "Miss Honolulu", 30 fathoms, Jul. 18. 1959.

Heniochus varius: **AMNH 88362** (SDB 78), 48 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data; **AMNH 88363** (SDB 101), 35 and 54 mm, from Guaranteed Hawaiian Fishes, no data (jaws of 54 mm specimen removed for SEM).

Johnrandallia nigrirostris: **SU 47435**, 60 mm, Isla Partida, Baja California, Mexico, by John Briggs et al., Mar. 22, 1953.

Prognathodes aculeatus: **AMNH 88374** (SDB 155), 74 and 75 (approx., jaws removed by collector) mm, St. Croix, US Virgin Islands, West Wall, South River Canyon, depth 20-50', Philip Motta, mini-spear, Aug 11-13, 1987.

Prognathodes aya: **USNM 266900**, 54 mm, Yucatan Channel, "Oregon" Station #3640, 86°34'W, 21°50'N, 30 fathoms, Jun. 12, 1962 (C&S one of seven); **AMNH 85143** (USA 05143), 88 mm, Gulf of Mexico, 25°05'N, 83°39'W, "Oregon II", No. 23598, 42 fathoms, by R.D. Nester, Jan. 28, 1978; **AMNH 802323** (USA 02323), 80 mm, 28°26'N, 84°56'W, 3H1-3685, 3H0-2834, BLM 22, by Shipp, Bortone,

Nester, Hastings, and Searcy, Oct. 20, 1975 (C&S 1 of 14).

Roa modestus: **CAS 15897**, 48 mm, Formosa Bank, Taiwan
Straight, trawled in 60 m, by F.B. Steiner, Feb., 1972;
Roa excelsa: **AMNH 88385** (SDB 123), 39 mm, Hawaiian Islands,
via J.D. Parrish (UH), gut contents of larger fish.

UNIDENTIFIED CHAETODONTIDAE

Chaetodon (Lepidochaetodon) sp., (larva): **USNM 266895**, 19
mm, "Te Vega", Cr. 5, Station 196, 05°06'N, 84°51'E,
midwater trawl, 75-85 m, Nov. 21, 1964.

Chaetodon sp. (larvae): **USNM 152964**, 18 mm, Namu Island,
Bikini, by Univ. of Wash., Area 95146, Aug. 16, 1947.

Chaetodon sp. (larva): **ANSP 82212**, 10 mm, Papeete, Tahiti,
by G. Vanderbilt Exp. S. Pacific, Apr 9, 1936 (C&S one
of five, misidentified as Parachaetodon);

Chaetodon sp. (larva): **ANSP 82213**, 10 mm, Christmas Island,
by G. Vanderbilt Exp. S. Pacific, May 6, 1936 (C&S one
of eight, misidentified as Parachaetodon);

Chaetodon sp.: **USNM 266893**, 15 mm, Putic Island, Palawan
province, Philippines, NW side of Cuyo Island, Station
SP78-18, depth 0-4.6 m (recently settled juvenile, C&S
one of two).

APPENDIX B

TOOTH REPLACEMENT IN POMACANTHIDS AND CHAETODONTIDS

The arrangement of teeth and the process of tooth replacement in pomacanthids and chaetodontids makes them distinct from all other percoids, as far as known. In pomacanthids and chaetodontids, as in most other teleosts (e.g. *Chaetodipterus*, Fig. 4A, an ehippidid), the teeth are arranged in rows that follow the labial margin of the jaw (Fig. 4B, C and D, Fig. 25A and B). As in other percoids with a type 2 mode of tooth attachment (Fink, 1981), the functional teeth are supported by bony tooth pedestals (Motta, 1984). Within the tooth rows of pomacanthids and chaetodontids, however, sequences of five to ten (or more) mature, functional teeth alternate with sequences of immature, non-functional teeth that are not supported by tooth pedestals. If all teeth are removed from a jaw, the sequences of immature teeth appear as large gaps between rows of tooth pedestals, or alveoli. The gaps are staggered between rows such that, in the next more lingual row, the corresponding gap is offset medially. This arrangement of gaps produces bands of tooth rows, in which a band is composed of two or more adjacent rows, and the bands extend laterally from the median symphysis. The banding pattern results from an organized process of tooth replacement.

Motta (1984) described the morphology and development of teeth in Chaetodon miliaris. This broader survey indicates that his observations pertain to all other chaetodontids and pomacanthids. As in other fishes with a type 2 mode of tooth attachment (Fink 1981), the enameloid tooth cap forms first, deep within the alveolar region (but not within an alveolus). The tooth cap is pushed distally by the addition of pre dentine at the base of the tooth (Motta, 1984). New observations show that the immature replacement teeth are more flexible and stain with alizarin less readily in proximal areas than distal ones. This is consistent with Motta's finding that mineralization of the pre dentine proceeds from distal to proximal as the tooth shaft lengthens. Motta was unable to characterize the actual process of tooth replacement, but suspected that: "...one-for-one replacement may be occurring lingually and possibly laterally to the functional teeth..." (1984; p. 186). He was also unable to infer the mechanism by which a fully developed replacement tooth becomes attached to its pedestal. Apparently he had assumed that a single tooth pedestal could support more than one tooth, sequentially. Observations made here indicate that this is not the case.

Scanning electron micrographs (Figs. 4, and 25-28) bear evidence of a more constrained process of tooth loss and replacement. In both pomacanthids and chaetodontids,

shorter pedestals (ie. those not reaching the same height as others in the same row, and therefore not fully developed) are seen only on the lateral ends of tooth rows, never within a row, and never on the medial end of a row (see Fig. 27B). Similarly, in cleared and stained specimens (in which all teeth remain intact), the longest non-functional teeth are laterally adjacent to a tooth row. Moreover, degenerating tooth pedestals are seen only at the medial ends of the tooth rows, never within a row, and never laterally. Figure 4C shows an inverted pomacanthid premaxilla, from which the surrounding laminar bone was removed to expose a perpendicular (dorsal) view of the tooth pedestals. The depth of the pedestals increases smoothly toward the lateral end of each row. This indicates that, for a given pedestal, resorption proceeds from proximal to distal, and that within a row, resorption proceeds from medial to lateral. It also indicates that a significant amount of pedestal resorption occurs before tooth loss.

Thus, it appears that teeth do not become attached to pedestals, but rather pedestals develop directly beneath replacement teeth. The mature tooth is elevated into functional position by growth of the tooth pedestal. The medial resorption of pedestals indicates that each pedestal supports only one tooth in its lifetime. Similar morphology is seen in chaetodontids and indicates that this process of

tooth replacement is common to both families.

Although no serial observations were made in vivo, it appears that individual teeth do not migrate within the jaw.

However, the model of tooth replacement, lateral addition and medial resorption, predicts that each row of teeth should move postero-laterally in the jaw as a wave. Each row begins medially at the symphysis, and grows laterally as teeth are added laterally. The length of each row is determined by the number of new teeth that are brought into functional position laterally before the oldest tooth is lost medially. The length of a tooth row is determined by the lifespan of teeth, and the size of a gap within a tooth row is determined by rate of tooth development. The width of a tooth band (the greatest number of overlapping rows along a line perpendicular to a row) is determined by the "phase shift" between waves of replacement in adjacent rows (the number of more lingual rows that begin before teeth are lost and a gap begins in the most labial row of that band).

If the phase shift between adjacent rows is slightly less than 180 degrees, only two rows will overlap (as in Pomacanthus, Fig. 4B; and Chaetodontoplus, Fig. 4C). If the phase shift is slightly less than 60 degrees, three rows will overlap (as in Chaetodon capistratus, Fig. 25A and B).

If the inferred process of tooth replacement is correct, the exact arrangement of teeth in a given individual would

be transient. Specifically, the positions and number of tooth rows and bands should go through cycles.

It is also evident that a strong allometry exists between the size of teeth and the size of the jaw. In small individuals, the teeth are relatively larger (e.g. C. aureofasciatus, 47 mm, Fig. 27A and B). Tooth diameter does not increase isometrically with growth of the jaw (compare C. rainfordi, 76 mm, Fig. 27C and D; C. rainfordi is a member of the same species complex). Therefore, more teeth are required to compose a row of proportionately equivalent length, and more rows are required fill the width of the jaw.

The cycle of tooth replacement and the allometry between tooth and jaw sizes are sources of variation within species. Care was taken not to confound these sources of variation with interspecific differences when jaw morphologies and tooth arrangements were compared among species.

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